

ROSIE

D7.4 Set of instructions supporting trainers in using the teaching materials

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Responsible Open Science in Europe

ROSIE

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ABSTRACT:	The deliverable includes instructions for trainers for training materials in responsible Open Science. There are five sets of instructions included: (1) social sciences, (2) humanities, (3) natural sciences, (4) health and life sciences, (5) citizen science. There are 8 Units in each set of instructions, including one of several activities. The training course is planned for 2 days.
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Responsible Open Science in Europe

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TRAINING MATERIALS for Responsible Open Science Part I: Social Sciences

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Introduction

The aim of the ROSIE Training Materials for Responsible Open Science is to learn how to practice Open Science (OS) responsibly and how to prevent research misconduct in the context of OS by providing necessary knowledge and developing specific skills and attitudes.

In the ROSIE Didactic Framework we have identified the following skills and attitudes necessary for responsible practising of OS in four domains: (i) local and global citizenship, (ii) personal and social responsibility, (iii) epistemic skills, and (iv) collaborative problem-solving.

Local and global citizenship

- awareness of the importance and social benefits of OS and citizen science in local and global contexts
- participation in ethics and integrity self-regulation of OS and citizen science community

Personal and social responsibility

- personal and professional responsibility for implementation of OS and production of results
- openness to share own research data, results, tools and publications and appreciation of efforts of others

Epistemic skills

- ability to organize, present and use open data and knowledge with integrity
- ability to critically assess data, knowledge and scientific results produced by others
- ability to identify ethical and integrity issues in OS

Collaborative problem-solving

- ability to apply critical thinking skills in collaborative analysis of ethical and integrity problems in OS
- discussing, finding solutions and making decisions to handle ethics and integrity issues within OS community

To achieve optimal results, the ROSIE training materials rely on several learning and teaching strategies: (i) collaborative problem solving; (ii) case-based activities; (iii) dialogical activities; (iv) transformative learning. More information about these teaching strategies you can find in the ROSIE Didactic Framework.

The training material consists of a trainers' file including 8 units and respective activities, as well as a separate folder including materials for trainees – required readings, handouts and printouts. The activities can be implemented separately (e.g., for organising a single workshop to discuss cases) or for organising a complete twodays training course. The suggested schedule for the training course is as follows:

Time	DAY 1	Type of activity
90 min.	Unit 1. Ethical and societal foundations of OS, its purpose	Home readings and Socratic seminar
15 min.	Break	
90 min.	Unit 2. Protection of research participants' rights in OS	Case discussion
60 min.	Lunch break	
90 min.	Unit 3. Ethical aspects of citizen science in the context of OS	Home readings and group project
15 min.	Break	
90 min.	Unit 4. Protection of intellectual property in the context of OS	Case discussion (Pro and Contra)
Time	DAY 2	Type of activity
90 min.	Unit 5. The quality of the research outputs and data sets	Home readings and case discussion OR Case discussion
15 min.	Break	
90 min.	Unit 6. Responsible sharing and reuse of open social science data	Brainstorming and group work OR Case discussion
60 min.	Lunch break	
90 min.	Unit 7. Prevention of research malpractice in the context of OS	Group work and plenary activity OR Case discussion
15 min.	Break	
90 min.	Unit 8. Responsible dissemination and publication practices	Case discussion (Four Quadrant Method)

Unit 1. Ethical and societal foundations of OS, its purpose

Activity 1. Principles, values and benefits of OS

DESCRIPTION

This activity starts with homework where trainees are asked to read [UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science](#) and fill in the double-entry reading journal. The purpose of the reading journal is to give trainees an opportunity to express their thoughts and reflect on the text. It is followed by classroom discussion in a form of Socratic seminar on principles and values of OS, as well as main benefits and challenges in OS implementation.

Type of activity: home readings and Socratic seminar

Time: 90 min.

Target groups: students, early career researchers, senior researchers **Learning outcomes:**

	Learning outcomes <i>It is expected that trainees will:</i>	Indicators for their achievement <i>Trainees who have fully met the learning outcome are able to:</i>
	- demonstrate knowledge of foundations of OS	- explain and discuss principles and values of OS, its ethical foundations, and social benefits
	- understand the significance of citizen science for identifying and solving societal challenges	- provide examples for role of OS and citizen science in identifying and solving scientific problems and societal challenges

PROCEDURE

1. At least a week before the workshop send trainees the required readings ([UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science](#), file “SC_U1A1 Readings UNESCO Recommendation”) and the handout (file “SC_U1A1 Handout”).
2. Before the workshop trainees are required to read the parts I., II. and III. of the [UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science](#) (pp. 6-19).

3. Before the workshop trainees should fill in the double-entry reading journal table in the handout. The left side should contain quotations from the UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science with page numbers noted. The right side should contain trainee's response to each quotation (a question, commentary, analysis). When filling in the table, trainees may use the following prompts, included in the handout:
 - *I agree/disagree with..., because...*
 - *It is not clear for me...*
 - *I see the following challenges...*
 - *I have a question regarding...*
4. The classroom discussion is organized as a Socratic seminar. The aim of the Socratic seminar is to achieve "*a deeper understanding about the ideas and values in a particular text*"¹. The trainer is facilitator of the discussion, the discussion is led by using open-ended, high-level questions. Trainees are sitting in a circle.
5. The Socratic Seminar starts with introduction of the rules:
 - Only those trainees who have read the text and filled in the double-entry reading journal are allowed to participate;
 - It is important to focus on the text and to refer to evidence from the text;
 - Trainees are encouraged to talk to each other, not just to the trainer and to listen and respond to others' arguments.
6. Common questions used during a Socratic Seminar activity both by trainer and trainees include:
 - *What does this concept/idea/phrase etc. mean?*
 - *What do you think the authors are trying to say?*
 - *Is this what you mean to say...?*
 - *What is the origin of this?*
 - *What are the implications of this?*
 - *What else could that mean?*
 - *What would happen if...?*
7. This [overview of Socratic seminar](#) provides a list of suitable questions and more information about how to prepare for a discussion.

¹ Castellanos-Reyes, D. (2020). Socratic Seminar. In R. Kimmons & S. Caskurlu (Eds.), *The Students' Guide to Learning Design and Research*. EdTech Books.

https://edtechbooks.org/studentguide/socratic_seminar

PLANNING**Resources and equipment:**

- Handout “SC_U1A1 Handout”
-
- Required readings “SC_U1A1 Readings UNESCO Recommendation”
 - Make space for the trainees to sit in a circle

FURTHER READINGS

1. Castellanos-Reyes, D. (2020). Socratic Seminar. In R. Kimmons & S. Caskurlu (Eds.), *The Students' Guide to Learning Design and Research*. EdTech Books.
https://edtechbooks.org/studentguide/socratic_seminar
2. Düwell, M. (2019). Open science and ethics. *Ethical Theory and Moral Practice*, 22(5), 1051-1053. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10677-019-10053-3>
3. Tennant, J. P., Waldner, F., Jacques, D. C., Masuzzo, P., Collister, L. B., & Hartgerink, C. H. (2016). The academic, economic and societal impacts of Open Access: an evidence-based review. *F1000Research*, 5.
<https://f1000research.com/articles/5-632/v3>

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Unit 2. Protection of research participants' rights in OS

Activity 2. Open sharing of sensitive qualitative data in social sciences

DESCRIPTION

This activity is built around case discussion. Trainees are asked to discuss in small groups cases on ethical issues in gathering, open sharing and reuse of sensitive qualitative data in social sciences. Afterwards, small groups report to the whole group and continue with a reflective discussion involving the whole group.

Type of activity: case discussion

Time: 90 min.

Target group: students, early career researchers, senior researchers **Learning outcomes:**

	Learning outcomes <i>It is expected that trainees will:</i>	Indicators for their achievement <i>Trainees who have fully met the learning outcome are able to:</i>
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - recognize and analyse the risk to research participants in the context of OS 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - discuss how to minimize risks to research participants when practicing OS
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - apply critical thinking skills - questioning, comparing, summarizing, drawing conclusions and defending - to case studies and integrity in OS 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - develop reflective questions to define ethical problems in the case study - discuss cases with colleagues - justify a personal position on the case

PROCEDURE

1. Depending on the size of the group and background of the trainees choose how many cases to discuss during the workshop. There are four cases included in the file "SC_U2A2 Handout". You can also choose to watch the Case 3 in the classroom - **animation of this case is available on the [ROSIE webpage](#).**

2. Print out the case descriptions and questions for discussion for each trainee (file “SC_U2A2 Handout”).
3. Introduce the activity, its aim and, briefly, the procedure.
4. Ask trainees to split in small groups (4-5 trainees in a group) and to choose a rapporteur - a group member who will report results of the small group discussion to the whole group. Provide each group with a paper for taking notes.
5. **Step 1:** small group discussions – **30 minutes**. Trainees read the case description and discuss the questions in small groups. Each group takes notes.
Rapporteurs prepare to present the results to the whole group.
6. **Step 2:** reports from small group discussions – **40 minutes**. Depending on the number of the small groups, allocate a time slot for each group presentation (e.g., if there are 4 small groups, each group have 10 minutes for a presentation). Rapporteurs present the results of their group discussions.
7. **Step 3:** group discussion – **20 minutes**. The trainer moderates a reflective group discussion. The trainer writes the solutions suggested during the discussion on the whiteboard and summarises them. Sample questions for reflective discussion are, e.g.:
 - *What are the specific ethical concerns related to archiving, open sharing and reuse of social media data?*
 - *What are specific requirements for open sharing of data collected from vulnerable research participants?*
 - *How to inform research participants about open sharing of data? What are specific requirements for informed consent or assent in the context of open sharing of data?*
 - *How to ensure privacy of research participants? Is it possible to anonymize qualitative data? If so, how?*

PLANNING

Resources and equipment:

- Handout “SC_U2A2 Handout” and/or video of case animation
- Paper for taking notes during small group discussions
- Whiteboard for discussion notes
- Make space for the trainees to work in small groups

FURTHER READINGS

1. Campbell, R., Goodman-Williams, R., & Javorka, M. (2019). A trauma-informed approach to sexual violence research ethics and open science. *Journal of interpersonal violence*, 34(23-24), 4765-4793. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0886260519871530>

2. DuBois, J. M., Strait, M., & Walsh, H. (2018). Is it time to share qualitative research data? *Qualitative Psychology*, 5(3), 380–393. <https://doi.org/10.1037/qap0000076>
3. Fox, J., Pearce, K. E., Massanari, A. L., Riles, J. M., Szulc, Ł., Ranjit, Y. S., ... & L. Gonzales, A. (2021). Open science, closed doors? Countering marginalization through an agenda for ethical, inclusive research in communication. *Journal of Communication*, 71(5), 764-784. <https://doi.org/10.1093/joc/jgab029>
4. VandeVusse, A., Mueller, J., & Karcher, S. (2022).

Qualitative Data Sharing:

Participant Understanding, Motivation, and Consent. *Qualitative Health Research*, 32(1), 182-191. <https://doi.org/10.1177/10497323211054058>

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Unit 3. Ethical aspects of citizen science in the context of OS

Activity 3. Development of an ethically sound citizen science project

DESCRIPTION

This activity involves home reading before the classroom activity, to introduce the concept of citizen science in the context of social sciences. It is followed by group project onsite where trainees are asked to develop their own citizen social science projects and analyse ethical aspects of these projects.

Type of activity: home readings and group project

Time: 90 min.

Target group: students, early career researchers, senior researchers **Learning outcomes:**

	Learning outcomes <i>It is expected that trainees</i>	Indicators for their achievement <i>Trainees who have fully met the learning</i> <i>outcome are able to:</i>
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> understand the significance of citizen science for identifying and solving scientific and societal challenges 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> provide examples for role of citizen science in identifying and solving scientific problems and societal challenges

PROCEDURE

- At least a week before the workshop send trainees the required readings (file "SC_U3A3 Readings Albert et. al 2021"²).
- During the workshop, introduce the group activity, its aim and, briefly, the procedure.
- Ask trainees to split in three groups. The group task is to develop an idea for a citizen social science project, by using definitions and examples provided in the

² Albert, A., Balázs, B., Butkevičienė, E., Mayer, K., & Perelló, J. (2021). Citizen social science: New and established approaches to participation in social research. *Chapter 7. In: Vohland K. et al. (Eds). 2021. The Science of Citizen Science. Springer. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-58278-4>. pp: 119-138.*

required readings. For taking notes print one copy of “Handout SC_U3A3” for each group.

4. **Step 1** development of the project idea – **30 minutes**. Each group should discuss and fill in the table 1 in the “SC_U3A3 Handout”.
5. **Step 2** reflection on ethical aspects of the project – **30 minutes**. Each group should discuss and fill in the table 2 in the “SC_U3A3 Handout”.
6. **Step 3** presentation of group projects and general discussion – **30 minutes**.
Sample questions for reflective discussion are, e.g.:
 - What does citizen social science add to the field of social sciences?
 - What are the main ethical challenges and their solutions in citizen social science projects?

PLANNING

Resources and equipment:

- Readings “SC_U3A3 Readings Albert et. al 2021”
- Handout “SC_U3A3 Handout”
- Make space for the trainees to work in small groups

FURTHER READINGS

1. Balázs, B., Mooney, P., Nováková, E., Bastin, L., Jokar Arsanjani, J. (2021). Data Quality in Citizen Science. In: *The Science of Citizen Science*. Springer https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-58278-4_8
2. López, M. P., Soekijad, M., Berends, H., & Huysman, M. (2020). A knowledge perspective on quality in complex citizen science. *Citizen Science: Theory and Practice*, 5(1). <http://doi.org/10.5334/cstp.250>
3. Mahr, D., Göbel, C., Irwin, A., & Vohland, K. (2018). Watching or being watched enhancing productive discussion between the citizen sciences, the social sciences and the humanities. UCL Press. <https://doi.org/10.14324/111.9781787352339>
4. Tauginienė, L., Butkevičienė, E., Vohland, K., Heinisch, B., Daskolia, M., Suškevičs, M., ... & Prūse, B. (2020). Citizen science in the social sciences and humanities: the power of interdisciplinarity. *Palgrave Communications*, 6(1), 1-11. <https://doi.org/10.1057/s41599-020-0471-y>

Unit 4. Protection of intellectual property in the context of OS

Activity 4. Authorship, contributorship and group coauthorship in citizen science

DESCRIPTION

This activity is built around case discussion and involves evaluating pro and contra arguments for different types of acknowledging citizen scientist contributions to research. Trainees are asked to discuss the case in small groups, develop and discuss their arguments. Afterwards, small groups report to the whole group and continue with a reflective discussion involving the whole group.

Type of activity: case discussion

Time: 90 min.

Target group: students, early career researchers, senior researchers **Learning outcomes:**

	Learning outcomes <i>It is expected that trainees will:</i>	Indicators for their achievement <i>Trainees who have fully met the learning outcome are able to:</i>
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> be aware of protection of intellectual property in OS 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> acknowledge authors and contributors of open data sets and other research outputs
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> be aware of citizen scientists' right to be recognized and acknowledged by academic scientists and society 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> discuss and assert their right to be recognized and acknowledged by academic scientists and society
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> apply critical thinking skills - questioning, comparing, summarizing, drawing conclusions and defending - to case studies ethics and integrity in OS 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> develop reflective questions to define ethical problems in the case study discuss cases with colleagues justify a personal position on the case

PROCEDURE

1. Introduce the activity, its aim and, briefly, the procedure.
2. Ask trainees to split in small groups (3-4 trainees in a group) and to choose a rapporteur - a group member who will report results of the small group discussion to the whole group.
3. Print out case description and questions for discussion for each trainee (file "SC_U4A4 Handout". You can also choose to watch the case in the classroom - **animation of this case is available on the [ROSiE webpage](#)**.
4. **Step 1:** small group discussions – **30 minutes**. Trainees read the case description and discuss the questions in small groups. Each group fills in the table included in the handout with pro and contra arguments. Rapporteurs prepare to present the results to the whole group.
5. **Step 2:** short reports from small group discussions – **20 minutes**. Rapporteurs present the results of their group discussions - pro and contra arguments for each type of acknowledging the contribution of citizen scientists in this case.
6. **Step 3:** group discussion – **40 minutes**. The trainer moderates a reflective group discussion. Sample questions for reflective discussion are, e.g.:
 - *Based on the pro and contra arguments developed during the group work, what is the best solution for this case?*
 - *Do you have other suggestions for recognizing the contribution of citizen scientists in scientific publications?*

PLANNING

Resources and equipment:

- Handout "SC_U4A4 Handout" and/or video of case animation
- Make space for the trainees to work in small groups

FURTHER READINGS

1. COPE Council (2003). How to Handle Authorship Disputes: A Guide for New Researchers. <https://doi.org/10.24318/cope.2018.1.1>
2. ICMJE. Defining the role of authors and contributors. <https://bit.ly/N7uog3>
3. Smith, E., Bélisle-Pipon, J. C., & Resnik, D. (2019). Patients as research partners; how to value their perceptions, contribution and labor? *Citizen science: theory and practice*, 4(1). <https://doi.org/10.5334/cstp.184>
4. The Embassy of Good Science: "[Authorship criteria](#)"
5. Vasilevsky, N. A. et al. (2021). Is authorship sufficient for today's collaborative research? A call for contributor roles. *Accountability in Research*, 28(1), 23-43. <https://doi.org/10.1080/08989621.2020.1779591>

Activity 4.1. Inequities and potential of exploitation in OS

DESCRIPTION

This activity is built around case discussion. Trainees are asked to discuss in small groups a case on ethical issues on protection of intellectual property in OS in the context of low- and middle- income countries. Afterwards, small groups report to the whole group and continue with a reflective discussion involving the whole group.

Type of activity: case discussion

Time: 90 min.

Target group: students, early career researchers, senior researchers **Learning outcomes:**

	Learning outcomes <i>It is expected that trainees will:</i>	Indicators for their achievement <i>Trainees who have fully met the learning outcome are able to:</i>
	– be aware of protection of intellectual property in OS	– acknowledge authors and contributors of
	– apply critical thinking skills - questioning, comparing, summarizing, drawing conclusions, and defending - to case studies on ethics and integrity in OS	– develop reflective questions to define ethical position on the case – –

PROCEDURE

1. Introduce the activity, its aim and, briefly, the procedure.
2. Ask trainees to split in small groups (3-4 trainees in a group) and to choose a rapporteur - a group member who will report results of the small group discussion to the whole group.
3. Print out the case description and questions for discussion for each trainee (file “SC_U4A4.1 Handout”).
4. **Step 1:** small group discussions – **30 minutes**. Trainees read the case description and discuss the questions in small groups. Rapporteurs prepare to present the results to the whole group.
5. **Step 2:** short reports from small group discussions – **30 minutes**. Rapporteurs present the results of their group discussions.
6. **Step 3:** group discussion – **30 minutes**. The trainer moderates a reflective group discussion. Sample questions for reflective discussion are, e.g.:

- Based on the arguments developed during the group work, what are the best approaches for protection of intellectual property in the context of open sharing of data and other research outputs?
- Do you have other suggestions for recognizing the contribution of authors of open datasets, methods etc.?

PLANNING

Resources and equipment:

- Handout “SC_U4A4.1 Handout”
- Make space for the trainees to work in small groups

FURTHER READINGS

1. Bull, S., & Bhagwandin, N. (2020). The ethics of data sharing and biobanking in health research. *Wellcome Open Research*, 5. <https://doi.org/10.12688/wellcomeopenres.16351.1>
2. Ross-Hellauer, T., Reichmann, S., Cole, N. L., Fessl, A., Klebel, T., & Pontika, N. (2022). Dynamics of cumulative advantage and threats to equity in open science: a scoping review. *Royal Society Open Science*, 9(1), 211032. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rsos.211032>
3. Vasilevsky, N. A. et al. (2021). Is authorship sufficient for today’s collaborative research? A call for contributor roles. *Accountability in Research*, 28(1), 23-43. <https://doi.org/10.1080/08989621.2020.1779591>
4. Zeitlyn, D. (2003). Gift economies in the development of open source software: anthropological reflections. *Research Policy*, 32(7), 1287-1291. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0048-7333\(03\)00053-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0048-7333(03)00053-2)

Unit 5. The quality of the research outputs and data sets

Activity 5. Responsibility for the quality of research data

DESCRIPTION

This activity starts with homework where trainees are asked to read a paper on data quality in citizen science and create a mind map. The purpose of the mind map is to build a background knowledge for case discussion. It is followed by case discussion and development of guidelines for ensuring quality of citizen social sciences data.

Type of activity: home reading and case discussion **Time:** 90 min.

Target group: students, early career researchers **Learning outcomes:**

	Learning outcomes <i>It is expected that trainees will:</i>	Indicators for their achievement <i>Trainees who have fully met the learning outcome are able to:</i>
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> aware of importance of the data sets and research output and their responsible use 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> explain how to responsibly and critically assess and use open data and research outputs
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> apply critical thinking skills - questioning, comparing, summarizing, drawing conclusions and defending - to case studies and integrity in OS 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> develop reflective questions to define ethical problems in the case study discuss cases with colleagues justify a personal position on the case

PROCEDURE

1. At least a week before the workshop send trainees the required readings (file “SC_U5A5 Readings Balazs et al 2021”) and the handout for creating a mind map (file “SC_U5A5.1 Handout”).
2. Before the workshop trainees are required to read the required readings “SC_U5A5 Readings Balazs et. al 2021”³.

³ Balázs, B., Mooney, P., Nováková, E., Bastin, L., Jokar Arsanjani, J. (2021). Data Quality in Citizen Science. In: The Science of Citizen Science. Springer https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-582784_8.

3. Before the workshop trainees should create a mind map on quality of data in citizen science, based on the required readings. Instructions for creating a mind map are included in the handout “SC_U5A5_1 Handout”.
4. In the classroom, introduce the activity, its aim and, briefly, the procedure.
5. Ask trainees to split in small groups (4-6 trainees in a group) and to choose a rapporteur - a group member who will report results of the small group discussion to the whole group.
6. Print out the case description (file “SC_U5A5_2 Handout”) for each trainee

- Step 1:** small group discussions – **40 minutes**. Trainees read the case description, discuss the challenges, use the ideas from required readings and develop recommendations. Each group fills in a table with challenges and recommendations. The table is included in the “SC_U5A5_2 Handout”.

Rapporteurs prepare to present the results to the whole group.

- Step 2:** reports from small group discussions – **30 minutes**. Depending on the number of the small groups, allocate a time slot for each group presentation (e.g., if there are 3 small groups, each group have 10 minutes for a presentation). Rapporteurs present the results of their group discussions.
- Step 3:** group discussion – **20 minutes**. The trainer moderates a reflective group discussion. Sample questions for reflective discussion are, e.g.:
 - Which ideas from the required readings helped you to develop recommendations? How?
 - Which of the recommendations developed during the groupwork are the most useful? Why?
 - In your view, what are other considerable ethical challenges for social scientists collaborating with citizen scientists? How to address these challenges?

PLANNING

Resources and equipment:

- Required readings “SC_U5A5 Readings Balazs et. al 2021”
- Handout “SC_U5A5.1 Handout” for home reading and creating a mind map
- Handout “SC_U5A5_2 Handout” for case discussion
- Make space for the trainees to work in small groups

FURTHER READINGS

- Haklay, M. (2021). Why is it so difficult to integrate citizen science into practice? *Citizen Science and Public Policy Making*, 108.
<https://discovery.ucl.ac.uk/id/eprint/10130136>

Activity 5.1. Conflicts of interest

DESCRIPTION

This activity is built around case discussion. Trainees are asked to discuss in small groups a case on risk conflicts of interest in citizen science. Afterwards, small groups report to the whole group and continue with a reflective discussion involving the whole group.

Type of activity: case discussion

Time: 90 min.

Target group: early career researchers, senior researchers **Learning outcomes:**

	Learning outcomes <i>It is expected that trainees will:</i>	Indicators for their achievement <i>Trainees who have fully met the learning outcome are able to:</i>
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> understand the concept of conflict of interest and how to deal with it 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> recognize and disclose conflicts of interest in cases when citizen scientists have personal or political interests at stake
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> apply critical thinking skills - questioning, comparing, summarizing, drawing conclusions and defending - to case studies and integrity in OS 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> develop reflective questions to define ethical problems in the case study discuss cases with colleagues justify a personal position on the case

PROCEDURE

1. Print out the case description and questions for discussion for each trainee (file "SC_U5A5.1 Handout"). You can also choose to watch the case in the classroom - **animation of this case is available on the [ROSIE webpage](#).**
2. Introduce the activity, its aim and, briefly, the procedure.
3. Ask trainees to split in small groups (4-5 trainees in a group) and to choose a rapporteur - a group member who will report results of the small group discussion to the whole group. Provide each group with a paper for taking notes.
4. **Step 1:** small group discussions – **30 minutes**. Trainees read the case description and discuss the questions in small groups. Each group takes notes.
Rapporteurs prepare to present the results to the whole group.
5. **Step 2:** reports from small group discussions – **30 minutes**. Depending on the number of the small groups, allocate a time slot for each group presentation (e.g., if there are 4 small groups, each group have 10 minutes for a presentation). Rapporteurs present the results of their group discussions.
6. **Step 3:** group discussion – **30 minutes**. The trainer moderates a reflective group discussion. The trainer writes the solutions suggested during the discussion on the whiteboard and summarises them. Sample questions for reflective discussion are, e.g.:

- What is your personal experience with conflicts of interest in research?
- What types of conflicts of interests should be disclosed? Is there a consensus on that in your field of science?
- Do potential conflicts of interest in citizen science differ from potential conflicts of interest in science in general? If yes, what is the difference?
- How to deal with conflicts of interest in cases where they are discovered after the publication of a research study?

PLANNING

Resources and equipment:

- Handout "SC_U5A5.1 Handout" and/or video of case animation
- Paper for taking notes during small group discussions
- Whiteboard for discussion notes
- Make space for the trainees to work in small groups

FURTHER READINGS

1. COPE Council (2021). COPE Flowcharts and infographics: Undisclosed conflict of interest in a published article. <https://doi.org/10.24318/cope.2019.2.7>
2. Macey, G. P., Breech, R., Chernaik, M., Cox, C., Larson, D., Thomas, D., & Carpenter, D. O. (2014). Air concentrations of volatile compounds near oil and gas production: a community-based exploratory study. *Environmental Health*, 13(1), 1-18. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1476-069X-13-82>
3. Resnik, D. B., Konecny, B., & Kissling, G. E. (2017). Conflict of interest and funding disclosure policies of environmental, occupational, and public health journals. *Journal of occupational and environmental medicine*, 59(1), 28. <https://doi.org/10.1097/JOM.0000000000000910>
4. The Embassy of Good Science: "[Conflict of interests](#)", "[Intellectual conflicts of interest](#)"

Unit 6. Responsible sharing and reuse of open social science data

Activity 6. Concerns to share and reuse data

DESCRIPTION

This activity starts with brainstorming where trainees are asked to share their views on sharing and reusing research data. It is followed by group discussion on concerns to share and reuse data, as well as possible solutions. **Type of activity:** brainstorming and group discussion

Time: 90 min.

Target group: students, early career researchers **Learning outcomes:**

	Learning outcomes <i>It is expected that trainees</i>	Indicators for their achievement <i>will: Trainees who have fully met the learning outcome</i>
	- be aware about factors influencing willingness to share and use research data	- discuss how to increase willingness to open

PROCEDURE

- Step 1: brainstorming – 15 minutes.** The trainer starts brainstorming by posing two questions: (1) “Are you ready to share your research data in an open data repository? Why yes or no?” and (2) “Are you ready to use open access data in your research? Why yes or no?” and invite trainees to take a minute’s silence to think on it. Once the minute is up, invite everyone to share their views. Have a single person (trainer or one of trainees) who takes notes on a whiteboard. The main aim of brainstorming is just to listen to different views without criticism.
- Ask trainees to split in small groups (4-6 trainees in a group) and to choose a rapporteur - a group member who will report results of the small group discussion to the whole group.
- Distribute the handout (file “Handout SC_U6A6”) to each group. Half of the groups receive Task 1 from the handout (“Sharing your own research data”), other groups get Task 2 from the handout (“Using open data created by other researchers”).
- Step 2: small group discussions – 30 minutes.** Trainees discuss and fill in a table with concerns and possible solutions. Rapporteurs prepare to present the results to the whole group.
- Step 3: reports from small group discussions – 30 minutes.** Depending on the number of the small groups, allocate a time slot for each group presentation (e.g., if there are 3 small groups, each group have 10 minutes for a presentation). Rapporteurs present the results of their group discussions.
- Step 3: group discussion – 15 minutes.** The trainer moderates a reflective group discussion. Sample questions for reflective discussion are, e.g.:
 - *What are the most important concerns discouraging researchers to share their data for reuse and to use open data created by other researchers? What are possible solutions?*

- How to responsibly share and reuse quantitative data in social sciences? Is it possible to responsibly share and reuse qualitative data? How?

PLANNING

Resources and equipment:

- Handout “SC_U6A6 Handout” printed out for each small group
- Whiteboard for discussion notes
- Make space for the trainees to work in small groups

FURTHER READINGS

1. Zuiderwijk, A., Shinde, R., & Jeng, W. (2020). What drives and inhibits researchers to share and use open research data? A systematic literature review to analyze factors influencing open research data adoption. *PloS one*, 15(9), e0239283.
<https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0239283>

Activity 6.1. Case discussion on concerns about sharing the data

DESCRIPTION

This activity is built around case discussion. Trainees are asked to discuss in small groups cases on scientists’ concerns to share the data. Afterwards, small groups report to the whole group and continue with a reflective discussion involving the whole group. **Type of activity:** case discussion

Time: 90 min.

Target group: early career researchers, senior researchers **Learning outcomes:**

	Learning outcomes <i>It is expected that trainees will:</i>	Indicators for their achievement <i>Trainees who have fully met the learning outcome are able to:</i>
	- be aware of factors influencing willingness to share and use open research data	- discuss how to increase willingness to share and use open research data
	- apply critical thinking skills - questioning, comparing, summarizing, drawing conclusions and defending - to case studies and integrity in OS	- develop reflective questions to define ethical problems in the case study - discuss cases with colleagues - justify a personal position on the case

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PROCEDURE

1. Depending on the size of the group and background of the trainees choose how many cases to discuss during the workshop. There are four cases included in the file “SC_U6A6.1 Handout”. You can also choose to watch two of the cases in the classroom - **animations of cases are available on the [ROSiE webpage](#)**.
2. Introduce the activity, its aim and, briefly, the procedure.
3. Ask trainees to split in small groups (4-5 trainees in a group) and to choose a rapporteur - a group member who will report results of the small group discussion to the whole group. Provide each group with a paper for taking notes.
4. Print out case description(s) and questions for discussion for each trainee (file “SC_U6A6.1 Handout”).
5. **Step 1:** small group discussions – **30 minutes**. Trainees read the case description and discuss the questions in small groups. Each group takes notes. Rapporteurs prepare to present the results to the whole group.
6. **Step 2:** reports from small group discussions – **40 minutes**. Depending on the number of the small groups, allocate a time slot for each group presentation (e.g., if there are 4 small groups, each group have 10 minutes for a presentation). Rapporteurs present the results of their group discussions.
7. **Step 3:** group discussion – **20 minutes**. The trainer moderates a reflective group discussion. The trainer writes the solutions suggested during the discussion on the whiteboard and summarises them. Sample questions for reflective discussion are, e.g.:
 - *What are the most important concerns discouraging researchers to share their data for reuse and to use open data created by other researchers? What are possible solutions?*
 - *Are there any legitimate reasons not to share research data?*
 - *How to responsibly share and reuse data in social sciences?*

PLANNING

Resources and equipment:

- Handout “SC_U6A6.1 Handout” and/or animations of cases available on ROSiE webpage
- Paper for taking notes during small group discussions
- Whiteboard for discussion notes

- Make space for the trainees to work in small groups

FURTHER READINGS

1. Gewin, V. (2016.) Data sharing: An open mind on open data. *Nature* 529.
<https://doi.org/10.1038/nj7584-117a>
2. Laine, H. (2017). Afraid of scooping: Case study on researcher strategies against fear of scooping in the context of open science. *Data Science Journal*.
<https://doi.org/10.5334/dsj-2017-029>
3. Staunton, C., Barragán, C. A., Canali, S., Ho, C., Leonelli, S., Mayernik, M., ... & Wonkham, A. (2021). Open science, data sharing and solidarity: who benefits? *History and Philosophy of the Life Sciences*, 43(4), 115.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s40656-021-00468-6>
4. Zuiderwijk, A., Shinde, R., & Jeng, W. (2020). What drives and inhibits researchers to share and use open research data? A systematic literature review to analyze factors influencing open research data adoption. *PloS one*, 15(9), e0239283.
<https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0239283>

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Unit 7. Prevention of research malpractice in the context of OS

Activity 7. Violations of research integrity in OS and their prevention

DESCRIPTION

The activity aims to discuss different types of violations of research integrity in OS and their prevention. The trainees are split into five groups and their task is to reflect on potential type of violation and preventive measure in each particular type of Open Science activity. Each group shares the results of their discussions, and group work is followed by plenary activity where all trainees have an opportunity to supplement the results of group work.

Type of activity: group work and plenary activity

Time: 90 minutes

Target group: students, early career researchers, senior researchers **Learning outcomes:**

	Learning outcomes <i>It is expected that trainees will:</i>	Indicators for their achievement <i>Trainees who have fully met the learning outcome are able to:</i>
	– know potential types of research malpractice in the context of OS	– discuss causes of violations of research integrity in OS and ways of its prevention

PROCEDURE

- Before to the exercise, print out the pages with different types of Open Science activities (file “SC_U7A7 Printout”) and mark sections of a wall with the titles:
 - *Open access publishing*
 - *Sharing and using open data*
 - *Open reproducible research, e.g., open lab notes, reproducing of research studies*
 - *Open science evaluation, e.g., open metrics and impact, open peer review – Citizen science*
- Ask participants to split in five groups. Assign one of the types of Open Science activities listed above to each group.
- Step 1:** group discussion – **25 minutes**. Each group discusses the following questions in the context of the particular type of Open Science activities:

- *What potential violations of research integrity may arise in the context of this type of open science activities?*
- *How to prevent these potential violations?*

The results of the discussion should be written on paper cards/sticky notes – one potential type of violation and preventive measure on each card/sticky note and hanged on the wall under the respective type of Open Science activities.

4. **Step 2:** group work presentations and general discussion – **65 minutes**. Each group presents their results in 5 minutes. After each presentation there is 8 minutes general discussion where every trainee has an opportunity to suggest additional challenges and preventive measures. These additional challenges and preventive measures are written on paper cards/sticky notes and added to the respective type of Open Science activities.

PLANNING

Resources and equipment:

- Printout “SC_U7A7 Printout”
- Large wall or multiple pinboards to hang on printouts and results of discussions
- Empty cards & tape/sticky notes, pens/markers
- Make space for the trainees to work in small groups and to move around

FURTHER READINGS

1. Düwell, M. (2019). Open science and ethics. *Ethical Theory and Moral Practice*, 22, 1051-1053. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10677-019-10053-3>

Activity 7.1. Should scientists use access to pirated papers?

DESCRIPTION

This activity is built around case discussion. Trainees are asked to discuss in small groups a case on violations of intellectual property rights. Afterwards, small groups report to the whole group and continue with a reflective discussion involving the whole group.

Type of activity: case discussion

Time: 90 minutes

Target group: students, early career researchers, senior researchers **Learning outcomes:**

Learning outcomes	Indicators for their achievement
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	It is expected that trainees will:	Trainees who have fully met the learning outcome are able to:
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> know potential types of research practice in OS 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> discuss causes of violations of research integrity in OS and ways of its prevention recognise limits of OS for protection of data and intellectual property rights

PROCEDURE

1. Print out the case description and questions for discussion for each trainee (file "SC_U7A7.1 Handout". You can also choose to watch the case in the classroom - **animation of this case is available on the [ROSIE webpage](#)**.
2. Introduce the activity, its aim and, briefly, the procedure.
3. Ask trainees to split in small groups (4-5 trainees in a group) and to choose a rapporteur - a group member who will report results of the small group discussion to the whole group. Provide each group with a paper for taking notes.
4. **Step 1:** small group discussions – **30 minutes**. Trainees read the case description and discuss the questions in small groups. Each group takes notes. Rapporteurs prepare to present the results to the whole group.
5. **Step 2:** reports from small group discussions – **30 minutes**. Depending on the number of the small groups, allocate a time slot for each group presentation (e.g., if there are 4 small groups, each group have 10 minutes for a presentation). Rapporteurs present the results of their group discussions.
6. **Step 3:** group discussion – **30 minutes**. The trainer moderates a reflective group discussion. The trainer writes the solutions suggested during the discussion on the whiteboard and summarises them. Sample questions for reflective discussion are, e.g.:
 - *How important are intellectual property rights for scientific research and achievements?*
 - *Does the case address a relevant issue for you and researchers you are working together?*
 - *What are potential solutions at the policy level to the problem described in the case?*

PLANNING

Resources and equipment:

- Handout "SC_U7A7.1 Handout" and/or video of case animation
- Paper for taking notes during small group discussions

- Whiteboard for discussion notes
- Make space for the trainees to work in small groups

FURTHER READINGS

1. Monbiot, G. Scientific publishing is a rip-off. We fund the research - it should be free. *The Guardian*. 13.09. 2018.
<https://www.theguardian.com/commentisfree/2018/sep/13/scientificpublishing-rip-off-taxpayers-fund-research>. Accessed August 2, 2022.
2. Van Noorden, R. (2016). Alexandra Elbakyan: Paper pirate. *Nature*, 540, 512.
<https://www.nature.com/articles/540507a>
3. Vogel, G., & Kupferschmidt, K. (2017). A bold open-access push in Germany could change the future of academic publishing. *Science*, 23.
<https://www.science.org/content/article/bold-open-access-push-germany-couldchange-future-academic-publishing>

Unit 8. Responsible dissemination and publication practices

Activity 8. Open access publishing and predatory practices

DESCRIPTION

This activity applies the Four Quadrant Method for case analysis on predatory practices. Trainees are asked to discuss a case in small groups and fill in the four quadrant template. Afterwards, small groups report to the whole group and continue with a casuistic reasoning and justification discussion involving the whole group.

Type of activity: case discussion (Four Quadrant Method)

Time: 90 min.

Target group: students, early career researchers, senior researchers **Learning outcomes:**

Learning outcomes	Indicators for their achievement
It is expected that trainees will:	Trainees who have fully met the learning

		outcome are able to:
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> know criteria for good practice standards in open access publishing 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> critically assess scientific results published in open access and identify predatory publishing practices
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> apply critical thinking skills - questioning, comparing, summarizing, drawing conclusions and defending - to case studies and integrity in OS 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> develop reflective questions to define ethical problems in the case study discuss cases with colleagues justify a personal position on the case

PROCEDURE

1. Introduce the activity, its aim and, briefly, the procedure of the Four Quadrant Method⁴.
2. Print out the case description (file “SC_U8A8 Handout”) for each trainee.

⁴ Detailed description of the modified Four Quadrant Method for case analysis is provided by the EnTIRE project: Armond A.C. et al. (2019). D.5.3 Delivery of the entire set of case deliberation methods and case analyses as input for the platform, pp. 98-102. Available:

<https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/documents/downloadPublic?documentIds=080166e5c3a7e938&applied=PPGMS>

3. Ask trainees to split in small groups (3-4 trainees in a group) and to choose a rapporteur - a group member who will report results of the small group discussion to the whole group.
4. **Step 1. Initial perception – 20 minutes.** Trainees read the case and in small groups discuss some general questions to identify relevant aspects of the case:
 - *What are the ethical issues at stake in this case?*
 - *Who are the stakeholders?*
 - *How should stakeholders react to this case?*
 - *What should/can stakeholders do to prevent such cases?*
5. **Step 2. The Four Quadrant Analysis – 20 minutes.** Each group fills in the four quadrant table included in the file “SC_U8A8 Handout”.

I. Relevant Facts: What are the most relevant facts concerning the situation?

II. Uncertainties: Which features of the situation are uncertain, lacking in clarity, or controversial?

III. **Courses of Action:** What are the practically available options for providing a solution to the case (how to react to the case and how to prevent such cases in the future)?

IV. **Contextual Features:** What legal, financial and institutional policies and regulations apply to the case?

6. **Step 3.** Reports from small groups – **20 minutes.** The small groups report the results of the Four Quadrant Analysis to the whole group.
7. **Step 4.** Casuistic Reasoning and Justification – **30 minutes.** The trainer moderates the whole group discussion on the following questions:
 - *What is at issue? What is the major ethical issue at the case?*
 - *Do you know other cases like this one?*
 - *Why do academics publish their research in a predatory journal or books published by predatory publishers? What are the main factors that motivate such a practice? What are negative consequences of such a practice? What policies might minimise predatory publishing practices?*
 - *How should stakeholders react to cases like this?*

PLANNING

Resources and equipment:

- Handout “SC_U8A8 Handout”
- Make space for the trainees to work in small groups

FURTHER READINGS

1. Kurt, S. (2018). Why do authors publish in predatory journals? *Learned Publishing*, 31(2), 141-147. <https://doi.org/10.1002/leap.1150>
2. Heimstädt, M., & Dobusch, L. (2020). To address the rise of predatory publishing in the social sciences, journals need to experiment with open peer review. *Impact of Social Sciences Blog*. <https://blogs.lse.ac.uk/impactofsocialsciences/2020/01/10/to-address-the-rise-of-predatory-publishing-in-the-social-sciences-journals-need-to-experiment-with-open-peer-review/>

Activity 8.1. Open peer review

DESCRIPTION

This activity is built around case discussion. Trainees are asked to discuss in small groups a case on open peer review. Afterwards, small groups report to the whole group and continue with a reflective discussion involving the whole group.

Type of activity: case discussion

Time: 90 min.

Target group: early career researchers, senior researchers **Learning outcomes:**

	Learning outcomes <i>It is expected that trainees will:</i>	Indicators for their achievement <i>Trainees who have fully met the learning outcome are able to:</i>
	- be aware of importance of open peer view practices	- explain how to responsibly and critically p
	- apply critical thinking skills - questioning, comparing, summarizing, drawing conclusions, and defending - to case studies on ethics and integrity in OS	- develop reflective questions to define eth position on the case - -

PROCEDURE

1. Introduce the activity, its aim and, briefly, the procedure.
2. Ask trainees to split in small groups (4-5 trainees in a group) and to choose a rapporteur - a group member who will report results of the small group discussion to the whole group. Provide each group with a paper for taking notes.
3. Print out case description and questions for discussion for each trainee (file "SC_U8A8.1 Handout").
4. **Step 1:** small group discussions – **30 minutes**. Trainees read the case description and discuss the questions in small groups. Each group takes notes. Rapporteurs prepare to present the results to the whole group.
5. **Step 2:** reports from small group discussions – **40 minutes**. Depending on the number of the small groups, allocate a time slot for each group presentation (e.g., if there are 4 small groups, each group has 10 minutes for a presentation).
Rapporteurs present the results of their group discussions.

6. **Step 3:** group discussion – **20 minutes**. The trainer moderates a reflective group discussion. The trainer writes the ideas suggested during the discussion on the whiteboard and summarise them. Sample questions for reflective discussion are, e.g.:
- *What is the role of open peer review in the scientific publishing process?*
 - *What are the benefits and risks of open peer review?*

PLANNING

Resources and equipment:

- Handout “SC_U8A8.1 Handout”
- Paper for taking notes during small group discussions
- Whiteboard for discussion notes
- Make space for the trainees to work in small groups

FURTHER READINGS

1. Harms, P. D., & Credé, M. (2020). Bringing the review process into the 21st century: Post-publication peer review. *Industrial and Organizational Psychology*, 13(1), 51-53. <https://doi.org/10.1017/iop.2020.13>
2. Ross-Hellauer, T., Deppe, A., & Schmidt, B. (2017). Survey on open peer review: Attitudes and experience amongst editors, authors and reviewers. *PloS One*, 12(12), e0189311. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0189311>
3. Tenorio-Fornés, Á., Tirador, E. P., Sánchez-Ruiz, A. A., & Hassan, S. (2021). Decentralizing science: Towards an interoperable open peer review ecosystem using blockchain. *Information Processing & Management*, 58(6), 102724. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ipm.2021.102724>
4. The Embassy of Good Science: “[Post-publication peer review](#)”
5. The Embassy of Good Science: “[Open peer review - transparent way of gatekeeping science](#)”

ROSIE

TRAINING MATERIALS for Responsible Open Science Part II: Humanities

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Introduction

The aim of the ROSIE Training Materials for Responsible Open Science is to learn how to practice Open Science (OS) responsibly and how to prevent research misconduct in the context of OS by providing necessary knowledge and developing specific skills and attitudes.

In the ROSIE Didactic Framework we have identified the following skills and attitudes necessary for responsible practising of OS in four domains: (i) local and global citizenship, (ii) personal and social responsibility, (iii) epistemic skills, and (iv) collaborative problem-solving.

Local and global citizenship

- awareness of the importance and social benefits of OS and citizen science in local and global contexts
- participation in ethics and integrity self-regulation of OS and citizen science community

Personal and social responsibility

- personal and professional responsibility for implementation of OS and production of results
- openness to share own research data, results, tools and publications and appreciation of efforts of others

Epistemic skills

- ability to organize, present and use open data and knowledge with integrity
- ability to critically assess data, knowledge and scientific results produced by others
- ability to identify ethical and integrity issues in OS

Collaborative problem-solving

- ability to apply critical thinking skills in collaborative analysis of ethical and integrity problems in OS
- discussing, finding solutions and making decisions to handle ethics and integrity issues within OS community

To achieve optimal results, the ROSIE training materials rely on several learning and teaching strategies: (i) collaborative problem solving; (ii) case-based activities; (iii) dialogical activities; (iv) transformative learning. More information about these teaching strategies you can find in the ROSIE Didactic Framework.

The training material consists of a trainers' file including 8 units and respective activities, as well as a separate folder including materials for trainees – required readings, handouts and printouts. The activities can be implemented separately (e.g., for organising a single workshop to discuss cases) or for organising a complete twodays training course. The suggested schedule for the training course is as follows:

Time	DAY 1	Type of activity
90 min.	Unit 1. Ethical and societal foundations of OS, its purpose	Home readings and Socratic seminar
15 min.	Break	
90 min.	Unit 2. Protection of research participants and cultural heritage in OS	Case discussion
60 min.	Lunch break	
90 min.	Unit 3. Ethical aspects of citizen science in the context of OS	Home readings and group project
15 min.	Break	
90 min.	Unit 4. Protection of intellectual property in the context of OS	Case discussion (Pro and Contra)
Time	DAY 2	Type of activity
90 min.	Unit 5. The quality of the research outputs and data sets	Home readings and case discussion
15 min.	Break	
90 min.	Unit 6. Responsible sharing and use of open humanities data	Case discussion
60 min.	Lunch break	
90 min.	Unit 7. Prevention of research malpractice in the context of OS	Group work and plenary activity OR Case discussion
15 min.	Break	
90 min.	Unit 8. Responsible dissemination and publication practices	Case discussion (Four Quadrant Method)

Unit 1. Ethical and societal foundations of OS, its purpose

Activity 1. Principles, values and benefits of OS

DESCRIPTION

This activity starts with homework where trainees are asked to read [UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science](#) and fill in the double-entry reading journal. The purpose of the reading journal is to give trainees an opportunity to express their thoughts and reflect on the text. It is followed by classroom discussion in a form of Socratic seminar on principles and values of OS, as well as main benefits and challenges in OS implementation.

Type of activity: home reading and Socratic seminar

Time: 90 min.

Target groups: students, early career researchers, senior researchers **Learning outcomes:**

Learning outcomes <i>It is expected that trainees will:</i>	Indicators for their achievement <i>Trainees who have fully met the learning outcome are able to:</i>
- demonstrate knowledge of foundations of OS	- explain and discuss principles and values of OS, its ethical foundations, and social benefits
- understand the significance of citizen science for identifying and solving societal challenges	- provide examples for role of OS and citizen science in identifying and solving scientific problems and societal challenges

PROCEDURE

1. At least a week before the workshop send trainees the required readings ([UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science](#), file "HU_U1A1 Readings UNESCO Recommendation") and the handout (file "HU_U1A1 Handout").
2. Before the workshop trainees are required to read the parts I., II. and III. of the [UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science](#) (pp. 6-19).
3. Before the workshop trainees should fill in the double-entry reading journal table in the handout. The left side should contain quotations from the UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science with page numbers noted. The right side should contain trainee's response to each quotation (a question, commentary, analysis). When filling in the table, trainees may use the following prompts, included in the handout:
 - *I agree/disagree with..., because...*
 - *It is not clear for me...*
 - *I see the following challenges...*

- *I have a question regarding...*
4. The classroom discussion is organized as a Socratic seminar. The aim of the Socratic seminar is to achieve “*a deeper understanding about the ideas and values in a particular text*”². The trainer is facilitator of the discussion, the discussion is led by using open-ended, high-level questions. Trainees are sitting in a circle.
 5. The Socratic Seminar starts with introduction of the rules:
 - Only those trainees who have read the text and filled in the double-entry reading journal are allowed to participate;
 - It is important to focus on the text and to refer to evidence from the text;
 - Trainees are encouraged to talk to each other, not just to the trainer and to listen and respond to others’ arguments.
 6. Common questions used during a Socratic Seminar activity both by trainer and trainees include:
 - *What does this concept/idea/phrase etc. mean?*
 - *What do you think the authors are trying to say?*
 - *Is this what you mean to say...?*
 - *What is the origin of this?*
 - *What are the implications of this?*
 - *What else could that mean?* -
 - *What would happen if...?*
 7. This [overview of Socratic seminar](#) provides a list of suitable questions and more information about how to prepare for a discussion.

PLANNING

Resources and equipment:

- Handout “HU_U1A1 Handout”
- Required readings “HU_U1A1 Readings UNESCO Recommendation”
- Make space for the trainees to sit in a circle

FURTHER READINGS

1. Castellanos-Reyes, D. (2020). Socratic Seminar. In R. Kimmons & S. Caskurlu (Eds.), *The Students' Guide to Learning Design and Research*. EdTech Books.
https://edtechbooks.org/studentguide/socratic_seminar

² Castellanos-Reyes, D. (2020). Socratic Seminar. In R. Kimmons & S. Caskurlu (Eds.), *The Students' Guide to Learning Design and Research*. EdTech Books.

https://edtechbooks.org/studentguide/socratic_seminar

2. Düwell, M. (2019). Open science and ethics. *Ethical Theory and Moral Practice*, 22(5), 1051-1053. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10677-019-10053-3>
3. Longley Arthur, P., & Hearn, L. (2021). Toward open research: A narrative review of the challenges and opportunities for open humanities. *Journal of Communication*, 71(5), 827-853. <https://doi.org/10.1093/joc/iqab028>
4. Tennant, J. P., Waldner, F., Jacques, D. C., Masuzzo, P., Collister, L. B., & Hartgerink, C. H. (2016). The academic, economic and societal impacts of Open Access: an evidence-based review. *F1000Research*, 5. <https://f1000research.com/articles/5-632/v3>

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Unit 2. Protection of research participants and cultural heritage in OS

Activity 2. Open sharing of sensitive qualitative data

DESCRIPTION

This activity is built around case discussion. Trainees are asked to discuss in small groups one or two cases on ethical issues in gathering, sharing and reuse of sensitive qualitative data, like life stories and social media data, in humanities. Afterwards, small groups report to the whole group and continue with a reflective discussion involving the whole group.

Type of activity: case discussion

Target group: students, early career researchers, senior researchers **Learning outcomes:**

	Learning outcomes <i>It is expected that trainees will:</i>	Indicators for their achievement <i>Trainees who have fully met the learning outcome are able to:</i>
	- cognize and analyse the risk search participants in the co r r OS o	to - discuss how to minimize risks to research participants when practicing OS
	- apply critical thinking skills - questioning, comparing, summarizing, drawing conclusions and defending - to case studies ethics and integrity in OS a et	- develop reflective questions to define ethical problems in the case study - discuss cases with colleagues - justify a personal position on the case

PROCEDURE

1. Depending on the size of the group and background of the trainees choose how many cases to discuss during the workshop. There are two cases included in the file "HU_U2A2 Handout". You can also choose to watch the Case 1 in the classroom - **animation of this case is available on the [ROSIE webpage](#).**
2. Print out the case descriptions and questions for discussion for each trainee (file "HU_U2A2 Handout").
3. Introduce the activity, its aim and, briefly, the procedure.

4. Ask trainees to split in small groups (4-5 trainees in a group) and to choose a rapporteur - a group member who will report results of the small group discussion to the whole group. Provide each group with a paper for taking notes.
5. **Step 1:** small group discussions – **30 minutes**. Trainees read the case description and discuss the questions in small groups. Each group takes notes.
Rapporteurs prepare to present the results to the whole group.
6. **Step 2:** reports from small group discussions – **30 minutes**. Depending on the number of the small groups, allocate a time slot for each group presentation (e.g., if there are 4 small groups, each group have 10 minutes for a presentation). Rapporteurs present the results of their group discussions.
7. **Step 3:** group discussion – **30 minutes**. The trainer moderates a reflective group discussion. The trainer writes the solutions suggested during the discussion on the whiteboard and summarises them. Sample questions for reflective discussion are, e.g.:
 - *What are the specific ethical concerns related to archiving, open sharing and reuse of social media data?*
 - *What are specific requirements for open sharing of data collected from vulnerable research participants?*
 - *How to inform research participants about open sharing of data? What are specific requirements for informed consent or assent in the context of open sharing of data?*
 - *How to ensure privacy of research participants? Is it possible to anonymize qualitative data? If so, how?*

PLANNING

Resources and equipment:

- Handout “HU_U2A2 Handout” and/or video of case animation
- Paper for taking notes during small group discussions
- Whiteboard for discussion notes
- Make space for the trainees to work in small groups

FURTHER READINGS

1. DuBois, J. M., Strait, M., & Walsh, H. (2018). Is it time to share qualitative research data? *Qualitative Psychology*, 5(3), 380–393.
<https://doi.org/10.1037/qup0000076>
2. Fox, J., Pearce, K. E., Massanari, A. L., Riles, J. M., Szulc, Ł., Ranjit, Y. S., ... & L. Gonzales, A. (2021). Open science, closed doors? Countering marginalization through an agenda for ethical, inclusive research in communication. *Journal of Communication*, 71(5), 764-784. <https://doi.org/10.1093/joc/jqab029>

Activity 2.1 Open data and risk of looting in archaeology

DESCRIPTION

This activity is built around case discussion. Trainees are asked to discuss in small groups a case on risk of looting in archaeology in the context of sharing open data. Afterwards, small groups report to the whole group and continue with a reflective discussion involving the whole group.

Type of activity: case discussion

Time: 90 min.

Target group: students, early career researchers, senior researchers **Learning outcomes:**

	Learning outcomes <i>It is expected that trainees will:</i>	Indicators for their achievement <i>Trainees who have fully met the learning outcome are able to:</i>
	- describe the risks to cultural heritage in the context of OS	- minimize risks to cultural heritage when practicing OS
	- apply critical thinking skills - questioning, comparing, summarizing, drawing conclusions and defending - to case studies and integrity in OS	- develop reflective questions to define ethical problems in the case study - discuss cases with colleagues - justify a personal position on the case

PROCEDURE

1. Print out the case description and questions for discussion for each trainee (file "HU_U2A2.1 Handout").
2. Introduce the activity, its aim and, briefly, the procedure.
3. Ask trainees to split in small groups (4-5 trainees in a group) and to choose a rapporteur - a group member who will report results of the small group discussion to the whole group. Provide each group with a paper for taking notes.
4. **Step 1:** small group discussions – **30 minutes**. Trainees read the case description and discuss the questions in small groups. Each group takes notes.
Rapporteurs prepare to present the results to the whole group.
5. **Step 2:** reports from small group discussions – **30 minutes**. Depending on the number of the small groups, allocate a time slot for each group presentation (e.g., if there are 4 small groups, each group have 10 minutes for a presentation). Rapporteurs present the results of their group discussions.

6. **Step 3:** group discussion – **30 minutes**. The trainer moderates a reflective group discussion. The trainer writes the solutions suggested during the discussion on the whiteboard and summarises them. Sample questions for reflective discussion are, e.g.:

- *What is your personal experience with open sharing of sensitive archaeological data?*
- *How to responsibly implement the principle “as open as possible and as closed as necessary” regarding archaeological research data?*
- *Who should make decisions about whether and how to manage access to sensitive archaeological data?*

PLANNING

Resources and equipment:

- Handout “HU_U2A2.1 Handout”
- Paper for taking notes during small group discussions
- Whiteboard for discussion notes
- Make space for the trainees to work in small groups

FURTHER READINGS

1. Huggett, J. (2015). Digital Haystacks: Open Data and the Transformation of Archaeological Knowledge. *Open Source Archaeology: Ethics and Practice*, 6-29.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.17613/yfss-zt74>
2. Smith, C. (2020). Ethics and best practices for mapping archaeological sites. *Advances in Archaeological Practice*, 8(2), 162-173.
<https://doi.org/10.1017/aap.2020.9>

Unit 3. Ethical aspects of citizen science in the context of OS

Activity 3. Development of an ethically sound citizen science project

DESCRIPTION

This activity involves home reading before the classroom activity, to introduce the concept of citizen science in the context of humanities. It is followed by group project onsite where trainees are asked to develop their own citizen science projects in humanities and analyse ethical aspects of these projects.

Type of activity: home readings and group project

Time: 90 min.

Target group: students, early career researchers, senior researchers **Learning outcomes:**

	Learning outcomes <i>It is expected that trainees</i>	Indicators for their achievement <i>Trainees who have fully met the learning</i> <i>outcome are able to:</i>
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> understand the significance of citizen science for identifying scientific problems societal challenges 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> provide examples for role of citizen science in identifying and solving scientific problems and societal challenges

PROCEDURE

1. At least a week before the workshop send trainees the required readings (file "HU_U3A3 Readings Heinisch et al 2021"²).
2. During the workshop, introduce the group activity, its aim and, briefly, the procedure.
3. Ask trainees to split in three groups. The group task is to develop an idea for a citizen science project in humanities, by using definitions and examples

² Heinisch, B., Oswald, K., Weißpflug, M., Shuttleworth, S., & Belknap, G. (2021). Citizen humanities. In: The Science of Citizen Science. Springer https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-03058278-4_8

provided in the required readings. For taking notes print one copy of "HU_U3A3 Handout" for each group.

4. **Step 1** development of the project idea – **30 minutes**. Each group should discuss and fill in the table 1 in the "HU_U3A3 Handout".
5. **Step 2** reflection on ethical aspects of the project – **30 minutes**. Each group should discuss and fill in the table 2 in the "HU_U3A3 Handout".
6. **Step 3** presentation of group projects and general discussion – **30 minutes**.
 Sample questions for reflective discussion are, e.g.:
 - *What does citizen science add to the field of humanities?*
 - *What are the main ethical challenges and their solutions in citizen science projects in humanities?*

PLANNING

Resources and equipment:

- Readings “HU_U3A3 Readings Heinisch etal 2021”
- Handout “HU_U3A3 Handout”
- Make space for the trainees to work in small groups

FURTHER READINGS

1. Balázs, B., Mooney, P., Nováková, E., Bastin, L., Jokar Arsanjani, J. (2021). Data Quality in Citizen Science. In: *The Science of Citizen Science*. Springer https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-58278-4_8
2. López, M. P., Soekijad, M., Berends, H., & Huysman, M. (2020). A knowledge perspective on quality in complex citizen science. *Citizen Science: Theory and Practice*, 5(1). <http://doi.org/10.5334/cstp.250>
3. Mahr, D., Göbel, C., Irwin, A., & Vohland, K. (2018). Watching or being watched enhancing productive discussion between the citizen sciences, the social sciences and the humanities. UCL Press. <https://doi.org/10.14324/111.9781787352339>
4. Tauginienė, L., Butkevičienė, E., Vohland, K., Heinisch, B., Daskolia, M., Suškevičs, M., ... & Prūse, B. (2020). Citizen science in the social sciences and humanities: the power of interdisciplinarity. *Palgrave Communications*, 6(1), 1-11. <https://doi.org/10.1057/s41599-020-0471-y>

Unit 4. Protection of intellectual property in the context of OS

Activity 4. Collective authorship in digital humanities

DESCRIPTION

This activity is built around case discussion and involves evaluating pro and contra arguments for co-authorship in digital humanities. Trainees are asked to discuss the case in small groups, develop and discuss their arguments. Afterwards, small groups report to the whole group and continue with a reflective discussion involving the whole group.

Type of activity: case discussion

Time: 90 min.

Target group: students, early career researchers, senior researchers **Learning outcomes:**

	Learning outcomes <i>It is expected that trainees will:</i>	Indicators for their achievement <i>Trainees who have fully met the learning outcome are able to:</i>
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> be aware of protection of intellectual property in OS 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> acknowledge authors and contributors of open data sets and other research outputs
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> apply critical thinking skills - questioning, comparing, summarizing, drawing conclusions and defending - to case studies and integrity in OS 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> develop reflective questions to define ethical problems in the case study discuss cases with colleagues justify a personal position on the case

PROCEDURE

1. Introduce the activity, its aim and, briefly, the procedure.
2. Ask trainees to split in small groups (3-4 trainees in a group) and to choose a rapporteur - a group member who will report results of the small group discussion to the whole group.
3. Print out case description and questions for discussion for each trainee (file "HU_U4A4 Handout").
4. **Step 1:** small group discussions – **30 minutes**. Trainees read the case description and discuss the questions in small groups. Each group fills in the table included in the handout with pro and contra arguments. Rapporteurs prepare to present the results to the whole group.
5. **Step 2:** short reports from small group discussions – **20 minutes**. Rapporteurs present the results of their group discussions - pro and contra arguments for each type of acknowledging the contribution of citizen scientists in this case.
6. **Step 3:** group discussion – **40 minutes**. The trainer moderates a reflective group discussion. Sample questions for reflective discussion are, e.g.:
 - *What are the advantages and disadvantages of collaborative publishing in digital humanities?*
 - *How to recognize contribution of each co-author in case of collaborative authorship? What criteria of authorship should be used?*
 - *What ethical problems might arise in the context of collaborative authorship? How to prevent and solve these problems?*

PLANNING

Resources and equipment:

- Handout "HU_U4A4 Handout"
- Make space for the trainees to work in small groups

FURTHER READINGS

1. COPE Council (2003). How to Handle Authorship Disputes: A Guide for New Researchers. <https://doi.org/10.24318/cope.2018.1.1>
2. McCarty, W. (2016). Collaborative research in the digital humanities. In *Collaborative Research in the Digital Humanities* (pp. 13-22). Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781315572659>
3. The Embassy of Good Science: “[Authorship criteria](#)”

Activity 4.1. Authorship, contributorship and group coauthorship in citizen science

DESCRIPTION

This activity is built around case discussion and involves evaluating pro and contra arguments for different types of acknowledging citizen scientist contributions to research. Trainees are asked to discuss the case in small groups, develop and discuss their arguments. Afterwards, small groups report to the whole group and continue with a reflective discussion involving the whole group.

Type of activity: case discussion

Time: 90 min.

Target group: students, early career researchers, senior researchers **Learning outcomes:**

	Learning outcomes <i>It is expected that trainees will:</i>	Indicators for their achievement <i>Trainees who have fully met the learning outcome are able to:</i>
	- be aware of protection of intellectual property in OS	- acknowledge authors and contributors of open data sets and other research outputs
	- be aware of citizen scientists' right to be recognised and acknowledged by academic scientists and society	- discuss and assert their right to be recognized and acknowledged by academic scientists and society
	- apply critical thinking skills - questioning, comparing, summarizing, drawing conclusions and defending - to case studies ethics and integrity in OS	- develop reflective questions to define ethical problems in the case study - discuss cases with colleagues - justify a personal position on the case

PROCEDURE

1. Introduce the activity, its aim and, briefly, the procedure.

2. Ask trainees to split in small groups (3-4 trainees in a group) and to choose a rapporteur - a group member who will report results of the small group discussion to the whole group.
3. Print out case description and questions for discussion for each trainee (file "HU_U4A4.1 Handout". You can also choose to watch the case in the classroom - **animation of this case is available on the [ROSIE webpage](#)**.
4. **Step 1:** small group discussions – **30 minutes**. Trainees read the case description and discuss the questions in small groups. Each group fills in the table included in the handout with pro and contra arguments. Rapporteurs prepare to present the results to the whole group.
5. **Step 2:** short reports from small group discussions – **20 minutes**. Rapporteurs present the results of their group discussions - pro and contra arguments for each type of acknowledging the contribution of citizen scientists in this case.
6. **Step 3:** group discussion – **40 minutes**. The trainer moderates a reflective group discussion. Sample questions for reflective discussion are, e.g.:
 - *Based on the pro and contra arguments developed during the group work, what is the best solution for this case?*
 - *Do you have other suggestions for recognizing the contribution of citizen scientists in scientific publications?*

PLANNING

Resources and equipment:

- Handout "HU_U4A4.1 Handout" and/or video of case animation
- Make space for the trainees to work in small groups

FURTHER READINGS

1. COPE Council (2003). How to Handle Authorship Disputes: A Guide for New Researchers. <https://doi.org/10.24318/cope.2018.1.1>
2. ICMJE. Defining the role of authors and contributors. <https://bit.ly/N7uoq3>
3. The Embassy of Good Science: "[Authorship criteria](#)"
4. Vasilevsky, N. A. et al. (2021). Is authorship sufficient for today's collaborative research? A call for contributor roles. *Accountability in Research*, 28(1), 23-43. <https://doi.org/10.1080/08989621.2020.1779591>

Unit 5. The quality of the research outputs and data sets

Activity 5. Responsibility for the quality of research data

DESCRIPTION

This activity starts with homework where trainees are asked to read a paper on data quality in citizen science and create a mind map. The purpose of the mind map is to build a background knowledge for case discussion. It is followed by case discussion and development of guidelines for ensuring quality of citizen sciences data in humanities.

Type of activity: home reading and case discussion **Time:** 90 min.

Target group: students, early career researchers **Learning outcomes:**

	Learning outcomes <i>It is expected that trainees will:</i>	Indicators for their achievement <i>Trainees who have fully met the learning outcome are able to:</i>
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> aware of importance of the data sets and research outputs and their responsible use 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> explain how to responsibly and critically assess and use open data and research outputs
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> apply critical thinking skills - questioning, comparing, summarizing, drawing conclusions and defending - to case studies and integrity in OS 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> develop reflective questions to define ethical problems in the case study discuss cases with colleagues justify a personal position on the case

PROCEDURE

1. At least a week before the workshop send trainees the required readings (file "HU_U5A5 Readings Balazs et al 2021") and the handout for creating a mind map (file "HU_U5A5_1 Handout").
2. Before the workshop trainees are required to read the required readings "HU_U5A5 Readings Balazs et al 2021"³.

³ Balázs, B., Mooney, P., Nováková, E., Bastin, L., Jokar Arsanjani, J. (2021). Data Quality in Citizen Science. In: The Science of Citizen Science. Springer https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-582784_8.

3. Before the workshop trainees should create a mind map on quality of data in citizen science, based on the required readings. Instructions for creating a mind map are included in the handout “HU_U5A5_1 Handout”.
4. In the classroom, introduce the activity, its aim and, briefly, the procedure.
5. Ask trainees to split in small groups (4-6 trainees in a group) and to choose a rapporteur - a group member who will report results of the small group discussion to the whole group.
6. Print out the case description (file “HU_U5A5_2 Handout”) for each trainee
7. **Step 1:** small group discussions – **40 minutes**. Trainees read the case description, discuss the challenges, use the ideas from required readings and develop recommendations. Each group fills in a table with challenges and recommendations. The table is included in the “HU_U5A5_2 Handout”.
Rapporteurs prepare to present the results to the whole group.
8. **Step 2:** reports from small group discussions – **30 minutes**. Depending on the number of the small groups, allocate a time slot for each group presentation (e.g., if there are 3 small groups, each group have 10 minutes for a presentation). Rapporteurs present the results of their group discussions.
9. **Step 3:** group discussion – **20 minutes**. The trainer moderates a reflective group discussion. Sample questions for reflective discussion are, e.g.:
 - *Which ideas from the required readings helped you to develop recommendations? How?*
 - *Which of the recommendations developed during the groupwork are the most useful? Why?*
 - *In your view, what are other considerable ethical challenges for scientists collaborating with citizen scientists in the field of humanities? How to address these challenges?*

PLANNING

Resources and equipment:

- Required readings “HU_U5A5 Readings Balazs etal 2021”
- Handout “HU_U5A5_1 Handout” for home reading and creating a mind map
- Handout “HU_U5A5_2 Handout” for case discussion
- Make space for the trainees to work in small groups

FURTHER READINGS

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1. Haklay, M. (2021). Why is it so difficult to integrate citizen science into practice?
Citizen Science and Public Policy Making, 108. <https://discovery.ucl.ac.uk/id/eprint/10130136>

2. López, M. P., Soekijad, M., Berends, H., & Huysman, M. (2020). A knowledge perspective on quality in complex citizen science. *Citizen Science: Theory and Practice*, 5(1). <http://doi.org/10.5334/cstp.250>

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Unit 6. Responsible sharing and reuse of open humanities data

Activity 6. Concerns to share and reuse data

DESCRIPTION

This activity starts with brainstorming where trainees are asked to share their views on sharing and reusing research data. It is followed by group discussion on concerns to share and reuse data, as well as possible solutions. **Type of activity:** brainstorming and group discussion

Time: 90 min.

Target group: students, early career researchers, senior researchers **Learning outcomes:**

	Learning outcomes <i>It is expected that trainees</i>	Indicators for their achievement <i>Trainees who have fully met the outcome</i>
	- be aware about factors influencing willingness to share and use search data	- discuss how to increase willingness to open

PROCEDURE

- Step 1: brainstorming – 15 minutes.** The trainer starts brainstorming by posing two questions: (1) “Are you ready to share your research data in an open data repository? Why yes or no?” and (2) “Are you ready to use open access data in your research? Why yes or no?” and invite trainees to take a minute’s silence to think on it. Once the minute is up, invite everyone to share their views. Have a single person (trainer or one of trainees) who takes notes on a whiteboard. The main aim of brainstorming is just to listen to different views without criticism.
- Ask trainees to split in small groups (4-6 trainees in a group) and to choose a rapporteur - a group member who will report results of the small group discussion to the whole group.
- Distribute the handout (file “Handout HU_U6A6”) to each group. Half of the groups receive Task 1 from the handout (“Sharing your own research data”), other groups get Task 2 from the handout (“Using open data created by other researchers”).
- Step 2: small group discussions – 30 minutes.** Trainees discuss and fill in a table with concerns and possible solutions. Rapporteurs prepare to present the results to the whole group.
- Step 3: reports from small group discussions – 30 minutes.** Depending on the number of the small groups, allocate a time slot for each group presentation (e.g., if there are 3 small groups, each group have 10 minutes for a presentation). Rapporteurs present the results of their group discussions.

6. **Step 3:** group discussion – **15 minutes**. The trainer moderates a reflective group discussion. Sample questions for reflective discussion are, e.g.:
- *What are the most important concerns discouraging researchers to share their data for reuse and to use open data created by other researchers? What are possible solutions?*
 - *How to responsibly share and reuse quantitative data in humanities? Is it possible to responsibly share and reuse qualitative data? How?*

PLANNING

Resources and equipment:

- Handout “Handout HU_U6A6” printed out for each small group
- Whiteboard for discussion notes
- Make space for the trainees to work in small groups

FURTHER READINGS

1. Zuiderwijk, A., Shinde, R., & Jeng, W. (2020). What drives and inhibits researchers to share and use open research data? A systematic literature review to analyze factors influencing open research data adoption. *PLoS one*, 15(9), e0239283. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0239283>

Activity 6.1. Case discussion on concerns about sharing the data

DESCRIPTION

This activity is built around case discussion. Trainees are asked to discuss in small groups a case on scientists’ concerns to share the data. Afterwards, small groups report to the whole group and continue with a reflective discussion involving the whole group.

Type of activity: case discussion

Time: 90 min.

Target group: early career researchers, senior researchers **Learning outcomes:**

	Learning outcomes <i>It is expected that trainees will:</i>	Indicators for their achievement <i>Trainees who have fully met the learning outcome are able to:</i>
	– be aware of factors influencing willingness to share and use open research data	– discuss how to increase willingness to share and use open research data

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - apply critical thinking skills - questioning, comparing, summarizing, drawing conclusions and defending - to case studies and integrity in OS 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - develop reflective questions to define ethical problems in the case study - discuss cases with colleagues - justify a personal position on the case
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PROCEDURE

1. Introduce the activity, its aim and, briefly, the procedure.
2. Ask trainees to split in small groups (4-5 trainees in a group) and to choose a rapporteur - a group member who will report results of the small group discussion to the whole group. Provide each group with a paper for taking notes.
3. Print out the case description and questions for discussion for each trainee (file "HU_U6A6.1 Handout").
4. **Step 1:** small group discussions – **30 minutes**. Trainees read the case description and discuss the questions in small groups. Each group takes notes. Rapporteurs prepare to present the results to the whole group.
5. **Step 2:** reports from small group discussions – **40 minutes**. Depending on the number of the small groups, allocate a time slot for each group presentation (e.g., if there are 4 small groups, each group have 10 minutes for a presentation). Rapporteurs present the results of their group discussions.
6. **Step 3:** group discussion – **20 minutes**. The trainer moderates a reflective group discussion. The trainer writes the solutions suggested during the discussion on the whiteboard and summarises them. Sample questions for reflective discussion are, e.g.:
 - *What are the most important concerns discouraging researchers to share their data for reuse and to use open data created by other researchers? What are possible solutions?*
 - *Are there any legitimate reasons not to share research data?*
 - *How to responsibly share and reuse data in humanities?*

PLANNING

Resources and equipment:

- Handout "HU_U6A6.1 Handout" and/or animations of cases available on ROSiE webpage
- Paper for taking notes during small group discussions
- Whiteboard for discussion notes
- Make space for the trainees to work in small groups

FURTHER READINGS

1. Gewin, V. (2016.) Data sharing: An open mind on open data. *Nature* 529.
<https://doi.org/10.1038/nj7584-117a>

- Laine, H. (2017). Afraid of scooping: Case study on researcher strategies against fear of scooping in the context of open science. *Data Science Journal*.
<https://doi.org/10.5334/dsj-2017-029>
- Zuiderwijk, A., Shinde, R., & Jeng, W. (2020). What drives and inhibits researchers to share and use open research data? A systematic literature review to analyze factors influencing open research data adoption. *PLoS one*, 15(9), e0239283.
<https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0239283>

Unit 7. Prevention of research malpractice in the context of OS

Activity 7. Violations of research integrity in OS and their prevention

DESCRIPTION

The activity aims to discuss different types of violations of research integrity in OS and their prevention. The trainees are split into five groups and their task is to reflect on potential type of violation and preventive measure in each particular type of Open Science activity. Each group shares the results of their discussions, and group work is followed by plenary activity where all trainees have an opportunity to supplement the results of group work.

Type of activity: group work and plenary activity

Time: 90 minutes

Target group: students, early career researchers, senior researchers **Learning outcomes:**

	Learning outcomes <i>It is expected that trainees</i>	Indicators for their achievement <i>Trainees who have fully met the learning</i>
	<i>will:</i>	<i>outcome are able to:</i>
	– know potential types of research malpractice in OS	– discuss causes of violations of research integrity in OS and ways of its prevention

PROCEDURE

- Before to the exercise, print out the pages with different types of Open Science activities (file “HU_U7A7 Printout”) and mark sections of a wall with the titles:
 - *Open access publishing*
 - *Sharing and using open data*
 - *Open reproducible research, e.g., open lab notes, reproducing of research studies*

- *Open science evaluation, e.g., open metrics and impact, open peer review – Citizen science*
2. Ask participants to split in five groups. Assign one of the types of Open Science activities listed above to each group.
 3. **Step 1:** group discussion – **25 minutes**. Each group discusses the following questions in the context of the particular type of Open Science activities:
 - *What potential violations of research integrity may arise in the context of this type of open science activities?*
 - *How to prevent these potential violations?*

The results of the discussion should be written on paper cards/sticky notes – one potential type of violation and preventive measure on each card/sticky note and hanged on the wall under the respective type of Open Science activities.
 4. **Step 2:** group work presentations and general discussion – **65 minutes**. Each group presents their results in 5 minutes. After each presentation there is 8 minutes general discussion where every trainee has an opportunity to suggest additional challenges and preventive measures. These additional challenges and preventive measures are written on paper cards/sticky notes and added to the respective type of Open Science activities.

PLANNING

Resources and equipment:

- Printout “Printout HU_U7A7”
- Large wall or multiple pinboards to hang on printouts and results of discussions
- Empty cards & tape/sticky notes, pens/markers
- Make space for the trainees to work in small groups and to move around

FURTHER READINGS

1. Düwell, M. (2019). Open science and ethics. *Ethical Theory and Moral Practice*, 22, 1051-1053. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10677-019-10053-3>

Activity 7.1. Should scientists use access to pirated papers?

DESCRIPTION

This activity is built around case discussion. Trainees are asked to discuss in small groups a case on violations of intellectual property rights. Afterwards, small groups report to the whole group and continue with a reflective discussion involving the whole group.

Type of activity: case discussion

Time: 90 minutes

Target group: students, early career researchers, senior researchers **Learning outcomes:**

	Learning outcomes <i>It is expected that trainees</i>	Indicators for their achievement <i>Trainees who have fully met the learning</i> <i>outcome are able to:</i>
	know potential types of research practice in OS	discuss causes of violations of research integrity in OS and ways of its prevention recognise limits of OS for protection of data and intellectual property rights

PROCEDURE

1. Print out the case description and questions for discussion for each trainee (file "HU_U7A7.1 Handout". You can also choose to watch the case in the classroom - **animation of this case is available on the [ROSIE webpage](#).**
2. Introduce the activity, its aim and, briefly, the procedure.
3. Ask trainees to split in small groups (4-5 trainees in a group) and to choose a rapporteur - a group member who will report results of the small group discussion to the whole group. Provide each group with a paper for taking notes.
4. **Step 1:** small group discussions – **30 minutes**. Trainees read the case description and discuss the questions in small groups. Each group takes notes.
Rapporteurs prepare to present the results to the whole group.
5. **Step 2:** reports from small group discussions – **30 minutes**. Depending on the number of the small groups, allocate a time slot for each group presentation (e.g., if there are 4 small groups, each group have 10 minutes for a presentation). Rapporteurs present the results of their group discussions.
6. **Step 3:** group discussion – **30 minutes**. The trainer moderates a reflective group discussion. The trainer writes the solutions suggested during the discussion on the whiteboard and summarises them. Sample questions for reflective discussion are, e.g.:
 - *How important are intellectual property rights for scientific research and achievements?*
 - *Does the case address a relevant issue for you and researchers you are working together?*
 - *What are potential solutions at the policy level to the problem described in the case?*

PLANNING

Resources and equipment:

- Handout "HL_U7A7.1 Handout" and/or video of case animation

- Paper for taking notes during small group discussions
- Whiteboard for discussion notes
- Make space for the trainees to work in small groups

FURTHER READINGS

1. Monbiot, G. Scientific publishing is a rip-off. We fund the research - it should be free. *The Guardian*. 13.09. 2018.
<https://www.theguardian.com/commentisfree/2018/sep/13/scientificpublishing-rip-off-taxpayers-fund-research>. Accessed August 2, 2022.
2. Van Noorden, R. (2016). Alexandra Elbakyan: Paper pirate. *Nature*, 540, 512.
<https://www.nature.com/articles/540507a>
3. Vogel, G., & Kupferschmidt, K. (2017). A bold open-access push in Germany could change the future of academic publishing. *Science*, 23.
<https://www.science.org/content/article/bold-open-access-push-germany-couldchange-future-academic-publishing>

Unit 8. Responsible dissemination and publication practices

Activity 8. Open access publishing and predatory practices

DESCRIPTION

This activity applies the Four Quadrant Method for case analysis on predatory practices. Trainees are asked to discuss a case in small groups and fill in the four quadrant template. Afterwards, small groups report to the whole group and continue with a casuistic reasoning and justification discussion involving the whole group.

Type of activity: case discussion (Four Quadrant Method)

Time: 90 min.

Target group: students, early career researchers **Learning outcomes:**

Learning outcomes	Indicators for their achievement
It is expected that trainees will:	Trainees who have fully met the learning

		outcome are able to:
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> know criteria for good practice standards in open access publishing 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> critically assess scientific results published in open access and identify predatory publishing practices
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> apply critical thinking skills - questioning, comparing, summarizing, drawing conclusions and defending - to case studies and integrity in OS 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> develop reflective questions to define ethical problems in the case study discuss cases with colleagues justify a personal position on the case

PROCEDURE

1. Introduce the activity, its aim and, briefly, the procedure of the Four Quadrant Method⁴.
2. Print out the case description (file “HU_U8A8 Handout”) for each trainee.

⁴ Detailed description of the modified Four Quadrant Method for case analysis is provided by the EnTIRE project: Armond A.C. et al. (2019). D.5.3 Delivery of the entire set of case deliberation methods and case analyses as input for the platform, pp. 98-102. Available:

<https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/documents/downloadPublic?documentIds=080166e5c3a7e938&appId=PPGMS>

3. Ask trainees to split in small groups (3-4 trainees in a group) and to choose a rapporteur - a group member who will report results of the small group discussion to the whole group.
4. **Step 1.** Initial perception – **20 minutes**. Trainees read the case and in small groups discuss some general questions to identify relevant aspects of the case:
 - *What are the ethical issues at stake in this case?*
 - *Who are the stakeholders?*
 - *How should stakeholders react to this case?*
 - *What should/can stakeholders do to prevent such cases?*
5. **Step 2.** The Four Quadrant Analysis – **20 minutes**. Each group fills in the four quadrant table included in the file “HU_U8A8 Handout”.

I. Relevant Facts: What are the most relevant facts concerning the situation?	II. Uncertainties: Which features of the situation are uncertain, lacking in clarity, or controversial?
III. Courses of Action: What are the practically available options for providing a solution to the case (how to react to the case and how to prevent such cases in the future)?	IV. Contextual Features: What legal, financial and institutional policies and regulations apply to the case?

6. **Step 3.** Reports from small groups – **20 minutes**. The small groups report the results of the Four Quadrant Analysis to the whole group.
7. **Step 4.** Casuistic Reasoning and Justification – **30 minutes**. The trainer moderates the whole group discussion on the following questions:
 - *What is at issue? What is the major ethical issue at the case?*
 - *Do you know other cases like this one?*
 - *Why do academics publish their research in a predatory journal or books published by predatory publishers? What are the main factors that motivate such a practice? What are negative consequences of such a practice? What policies might minimise predatory publishing practices? – How should stakeholders react to cases like this?*

PLANNING

Resources and equipment:

- Handout “HU_U8A8 Handout”
- Make space for the trainees to work in small groups

FURTHER READINGS

1. Kurt, S. (2018). Why do authors publish in predatory journals? *Learned Publishing*, 31(2), 141-147. <https://doi.org/10.1002/leap.1150>

UNDER REVIEW BY THE EUROPEAN COMMISSION

Activity 8.1. Open peer review

DESCRIPTION

This activity is built around case discussion. Trainees are asked to discuss in small groups a case on open peer review. Afterwards, small groups report to the whole group and continue with a reflective discussion involving the whole group.

Type of activity: case discussion

Time: 90 min.

Target group: early career researchers, senior researchers **Learning outcomes:**

	Learning outcomes <i>It is expected that trainees will:</i>	Indicators for their achievement <i>Trainees who have fully met the learning outcome are able to:</i>
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - aware of importance of open peer review practices 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - explain how to responsibly and critically perform open peer review
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - apply critical thinking skills - questioning, comparing, summarizing, drawing conclusions, and defending - to case studies on ethics and integrity in OS 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - develop reflective questions to define ethical problems in the case study - discuss cases with colleagues - justify a personal position on the case

PROCEDURE

1. Introduce the activity, its aim and, briefly, the procedure.
2. Ask trainees to split in small groups (4-5 trainees in a group) and to choose a rapporteur - a group member who will report results of the small group discussion to the whole group. Provide each group with a paper for taking notes.
3. Print out case description and questions for discussion for each trainee (file "HU_U8A8.1 Handout").
4. **Step 1:** small group discussions – **30 minutes**. Trainees read the case description and discuss the questions in small groups. Each group takes notes. Rapporteurs prepare to present the results to the whole group.

5. **Step 2:** reports from small group discussions – **40 minutes**. Depending on the number of the small groups, allocate a time slot for each group presentation (e.g., if there are 4 small groups, each group has 10 minutes for a presentation).
Rapporteurs present the results of their group discussions.
6. **Step 3:** group discussion – **20 minutes**. The trainer moderates a reflective group discussion. The trainer writes the ideas suggested during the discussion on the whiteboard and summarise them. Sample questions for reflective discussion are, e.g.:
 - *What is the role of open peer review in the scientific publishing process?*
 - *What are the benefits and risks of open peer review?*

PLANNING

Resources and equipment:

- Handout “HU_U8A8.1 Handout”
- Paper for taking notes during small group discussions
- Whiteboard for discussion notes
- Make space for the trainees to work in small groups

FURTHER READINGS

1. Harms, P. D., & Credé, M. (2020). Bringing the review process into the 21st century: Post-publication peer review. *Industrial and Organizational Psychology*, 13(1), 51-53. <https://doi.org/10.1017/iop.2020.13>
2. Ross-Hellauer, T., Deppe, A., & Schmidt, B. (2017). Survey on open peer review: Attitudes and experience amongst editors, authors and reviewers. *PloS One*, 12(12), e0189311. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0189311>
3. Tenorio-Fornés, Á., Tirador, E. P., Sánchez-Ruiz, A. A., & Hassan, S. (2021). Decentralizing science: Towards an interoperable open peer review ecosystem using blockchain. *Information Processing & Management*, 58(6), 102724. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ipm.2021.102724>
4. The Embassy of Good Science: “[Post-publication peer review](#)”
5. The Embassy of Good Science: “[Open peer review - transparent way of gatekeeping science](#)”

ROSIE

TRAINING MATERIALS for Responsible Open Science Part III: Natural Sciences

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Introduction

The aim of the ROSIE Training Materials for Responsible Open Science is to learn how to practice Open Science (OS) responsibly and how to prevent research misconduct in the context of OS by providing necessary knowledge and developing specific skills and attitudes.

In the ROSIE Didactic Framework we have identified the following skills and attitudes necessary for responsible practising of OS in four domains: (i) local and global citizenship, (ii) personal and social responsibility, (iii) epistemic skills, and (iv) collaborative problem-solving.

Local and global citizenship

- awareness of the importance and social benefits of OS and citizen science in local and global contexts
- participation in ethics and integrity self-regulation of OS and citizen science community

Personal and social responsibility

- personal and professional responsibility for implementation of OS and production of results
- openness to share own research data, results, tools and publications and appreciation of efforts of others

Epistemic skills

- ability to organize, present and use open data and knowledge with integrity
- ability to critically assess data, knowledge and scientific results produced by others
- ability to identify ethical and integrity issues in OS

Collaborative problem-solving

- ability to apply critical thinking skills in collaborative analysis of ethical and integrity problems in OS
- discussing, finding solutions and making decisions to handle ethics and integrity issues within OS community

To achieve optimal results, the ROSIE training materials rely on several learning and teaching strategies: (i) collaborative problem solving; (ii) case-based activities; (iii) dialogical activities; (iv) transformative learning. More information about these teaching strategies you can find in the ROSIE Didactic Framework.

The training material consists of a trainers' file including 8 units and respective activities, as well as a separate folder including materials for trainees – required readings, handouts and printouts. The activities can be implemented separately (e.g., for organising a single workshop to discuss cases) or for organising a complete two-days training course. The suggested schedule for the training course is as follows:

Time	DAY 1	Type of activity
90 min.	Unit 1. Ethical and societal foundations of OS, its purpose	Home readings and Socratic seminar
15 min.	Break	
90 min.	Unit 2. Open science and data privacy in natural sciences	Case discussion
60 min.	Lunch break	
90 min.	Unit 3. Ethical aspects of citizen science in the context of OS	Home readings and group project
15 min.	Break	
90 min.	Unit 4. Protection of intellectual property in the context of OS	Case discussion (Pro and Contra)
Time	DAY 2	Type of activity
90 min.	Unit 5. The quality of the research outputs and data sets	Home readings and case discussion OR Case discussion
15 min.	Break	
90 min.	Unit 6. Responsible sharing and reuse of open natural science data	Brainstorming and group work OR Case discussion
60 min.	Lunch break	
90 min.	Unit 7. Prevention of research malpractice in the context of OS	Group work and plenary activity OR Case discussion
15 min.	Break	
90 min.	Unit 8. Responsible dissemination and publication practices	Case discussion (Four Quadrant Method)

Unit 1. Ethical and societal foundations of OS, its purpose

Activity 1. Principles, values and benefits of OS

DESCRIPTION

This activity starts with homework where trainees are asked to read [UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science](#) and fill in the double-entry reading journal. The purpose of the reading journal is to give trainees an opportunity to express their thoughts and reflect on the text. It is followed by classroom discussion in a form of Socratic seminar on principles and values of OS, as well as main benefits and challenges in OS implementation.

Type of activity: home reading and Socratic seminar

Time: 90 min.

Target groups: students, early career researchers, senior researchers **Learning outcomes:**

	Learning outcomes <i>It is expected that trainees</i>	Indicators for their achievement <i>Trainees who have fully met the learning</i> <i>outcome are able to:</i>
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - demonstrate knowledge of foundations of OS - understand the significance of citizen science for identifying and solving societal challenges 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - explain and discuss principles and values of OS, its ethical foundations, and social benefits - provide examples for role of OS and citizen science in identifying and solving scientific problems and societal challenges

PROCEDURE

1. At least a week before the workshop send trainees the required readings ([UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science](#), file “NS_U1A1 Readings UNESCO Recommendation”) and the handout (file “NS_U1A1 Handout”).
2. Before the workshop trainees are required to read the parts I., II. and III. of the [UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science](#) (pp. 6-19).
3. Before the workshop trainees should fill in the double-entry reading journal table in the handout. The left side should contain quotations from the UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science with page numbers noted. The right side should contain trainee’s response to each quotation (a question, commentary, analysis). When filling in the table, trainees may use the following prompts, included in the handout:
 - *I agree/disagree with..., because...*

- *It is not clear for me...*
 - *I see the following challenges...*
 - *I have a question regarding...*
4. The classroom discussion is organized as a Socratic seminar. The aim of the Socratic seminar is to achieve “a deeper understanding about the ideas and values in a particular text”³. The trainer is facilitator of the discussion, the discussion is led by using open-ended, high-level questions. Trainees are sitting in a circle.
 5. The Socratic Seminar starts with introduction of the rules:
 - Only those trainees who have read the text and filled in the double-entry reading journal are allowed to participate;
 - It is important to focus on the text and to refer to evidence from the text;
 - Trainees are encouraged to talk to each other, not just to the trainer and to listen and respond to others’ arguments.
 6. Common questions used during a Socratic Seminar activity both by trainer and trainees include:
 - *What does this concept/idea/phrase etc. mean?*
 - *What do you think the authors are trying to say?*
 - *Is this what you mean to say...?*
 - *What is the origin of this?*
 - *What are the implications of this?*
 - *What else could that mean?*
 - *What would happen if....?*
 7. This [overview of Socratic seminar](#) provides a list of suitable questions and more information about how to prepare for a discussion.

PLANNING

Resources and equipment:

- Handout “NS_U1A1 Handout”
 - Required readings “NS_U1A1 Readings UNESCO Recommendation”
-
- Make space for the trainees to sit in a circle

FURTHER READINGS

³ Castellanos-Reyes, D. (2020). Socratic Seminar. In R. Kimmons & S. Caskurlu (Eds.), *The Students' Guide to Learning Design and Research*. EdTech Books.

https://edtechbooks.org/studentguide/socratic_seminar

1. Castellanos-Reyes, D. (2020). Socratic Seminar. In R. Kimmons & S. Caskurlu (Eds.), *The Students' Guide to Learning Design and Research*. EdTech Books.
https://edtechbooks.org/studentguide/socratic_seminar
2. Düwell, M. (2019). Open science and ethics. *Ethical Theory and Moral Practice*, 22(5), 1051-1053. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10677-019-10053-3>
3. Tennant, J. P., Waldner, F., Jacques, D. C., Masuzzo, P., Collister, L. B., & Hartgerink, C. H. (2016). The academic, economic and societal impacts of Open Access: an evidence-based review. *F1000Research*, 5. <https://f1000research.com/articles/5632/v3>

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Unit 2. Open science and data privacy in natural sciences

Activity 2. Data privacy and security in natural sciences

DESCRIPTION

This activity is built around case discussion. Trainees are asked to discuss in small groups cases on ethical issues in gathering, open sharing and reuse of sensitive data in natural sciences. Afterwards, small groups report to the whole group and continue with a reflective discussion involving the whole group.

Type of activity: case discussion

Time: 90 min.

Target group: students, early career researchers, senior researchers **Learning outcomes:**

	Learning outcomes <i>It is expected that trainees will:</i>	Indicators for their achievement <i>Trainees who have fully met the learning outcome are able to:</i>
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> describe the risks to research participants, environment, plants, animals, and ecosystems in the context of OS 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> discuss how to minimize risks to research participants, environment, plants, animals, and ecosystems when practicing OS
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> apply critical thinking skills - questioning, comparing, summarizing, drawing conclusions and defending - to case studies and integrity in OS 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> develop reflective questions to define ethical problems in the case study discuss cases with colleagues justify a personal position on the case

PROCEDURE

- Depending on the size of the group and background of the trainees choose how many cases to discuss during the workshop. There are two cases included in the file "NS_U2A2 Handout".
- Introduce the activity, its aim and, briefly, the procedure.
- Print out case description(s) and questions for discussion for each trainee (file "NS_U2A2 Handout").

4. Ask trainees to split in small groups (4-5 trainees in a group) and to choose a rapporteur - a group member who will report results of the small group discussion to the whole group. Provide each group with a paper for taking notes.
5. **Step 1:** small group discussions – **30 minutes**. Trainees read the case description and discuss the questions in small groups. Each group takes notes. Rapporteurs prepare to present the results to the whole group.
6. **Step 2:** reports from small group discussions – **40 minutes**. Depending on the number of the small groups, allocate a time slot for each group presentation (e.g., if there are 4 small groups, each group have 10 minutes for a presentation).
Rapporteurs present the results of their group discussions.
7. **Step 3:** group discussion – **20 minutes**. The trainer moderates a reflective group discussion. The trainer writes the solutions suggested during the discussion on the whiteboard and summarises them. Sample questions for reflective discussion are, e.g.:
 - Which types of data are potentially sensitive in natural sciences?
 - How sharing these types of data might violate the privacy and security of individuals or communities?
 - Do you agree with the authors' statement in one of the cases that: "Natural scientists have little guidance to deal with privacy concerns for open science, which are inherent in socio-environmental research"?
 - What should the scientists do to protect data privacy and security? What support they do need?

PLANNING

Resources and equipment:

- Handout "NS_U2A2 Handout"
- Paper for taking notes during small group discussions
- Whiteboard for discussion notes
- Make space for the trainees to work in small groups

FURTHER READINGS

1. Blatt, A. J. (2015). The benefits and risks of volunteered geographic information. *Journal of Map & Geography Libraries*, 11(1), 99-104.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/15420353.2015.1009609>
2. Richardson, D. B., Kwan, M. P., Alter, G., & McKendry, J. E. (2015). Replication of scientific research: addressing geoprivacy, confidentiality, and data sharing challenges in geospatial research. *Annals of GIS*, 21(2), 101-110. <https://doi.org/10.1080/19475683.2015.1027792>

3. Zipper, S. C., Stack Whitney, K., Deines, J. M., Befus, K. M., Bhatia, U., Albers, S. J., ... & Schlager, E. (2019). Balancing open science and data privacy in the water sciences. *Water Resources Research*, 55(7), 5202-5211.

<https://doi.org/10.1029/2019WR025080>

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Unit 3. Ethical aspects of citizen science in the context of OS

Activity 3. Development of an ethically sound citizen science project

DESCRIPTION

This activity involves home reading before the classroom activity, to introduce the concept of citizen science in the context of natural sciences. It is followed by group project onsite where trainees are asked to develop their own citizen science projects and analyse ethical aspects of these projects.

Type of activity: home reading and group project

Time: 90 min.

Target group: students, early career researchers, senior researchers **Learning outcomes:**

	Learning outcomes <i>It is expected that trainees will:</i>	Indicators for their achievement <i>Trainees who have fully met the learning outcome are able to:</i>
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> understand the significance of citizen science for identifying and solving scientific problems and societal challenges 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> provide examples for role of citizen science in identifying and solving scientific problems and societal challenges

PROCEDURE

1. At least a week before the workshop send trainees the required readings (file “NS_U3A3 Readings_Citizen science—bridging the gap between scientists and amateurs”²).
2. During the workshop, introduce the group activity, its aim and, briefly, the procedure.
3. Ask trainees to split in three groups. The group task is to develop an idea for a citizen science project in natural sciences, by using definitions and examples

² Stratilová Urválková, E. S., & Janoušková, S. (2019). Citizen science—bridging the gap between scientists and amateurs. *Chemistry Teacher International*, 1(2). <https://doi.org/10.1515/cti-2018-0032>

provided in the required readings. For taking notes print one copy of “NS_U3A3 Handout” for each group.

4. **Step 1** development of the project idea – **30 minutes**. Each group should discuss and fill in the table 1 in the “NS_U3A3 Handout”.

5. **Step 2** reflection on ethical aspects of the project – **30 minutes**. Each group should discuss and fill in the table 2 in the “NS_U3A3 Handout”.
6. **Step 3** presentation of group projects and general discussion – **30 minutes**.
Sample questions for reflective discussion are, e.g.:
 - *What does citizen science add to the field of natural sciences?*
 - *What are the main ethical challenges and their solutions in citizen science projects in natural sciences?*

PLANNING

Resources and equipment:

- Readings “NS_U3A3 Readings_Citizen science–bridging the gap between scientists and amateurs ”
- Handout “NS_U3A3 Handout”
- Make space for the trainees to work in small groups

FURTHER READINGS

1. Balázs, B., Mooney, P., Nováková, E., Bastin, L., Jokar Arsanjani, J. (2021). Data Quality in Citizen Science. In: *The Science of Citizen Science*. Springer https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-58278-4_8
2. Frigerio, D., Richter, A., Per, E., Pruse, B., & Vohland, K. (2021). Citizen science in the natural sciences. In: *The Science of Citizen Science*. Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-58278-4_5

Unit 4. Protection of intellectual property in the context of OS

Activity 4. Authorship and contributorship in citizen science

DESCRIPTION

This activity is built around case discussion and involves evaluating pro and contra arguments for different types of acknowledging citizen scientist contributions to research. Trainees are asked to discuss the case in small groups, develop and discuss their arguments. Afterwards, small groups report to the whole group and continue with a reflective discussion involving the whole group.

Type of activity: case discussion

Time: 90 min.

Target group: students, early career researchers, senior researchers **Learning outcomes:**

	Learning outcomes <i>It is expected that trainees will:</i>	Indicators for their achievement <i>Trainees who have fully met the learning outcome are able to:</i>
	– be aware of protection of intellectual property in OS	– acknowledge authors and contributors of open data sets and other research outputs
	– be aware of citizen scientists' right to be recognised and acknowledged by academic scientists and society	– discuss and assert their right to be recognized and acknowledged by academic scientists and society
	– apply critical thinking skills - questioning, comparing, summarizing, drawing conclusions and defending - to case studies and integrity in OS	– develop reflective questions to define ethical problems in the case study – discuss cases with colleagues – justify a personal position on the case

PROCEDURE

1. Introduce the activity, its aim and, briefly, the procedure.
2. Ask trainees to split in small groups (3-4 trainees in a group) and to choose a rapporteur - a group member who will report results of the small group discussion to the whole group.
3. Print out case description and questions for discussion for each trainee (file "NS_U4A4 Handout". You can also choose to watch the case in the classroom - **animation of this case is available on the [ROSIE webpage](#)**.
4. **Step 1:** small group discussions – **30 minutes**. Trainees read the case description and discuss the questions in small groups. Each group fills in the table included in the handout with pro and contra arguments. Rapporteurs prepare to present the results to the whole group.
5. **Step 2:** short reports from small group discussions – **20 minutes**. Rapporteurs present the results of their group discussions - pro and contra arguments for each type of acknowledging the contribution of citizen scientists in this case.
6. **Step 3:** group discussion – **40 minutes**. The trainer moderates a reflective group discussion. Sample questions for reflective discussion are, e.g.:
 - *Based on the pro and contra arguments developed during the group work, what is the best solution for this case?*
 - *Do you have other suggestions for recognizing the contribution of citizen scientists in scientific publications?*

PLANNING

Resources and equipment:

- Handout “NS_U4A4 Handout” and/or video of case animation
- Make space for the trainees to work in small groups

FURTHER READINGS

1. COPE Council (2003). How to Handle Authorship Disputes: A Guide for New Researchers. <https://doi.org/10.24318/cope.2018.1.1>
2. ICMJE. Defining the role of authors and contributors. <https://bit.ly/N7uoq3>
3. The Embassy of Good Science: “[Authorship criteria](#)”
4. Vasilevsky, N. A. et al. (2021). Is authorship sufficient for today’s collaborative research? A call for contributor roles. *Accountability in Research*, 28(1), 23-43. <https://doi.org/10.1080/08989621.2020.1779591>

Activity 4.1. Inequities and potential of exploitation in OS

DESCRIPTION

This activity is built around case discussion. Trainees are asked to discuss in small groups a case on ethical issues on protection of intellectual property in OS in life sciences and medicine, especially in the context of low- and middle- income countries. Afterwards, small groups report to the whole group and continue with a reflective discussion involving the whole group.

Type of activity: case discussion

Time: 90 min.

Target group: students, early career researchers, senior researchers **Learning outcomes:**

	Learning outcomes <i>It is expected that trainees will:</i>	Indicators for their achievement <i>Trainees who have fully met the learning outcome are able to:</i>
	- be aware of protection of intellectual property in OS	- acknowledge authors and contributors of open data sets and other research outputs
	- apply critical thinking skills - questioning, comparing, summarizing, drawing conclusions, and defending - to case studies on ethics and integrity in OS	- develop reflective questions to define ethical problems in the case study - discuss cases with colleagues - justify a personal position on the case

PROCEDURE

1. Introduce the activity, its aim and, briefly, the procedure.

2. Ask trainees to split in small groups (3-4 trainees in a group) and to choose a rapporteur - a group member who will report results of the small group discussion to the whole group.
3. Print out the case description and questions for discussion for each trainee (file "NS_U4A4.1 Handout").
4. **Step 1:** small group discussions – **30 minutes**. Trainees read the case description and discuss the questions in small groups. Rapporteurs prepare to present the results to the whole group.
5. **Step 2:** short reports from small group discussions – **30 minutes**. Rapporteurs present the results of their group discussions.
6. **Step 3:** group discussion – **30 minutes**. The trainer moderates a reflective group discussion. Sample questions for reflective discussion are, e.g.:
 - Based on the arguments developed during the group work, what are the best approaches for protection of intellectual property in the context of open sharing of data and other research outputs?
 - Do you have other suggestions for recognizing the contribution of authors of open datasets, methods etc.?

PLANNING

Resources and equipment:

- Handout "NS_U4A4.1 Handout"
- Make space for the trainees to work in small groups

FURTHER READINGS

1. Bull, S., & Bhagwandin, N. (2020). The ethics of data sharing and biobanking in health research. Wellcome Open Research, 5. <https://doi.org/10.12688/wellcomeopenres.16351.1>
2. Ross-Hellauer, T., Reichmann, S., Cole, N. L., Fessler, A., Klebel, T., & Pontika, N. (2022). Dynamics of cumulative advantage and threats to equity in open science: a scoping review. Royal Society Open Science, 9(1), 211032. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rsos.211032>
3. Vasilevsky, N. A. et al. (2021). Is authorship sufficient for today's collaborative research? A call for contributor roles. Accountability in Research, 28(1), 23-43. <https://doi.org/10.1080/08989621.2020.1779591>
4. Zeitlyn, D. (2003). Gift economies in the development of open source software: anthropological reflections. Research Policy, 32(7), 1287-1291. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0048-7333\(03\)00053-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0048-7333(03)00053-2)

Unit 5. The quality of the research outputs and data sets

Activity 5. Responsibility for the quality of research data

DESCRIPTION

This activity starts with homework where trainees are asked to read a paper on data quality in citizen science and create a mind map. The purpose of the mind map is to build a background knowledge for case discussion. It is followed by case discussion and development of guidelines for ensuring quality of citizen sciences data in natural sciences.

Type of activity: home readings and case discussion

Time: 90 min.

Target group: students, early career researchers **Learning outcomes:**

	Learning outcomes <i>It is expected that trainees will:</i>	Indicators for their achievement <i>Trainees who have fully met the learning outcome are</i>
	- be aware of importance of the data sets and research outputs and their responsible use	- explain how to responsibly and
	- apply critical thinking skills - questioning, comparing, summarizing, drawing conclusions, and defending - to case studies ethics and integrity in OS	- develop - discuss cases with colleagues - justify a personal position

PROCEDURE

1. At least a week before the workshop send trainees the required readings (file “NS_U5A5 Readings_Data Quality in Citizen Science”) and the handout for creating a mind map (file “NS_U5A5_1 Handout”).
2. Before the workshop trainees are required to read the required readings “NS_U5A5 Readings_Data Quality in Citizen Science”⁴.

⁴ Balázs, B., Mooney, P., Nováková, E., Bastin, L., Jokar Arsanjani, J. (2021). Data Quality in Citizen Science. In: The Science of Citizen Science. Springer https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-582784_8.

3. Before the workshop trainees should create a mind map on quality of data in citizen science, based on the required readings. Instructions for creating a mind map are included in the handout “NS_U5A5_1 Handout”.
4. In the classroom, introduce the activity, its aim and, briefly, the procedure.
5. Ask trainees to split in small groups (4-6 trainees in a group) and to choose a rapporteur - a group member who will report results of the small group discussion to the whole group.
6. Print out the case description (file “NS_U5A5_2 Handout”) for each trainee
7. **Step 1:** small group discussions – **40 minutes**. Trainees read the case description, discuss the challenges, use the ideas from required readings and develop recommendations. Each group fills in a table with challenges and recommendations. The table is included in the “NS_U5A5_2 Handout”. Rapporteurs prepare to present the results to the whole group.
8. **Step 2:** reports from small group discussions – **30 minutes**. Depending on the number of the small groups, allocate a time slot for each group presentation (e.g., if there are 3 small groups, each group have 10 minutes for a presentation). Rapporteurs present the results of their group discussions.
9. **Step 3:** group discussion – **20 minutes**. The trainer moderates a reflective group discussion. Sample questions for reflective discussion are, e.g.:
 - *Which ideas from the required readings helped you to develop recommendations? How?*
 - *Which of the recommendations developed during the groupwork are the most useful? Why?*
 - *In your view, what are other considerable ethical challenges for scientists collaborating with citizen scientists? How to address these challenges?*

PLANNING

Resources and equipment:

- Required readings “NS_U5A5 Readings_Data Quality in Citizen Science ”
 - Handout “NS_U5A5_1 Handout” for home reading and creating a mind map
 - Handout “NS_U5A5_2 Handout” for case discussion
-
- Make space for the trainees to work in small groups

FURTHER READINGS

1. Haklay, M. (2021). Why is it so difficult to integrate citizen science into practice? *Citizen Science and Public Policy Making*, 108. <https://discovery.ucl.ac.uk/id/eprint/10130136>
2. Herodotou, C., Scanlon, E., & Sharples, M. (2021). Methods of promoting learning and data quality in citizen and Community Science. *Frontiers in Climate*,

53. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fclim.2021.614567>

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Activity 5.1. Conflicts of interest in citizen science

DESCRIPTION

This activity is built around case discussion. Trainees are asked to discuss in small groups a case on risk conflicts of interest in citizen science. Afterwards, small groups report to the whole group and continue with a reflective discussion involving the whole group.

Type of activity: case discussion

Time: 90 min.

Target group: students, early career researchers, senior researchers **Learning outcomes:**

	Learning outcomes <i>It is expected that trainees will:</i>	Indicators for their achievement <i>Trainees who have fully met the learning outcome are able to:</i>
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> understand the concept of conflict of interest and how to deal with it 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> recognize and disclose conflicts of interest
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> apply critical thinking skills - questioning, comparing, summarizing, drawing conclusions and defending - to case studies ethics and integrity in OS 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> develop reports discuss cases with colleagues justify a personal position on

PROCEDURE

1. Print out the case description and questions for discussion for each trainee (file "NS_U5A5.1 Handout". You can also choose to watch the case in the classroom - **animation of this case is available on the [ROSIE webpage](#)**.
2. Introduce the activity, its aim and, briefly, the procedure.
3. Ask trainees to split in small groups (4-5 trainees in a group) and to choose a rapporteur - a group member who will report results of the small group discussion to the whole group. Provide each group with a paper for taking notes.
4. **Step 1:** small group discussions – **30 minutes**. Trainees read the case description and discuss the questions in small groups. Each group takes notes. Rapporteurs prepare to present the results to the whole group.
5. **Step 2:** reports from small group discussions – **30 minutes**. Depending on the number of the small groups, allocate a time slot for each group presentation (e.g., if there are 4 small groups, each group have 10 minutes for a presentation). Rapporteurs present the results of their group discussions.

6. **Step 3:** group discussion – **30 minutes**. The trainer moderates a reflective group discussion. The trainer writes the solutions suggested during the discussion on the whiteboard and summarises them. Sample questions for reflective discussion are, e.g.:

- *What is your personal experience with conflicts of interest in research?*
- *What types of conflicts of interests should be disclosed? Is there a consensus on that in your field of science?*
- *Do potential conflicts of interest in citizen science differ from potential conflicts of interest in science in general? If yes, what is the difference?*
- *How to deal with conflicts of interest in cases where they are discovered after the publication of a research study?*

PLANNING

Resources and equipment:

- Handout “NS_U5A5.1 Handout” and/or video of case animation
- Paper for taking notes during small group discussions
- Whiteboard for discussion notes
- Make space for the trainees to work in small groups

FURTHER READINGS

1. COPE Council (2021). COPE Flowcharts and infographics: Undisclosed conflict of interest in a published article. <https://doi.org/10.24318/cope.2019.2.7>
2. Macey, G. P., Breech, R., Chernaik, M., Cox, C., Larson, D., Thomas, D., & Carpenter, D. O. (2014). Air concentrations of volatile compounds near oil and gas production: a community-based exploratory study. *Environmental Health*, 13(1), 1-18. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1476-069X-13-82>
3. Resnik, D. B., Konecny, B., & Kissling, G. E. (2017). Conflict of interest and funding disclosure policies of environmental, occupational, and public health journals. *Journal of occupational and environmental medicine*, 59(1), 28. <https://doi.org/10.1097/JOM.0000000000000910>
4. The Embassy of Good Science: [“Conflict of interests”](#), [“Intellectual conflicts of interest”](#)

Unit 6. Responsible sharing and reuse of natural science data

Activity 6. Concerns to share and reuse data

DESCRIPTION

This activity starts with brainstorming where trainees are asked to share their views on sharing and reusing research data. It is followed by group discussion on concerns to share and reuse data, as well as possible solutions. **Type of activity:** brainstorming and group discussion

Time: 90 min.

Target group: students, early career researchers **Learning outcomes:**

	Learning outcomes <i>It is expected that trainees</i>	Indicators for their achievement <i>Trainees who have fully met t</i>
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> be aware about factors influencing willingness to share and reuse research data 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> discuss how to increase sharing and reuse of open data

PROCEDURE

- Step 1: brainstorming – 15 minutes.** The trainer starts brainstorming by posing two questions: (1) *“Are you ready to share your research data in an open data repository? Why yes or no?”* and (2) *“Are you ready to use open access data in your research? Why yes or no?”* and invite trainees to take a minute’s silence to think on it. Once the minute is up, invite everyone to share their views. Have a single person (trainer or one of trainees) who takes notes on a whiteboard. The main aim of brainstorming is just to listen to different views without criticism.
- Ask trainees to split in small groups (4-6 trainees in a group) and to choose a rapporteur - a group member who will report results of the small group discussion to the whole group.
- Distribute the handout (file “NS_U6A6 Handout”) to each group. Half of the groups receive Task 1 from the handout (“Sharing your own research data”), other groups get Task 2 from the handout (“Using open data created by other researchers”).
- Step 2: small group discussions – 30 minutes.** Trainees discuss and fill in a table with concerns and possible solutions. Rapporteurs prepare to present the results to the whole group.
- Step 3: reports from small group discussions – 30 minutes.** Depending on the number of the small groups, allocate a time slot for each group presentation (e.g., if there are 3 small groups, each group have 10 minutes for a presentation).
Rapporteurs present the results of their group discussions.
- Step 3: group discussion – 15 minutes.** The trainer moderates a reflective group discussion. Sample questions for reflective discussion are, e.g.:
 - What are the most important concerns discouraging researchers to share their data for reuse and to use open data created by other researchers? What are possible solutions?*
 - Are there any legitimate reasons not to share research data?*
 - How to responsibly share and reuse data in natural sciences?*

PLANNING

Resources and equipment:

- Handout “Handout NS_U6A6” printed out for each small group
- Whiteboard for discussion notes
- Make space for the trainees to work in small groups

FURTHER READINGS

1. Data sharing and the future of science. *Nature Communications* 9, 2817 (2018). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-018-05227-z>
2. Staunton, C., Barragán, C. A., Canali, S., Ho, C., Leonelli, S., Mayernik, M., ... & Wonkham, A. (2021). Open science, data sharing and solidarity: who benefits? *History and Philosophy of the Life Sciences*, 43(4), 115. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40656-021-00468-6>
3. McAllister, J. W. (2012). Climate science controversies and the demand for access to empirical data. *Philosophy of Science*, 79(5), 871-880. <https://doi.org/10.1086/667871>
4. Zuiderwijk, A., Shinde, R., & Jeng, W. (2020). What drives and inhibits researchers to share and use open research data? A systematic literature review to analyze factors influencing open research data adoption. *PloS one*, 15(9), e0239283. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0239283>

Activity 6.1. Case discussion on concerns about sharing the data

DESCRIPTION

This activity is built around case discussion. Trainees are asked to discuss in small groups cases on scientists’ concerns to share the data. Afterwards, small groups report to the whole group and continue with a reflective discussion involving the whole group.

Type of activity: case discussion

Time: 90 min.

Target group: early career researchers, senior researchers **Learning outcomes:**

	Learning outcomes <i>It is expected that trainees will:</i>	Indicators for their achievement <i>Trainees who have fully met the learning outcome are able to:</i>
	- aware about factors influencing willingness to share and use open research data	- discuss how to increase willingness to share and use open research data

	<p>li n resea</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - critical thinking skills - oning, comparing, aarizing, drawing conclusions, p:efending - to case studies on pand integrity in OS <p>l y q u e s t i s u r a n d d e t h i c s</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - develop reflective questions to define ethical problems in the case study - discuss cases with colleagues - justify a personal position on the case
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PROCEDURE

1. Depending on the size of the group and background of the trainees choose how many cases to discuss during the workshop. There are four cases included in the file "NS_U6A6.1 Handout". You can also choose to watch two of the cases in the classroom - **animations of cases are available on the [ROSIE webpage](#).**
2. Introduce the activity, its aim and, briefly, the procedure.
3. Ask trainees to split in small groups (4-5 trainees in a group) and to choose a rapporteur - a group member who will report results of the small group discussion to the whole group. Provide each group with a paper for taking notes.
4. Print out case description(s) and questions for discussion for each trainee (file "NS_U6A6.1 Handout").
5. **Step 1:** small group discussions – **30 minutes**. Trainees read the case description and discuss the questions in small groups. Each group takes notes. Rapporteurs prepare to present the results to the whole group.

6. **Step 2:** reports from small group discussions – **40 minutes**. Depending on the number of the small groups, allocate a time slot for each group presentation (e.g., if there are 4 small groups, each group have 10 minutes for a presentation).
Rapporteurs present the results of their group discussions.
7. **Step 3:** group discussion – **20 minutes**. The trainer moderates a reflective group discussion. The trainer writes the solutions suggested during the discussion on the whiteboard and summarises them. Sample questions for reflective discussion are, e.g.:
 - *What are the most important concerns discouraging researchers to share their data for reuse and to use open data created by other researchers? What are possible solutions?*
 - *Are there any legitimate reasons not to share research data?*
 - *How to responsibly share and reuse data in natural sciences?*

PLANNING

Resources and equipment:

- Handout “NS_U6A6.1 Handout” and/or animations of cases available on ROSiE webpage
- Paper for taking notes during small group discussions
- Whiteboard for discussion notes
- Make space for the trainees to work in small groups

FURTHER READINGS

1. Availability of Data. Nature portfolio. <https://www.nature.com/natureportfolio/editorial-policies/reporting-standards#availability-of-data>
2. Data sharing and the future of science. *Nat Commun* 9, 2817 (2018).
<https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-018-05227-z>
3. Gewin, V. (2016.) Data sharing: An open mind on open data. *Nature* 529.
<https://doi.org/10.1038/nj7584-117a>
4. Laine, H. (2017). Afraid of scooping: Case study on researcher strategies against fear of scooping in the context of open science. *Data Science Journal*.
<https://doi.org/10.5334/dsj-2017-029>
5. Staunton, C., Barragán, C. A., Canali, S., Ho, C., Leonelli, S., Mayernik, M., ... & Wonkham, A. (2021). Open science, data sharing and solidarity: who benefits? *History and Philosophy of the Life Sciences*, 43(4), 115. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40656-021-00468-6>
6. Zuiderwijk, A., Shinde, R., & Jeng, W. (2020). What drives and inhibits researchers to share and use open research data? A systematic literature review to analyze factors influencing open research data adoption. *PloS one*, 15(9), e0239283.
<https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0239283>

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Unit 7. Prevention of research malpractice in the context of OS

Activity 7. Violations of research integrity in OS and their prevention

The activity aims to discuss different types of violations of research integrity in OS and their prevention. The trainees are split into five groups and their task is to reflect on potential type of violation and preventive measure in each particular type of Open Science activity. Each group shares the results of their discussions, and group work is followed by plenary activity where all trainees have an opportunity to supplement the results of group work.

Type of activity: group work and plenary activity

Time: 90 minutes

Target group: students, early career researchers, senior researchers **Learning outcomes:**

	Learning outcomes <i>It is expected that trainees</i>	Indicators for their achievement <i>Trainees who have fully met the learning outcome are able to:</i>
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - potential types of research malpractice in OS 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - discuss causes of violations of research integrity in OS and ways of its prevention

PROCEDURE

1. Before the exercise, print out the pages with different types of Open Science activities (file "NS_U7A7 Printout") and mark sections of a wall with the titles:
 - *Open access publishing*
 - *Sharing and using open data*
 - *Open reproducible research, e.g., open lab notes, reproducing of research studies*
 - *Open science evaluation, e.g., open metrics and impact, open peer review – Citizen science*

2. Ask participants to split in five groups. Assign one of the types of Open Science activities listed above to each group.
3. **Step 1:** group discussion – **25 minutes**. Each group discusses the following questions in the context of the particular type of Open Science activities:
 - *What potential violations of research integrity may arise in the context of this type of open science activities?*
 - *How to prevent these potential violations?*

The results of the discussion should be written on paper cards/sticky notes – one potential type of violation and preventive measure on each card/sticky note and hung on the wall under the respective type of Open Science activities.
4. **Step 2:** group work presentations and general discussion – **65 minutes**. Each group presents their results in 5 minutes. After each presentation, there is 8 minutes general discussion where every trainee has an opportunity to suggest additional challenges and preventive measures. These additional challenges and preventive measures are written on paper cards/sticky notes and added to the respective type of Open Science activities.

PLANNING

Resources and equipment:

- Printout “NS_U7A7 Printout”
- Large wall or multiple pinboards to hang on printouts and results of discussions
- Empty cards & tape/sticky notes, pens/markers
- Make space for the trainees to work in small groups and to move around

FURTHER READINGS

1. Düwell, M. (2019). Open science and ethics. *Ethical Theory and Moral Practice*, 22, 1051-1053. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10677-019-10053-3>

Activity 7.1. Should scientists use access to pirated papers?

DESCRIPTION

This activity is built around case discussion. Trainees are asked to discuss in small groups a case on violations of intellectual property rights by providing access to pirated scientific publications. Afterwards, small groups report to the whole group and continue with a reflective discussion involving the whole group.

Type of activity: case discussion

Time: 90 minutes

Target group: students, early career researchers, senior researchers **Learning outcomes:**

	Learning outcomes <i>It is expected that trainees</i>	Indicators for their achievement <i>will: Trainees who have fully met the learning outcome are</i>
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – know potential types of research practice in OS 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – discuss causes of violations of research – recognise limits of OS for protection

PROCEDURE

1. Print out the case description and questions for discussion for each trainee (file “NS_U7A7.1 Handout”. You can also choose to watch the case in the classroom - **animation of this case is available on the [ROSiE webpage](#).**
2. Introduce the activity, its aim and, briefly, the procedure.
3. Ask trainees to split in small groups (4-5 trainees in a group) and to choose a rapporteur - a group member who will report results of the small group discussion to the whole group. Provide each group with a paper for taking notes.
4. **Step 1:** small group discussions – **30 minutes**. Trainees read the case description and discuss the questions in small groups. Each group takes notes. Rapporteurs prepare to present the results to the whole group.
5. **Step 2:** reports from small group discussions – **30 minutes**. Depending on the number of the small groups, allocate a time slot for each group presentation (e.g., if there are 4 small groups, each group have 10 minutes for a presentation).
Rapporteurs present the results of their group discussions.
6. **Step 3:** group discussion – **30 minutes**. The trainer moderates a reflective group discussion. The trainer writes the solutions suggested during the discussion on the whiteboard and summarises them. Sample questions for reflective discussion are, e.g.:
 - *How important are intellectual property rights for scientific research and achievements?*
 - *Does the case address a relevant issue for you and researchers you are working together?*
 - *What are potential solutions at the policy level to the problem described in the case?*

PLANNING

Resources and equipment:

- Handout “NS_U7A7.1 Handout” and/or video of case animation
- Paper for taking notes during small group discussions
- Whiteboard for discussion notes
- Make space for the trainees to work in small groups

FURTHER READINGS

1. Monbiot, G. Scientific publishing is a rip-off. We fund the research - it should be free. *The Guardian*. 13.09. 2018.
<https://www.theguardian.com/commentisfree/2018/sep/13/scientificpublishing-rip-off-taxpayers-fund-research>. Accessed August 2, 2022.
2. Van Noorden, R. (2016). Alexandra Elbakyan: Paper pirate. *Nature*, 540, 512.
<https://www.nature.com/articles/540507a>
3. Vogel, G., & Kupferschmidt, K. (2017). A bold open-access push in Germany could change the future of academic publishing. *Science*, 23.
<https://www.science.org/content/article/bold-open-access-push-germany-couldchange-future-academic-publishing>

Unit 8. Responsible dissemination and publication practices

Activity 8. Open access publishing and predatory practices

DESCRIPTION

This activity applies the Four Quadrant Method for case analysis on predatory practices. Trainees are asked to discuss a case in small groups and fill in the four quadrant template. Afterwards, small groups report to the whole group and continue with a casuistic reasoning and justification discussion involving the whole group.

Type of activity: case discussion (Four Quadrant Method)

Time: 90 min.

Target group: students, early career researchers, senior researchers **Learning outcomes:**

Learning outcomes	Indicators for their achievement
<i>It is expected that trainees will:</i>	<i>Trainees who have fully met the learning outcome are able to:</i>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> know criteria for good practice standards in open access publishing 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> critically assess scientific results published in open access and identify predatory publishing practices
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> apply critical thinking skills - questioning, comparing, summarizing, drawing conclusions and defending - to case studies and integrity in OS 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> develop reflective questions to define ethical problems in the case study discuss cases with colleagues justify a personal position on the case

PROCEDURE

1. Introduce the activity, its aim and, briefly, the procedure of the Four Quadrant Method⁴.

⁴ Detailed description of the modified Four Quadrant Method for case analysis is provided by the ENTIRE project: Armond A.C. et al. (2019). [D.5.3 Delivery of the entire set of case deliberation methods and case analyses as input for the platform](#), pp. 98-102.

<https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/documents/downloadPublic?documentIds=080166e5c3a7e938&appId=PPGMS>

2. Print out the case description (file “NS_U8A8 Handout”) for each trainee.
3. Ask trainees to split in small groups (3-4 trainees in a group) and to choose a rapporteur - a group member who will report results of the small group discussion to the whole group.
4. **Step 1.** Initial perception – **20 minutes**. Trainees read the case and in small groups discuss some general questions to identify relevant aspects of the case:
 - *What are the ethical issues at stake in this case?*
 - *Who are the stakeholders?*
 - *How should stakeholders react to this case?*
 - *What should/can stakeholders do to prevent such cases?*
5. **Step 2.** The Four Quadrant Analysis – **20 minutes**. Each group fills in the four quadrant table included in the file “NS_U8A8 Handout”.

<p>I. Relevant Facts: What are the most relevant facts concerning the situation?</p>	<p>II. Uncertainties: Which features of the situation are uncertain, lacking in clarity, or controversial?</p>
<p>III. Courses of Action: What are the practically available options for providing a solution to the case (how to react to the case and how to prevent such cases in the future)?</p>	<p>IV. Contextual Features: What legal, financial and institutional policies and regulations apply to the case?</p>

6. **Step 3.** Reports from small groups – **20 minutes**. The small groups report the results of the Four Quadrant Analysis to the whole group.
7. **Step 4.** Casuistic Reasoning and Justification – **30 minutes**. The trainer moderates the whole group discussion on the following questions:
 - *What is at issue? What is the major ethical issue at the case?*
 - *Do you know other cases like this one?*
 - *Why do academics publish their research in a predatory journal or books published by predatory publishers? What are the main factors that motivate such a practice? What are negative consequences of such a practice? What policies might minimise predatory publishing practices?*
 - *How should stakeholders react to cases like this?*

PLANNING

Resources and equipment:

- Handout “NS_U8A8 Handout”
- Make space for the trainees to work in small groups

FURTHER READINGS

1. Bartholomew, R. E. (2014). Science for sale: The rise of predatory journals. *Journal of the Royal Society of Medicine*, 107(10), 384–385. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0141076814548526>
2. Beall, J. (2015). Criteria for determining predatory open access publishers. <https://beallist.net/wp-content/uploads/2019/12/criteria-2015.pdf>
3. Kurt, S. (2018). Why do authors publish in predatory journals? *Learned Publishing*, 31(2), 141-147. <https://doi.org/10.1002/leap.1150>
4. The Embassy of Good Science: “[Predatory publishing](#)”

Activity 8.1. Open peer review

DESCRIPTION

This activity is built around case discussion. Trainees are asked to discuss in small groups a case on open peer review. Afterwards, small groups report to the whole group and continue with a reflective discussion involving the whole group.

Type of activity: case discussion

Time: 90 min.

Target group: early career researchers, senior researchers **Learning outcomes:**

	Learning outcomes <i>It is expected that trainees will:</i>	Indicators for their achievement <i>Trainees who have fully met the learning outcome are able to:</i>
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - aware of importance of open peer review practices 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - explain how to responsibly and critically perform open peer review
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - apply critical thinking skills - questioning, comparing, summarizing, drawing conclusions, and defending - to case studies on ethics and integrity in OS 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - develop reflective questions to define ethical problems in the case study - discuss cases with colleagues - justify a personal position on the case

PROCEDURE

1. Introduce the activity, its aim and, briefly, the procedure.
2. Ask trainees to split in small groups (4-5 trainees in a group) and to choose a rapporteur - a group member who will report results of the small group discussion to the whole group. Provide each group with a paper for taking notes.
3. Print out case description and questions for discussion for each trainee (file "NS_U8A8.1 Handout").
4. **Step 1:** small group discussions – **30 minutes**. Trainees read the case description and discuss the questions in small groups. Each group takes notes. Rapporteurs prepare to present the results to the whole group.

5. **Step 2:** reports from small group discussions – **40 minutes**. Depending on the number of the small groups, allocate a time slot for each group presentation (e.g., if there are 4 small groups, each group has 10 minutes for a presentation).
Rapporteurs present the results of their group discussions.
6. **Step 3:** group discussion – **20 minutes**. The trainer moderates a reflective group discussion. The trainer writes the ideas suggested during the discussion on the whiteboard and summarise them. Sample questions for reflective discussion are, e.g.:
 - *What is the role of open peer review in the scientific publishing process?*
 - *What are the benefits and risks of open peer review?*

PLANNING

Resources and equipment:

- Handout “NS_U8A8.1 Handout”
- Paper for taking notes during small group discussions
- Whiteboard for discussion notes
- Make space for the trainees to work in small groups

FURTHER READINGS

1. Harms, P. D., & Credé, M. (2020). Bringing the review process into the 21st century: Post-publication peer review. *Industrial and Organizational Psychology*, 13(1), 51-53. <https://doi.org/10.1017/iop.2020.13>
2. Ross-Hellauer, T., Deppe, A., & Schmidt, B. (2017). Survey on open peer review: Attitudes and experience amongst editors, authors and reviewers. *PloS One*, 12(12), e0189311. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0189311>
3. Tenorio-Fornés, Á., Tirador, E. P., Sánchez-Ruiz, A. A., & Hassan, S. (2021). Decentralizing science: Towards an interoperable open peer review ecosystem using blockchain. *Information Processing & Management*, 58(6), 102724. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ipm.2021.102724>
4. The Embassy of Good Science: “[Post-publication peer review](#)”
5. The Embassy of Good Science: “[Open peer review - transparent way of gatekeeping science](#)”

ROSIE

TRAINING MATERIALS for Responsible Open Science Part IV: Health and Life Sciences

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Introduction

The aim of the ROSiE Training Materials for Responsible Open Science is to learn how to practice Open Science (OS) responsibly and how to prevent research misconduct in the context of OS by providing necessary knowledge and developing specific skills and attitudes.

In the ROSiE Didactic Framework, we have identified the following transversal skills and attitudes necessary for responsible practising of OS in four domains: (i) local and global citizenship, (ii) personal and social responsibility, (iii) epistemic skills, and (iv) collaborative problem-solving.

Local and global citizenship

- awareness of the importance and social benefits of OS and citizen science in local and global contexts
- participation in ethics and integrity self-regulation of OS and citizen science community

Personal and social responsibility

- personal and professional responsibility for implementation of OS and production of results
- openness to share own research data, results, tools and publications and appreciation of efforts of others

Epistemic skills

- ability to organize, present and use open data and knowledge with integrity
- ability to critically assess data, knowledge and scientific results produced by others
- ability to identify ethical and integrity issues in OS

Collaborative problem-solving

- ability to apply critical thinking skills in collaborative analysis of ethical and integrity problems in OS
- discussing, finding solutions and making decisions to handle ethics and integrity issues within OS community

To achieve optimal results, the ROSiE training materials rely on several learning and teaching strategies: (i) collaborative problem solving; (ii) case-based activities; (iii) dialogical activities; and (iv) transformative learning. More information about these teaching strategies can be found in the ROSiE Didactic Framework.

The training material consists of a trainers' file including 8 units and respective activities, as well as a separate folder including materials for trainees – required readings, handouts and printouts. The activities can be implemented separately (e.g., for organising a single workshop to discuss cases) or for

organising a complete two-day training course. The suggested schedule for the training course is as follows:

Time	DAY 1	Type of activity
90 min.	Unit 1. Ethical and societal foundations of OS, its purpose	Home readings and Socratic seminar
15 min.	Break	
90 min.	Unit 2. Protection of research participants, animals, plants and ecosystems in OS	Case discussions
60 min.	Lunch break	
90 min.	Unit 3. Ethical aspects of citizen science in the context of OS	Home readings and group project
15 min.	Break	
90 min.	Unit 4. Protection of intellectual property in the context of OS	Case discussion (Pro and Contra)
Time	DAY 2	Type of activity
90 min.	Unit 5. The quality of the research outputs and data sets	Home reading and case discussion OR Case discussion
15 min.	Break	
90 min.	Unit 6. Responsible sharing and reuse of open science data	Brainstorming and group discussion OR Case discussion
60 min.	Lunch break	
90 min.	Unit 7. Prevention of research malpractice in the context of OS	Group work and plenary activity OR Case discussion
15 min.	Break	
90 min.	Unit 8. Responsible dissemination and publication practices	Case discussion (Four Quadrant Method)

Unit 1. Ethical and societal foundations of OS, its purpose

Activity 1. Principles, values, benefits and risks of OS

DESCRIPTION

This activity starts with homework where trainees are asked to read [UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science](#) and fill in the double-entry reading journal. The purpose of the reading journal is to allow trainees to express their thoughts and reflect on the text. It is followed by classroom discussion in a

form of a Socratic seminar on the principles and values of OS, as well as main benefits and challenges in OS implementation.

Type of activity: home reading and Socratic seminar

Time: 90 min.

Target groups: students, early career researchers, senior researchers **Learning outcomes:**

	Learning outcomes <i>It is expected that trainees will:</i>	Indicators for their achievement <i>Trainees who have fully met the learning outcome are able to:</i>
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - demonstrate knowledge of ethical foundations of OS ⋮ ⋮ ⋮ ⋮ 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - explain and discuss principles and values of OS, its ethical foundations, and social benefits
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - understand the significance of OS and citizen science for identifying and solving scientific problems and societal challenges ⋮ ⋮ ⋮ ⋮ 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - provide examples of role of OS and citizen science in identifying and solving scientific problems and societal challenges

PROCEDURE

1. At least a week before the workshop send trainees the required readings ([UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science](#), file “HL_U1A1 Readings UNESCO Recommendation”) and the handout (file “HL_U1A1 Handout”).
2. Before the workshop trainees are required to read parts I., II. and III. of the [UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science](#) (pp. 6-19).
3. Before the workshop trainees should fill in the double-entry reading journal table in the handout (file “HL_U1A1 Handout”). The left side should contain quotations from the UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science with page numbers noted. The right side should contain trainee’s response to each quotation - a question, commentary, analysis. When filling in the table, trainees may use the following prompts, included in the handout:
 - *I agree/disagree with..., because...*
 - *It is not clear for me...*
 - *I see the following challenges...*
 - *I have a question regarding...*

4. The classroom discussion is organized as a Socratic seminar. The aim of the Socratic seminar is to achieve “*a deeper understanding about the ideas and values in a particular text*”⁵. The trainer is facilitator of the discussion, the discussion is led by using open-ended, high-level questions. Trainees are sitting in a circle.
5. The Socratic Seminar starts with introduction of the rules:
 - Only those trainees who have read the text and filled in the double-entry reading journal are allowed to participate;
 - It is important to focus on the text and to refer to evidence from the text;
 - Trainees are encouraged to talk to each other, not just to the trainer and to listen and respond to others’ arguments.
6. Common questions used during a Socratic Seminar activity both by trainer and trainees include:
 - *What does this concept/idea/phrase etc. mean?*
 - *What do you think the authors are trying to say?*
 - *Is this what you mean to say...?*
 - *What is the origin of this?*
 - *What are the implications of this?*
 - *What else could that mean?* – *What would happen if....?*
7. This [overview of Socratic seminar](#) provides a list of suitable questions and more information about how to prepare for a discussion.

PLANNING

Resources and equipment:

- Handout “HL_U1A1 Handout”
- Required readings “HL_U1A1 Readings UNESCO Recommendation” – Make space for the trainees to sit in a circle

FURTHER READINGS

1. Allen, C., & Mehler, D. M. A. (2019). Open science challenges, benefits and tips in early career and beyond. *PLOS Biology*, 17(5), e3000246. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pbio.3000246>
2. Castellanos-Reyes, D. (2020). Socratic Seminar. In R. Kimmons & S. Caskurlu (Eds.), *The Students' Guide to Learning Design and Research*. EdTech Books. https://edtechbooks.org/studentguide/socratic_seminar
3. Düwell, M. (2019). Open science and ethics. *Ethical Theory and Moral Practice*, 22(5), 1051-1053. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10677-019-10053-3>

⁵ Castellanos-Reyes, D. (2020). Socratic Seminar. In R. Kimmons & S. Caskurlu (Eds.), *The Students' Guide to Learning Design and Research*. EdTech Books. https://edtechbooks.org/studentguide/socratic_seminar

4. Tennant, J. P., Waldner, F., Jacques, D. C., Masuzzo, P., Collister, L. B., & Hartgerink, C. H. (2016). The academic, economic and societal impacts of Open Access: an evidence-based review. *F1000Research*, 5.
<https://f1000research.com/articles/5632/v3>

UNDER REVIEW BY THE EUROPEAN COMMISSION

Unit 2. Protection of research participants, animals, plants and ecosystems in OS

Activity 2. Privacy of research participants in the context of OS

DESCRIPTION

This activity is built around case discussion. Trainees are asked to discuss in small groups one or two cases on ethical issues in sharing data and research results in open access in health and life sciences. Afterwards, small groups report to the whole group and continue with a reflective discussion involving the whole group.

Type of activity: case discussion

Time: 90 min.

Target group: students, early career researchers, senior researchers **Learning outcomes:**

	Learning outcomes <i>It is expected that trainees will:</i>	Indicators for their achievement <i>Trainees who have fully met the learning outcome are able to:</i>
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> recognize and analyse the risks search participants in the con OS 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> discuss how to minimize risks to research participants when practicing OS
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> apply critical thinking skills - questioning, comparing, summarizing, drawing conclusions and defending - to case studies and integrity in OS 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> develop reflective questions to define ethical problems in the case study discuss cases with colleagues justify a personal position on the case

PROCEDURE

- Depending on the size of the group and background of the trainees choose whether you will discuss one or both cases during the workshop. The cases are included in the file "HL_U2A2 Handout".
- Introduce the activity, its aim and, briefly, the procedure.

3. Ask trainees to split in small groups (4-5 trainees in a group) and to choose a rapporteur - a group member who will report results of the small group discussion to the whole group. Provide each group with a paper for taking notes.
4. Print out case description(s) and questions for discussion for each trainee (file "HL_U2A2 Handout").
5. **Step 1:** small group discussions – **30 minutes**. Trainees read the case description and discuss the questions in small groups. Each group takes notes. Rapporteurs prepare to present the results to the whole group.
6. **Step 2:** reports from small group discussions – **40 minutes**. Depending on the number of the small groups, allocate a time slot for each group presentation (e.g., if there are 4 small groups, each group has 10 minutes for a presentation). Rapporteurs present the results of their group discussions.
7. **Step 3:** group discussion – **20 minutes**. The trainer moderates a reflective group discussion. The trainer writes the ideas suggested during the discussion on the whiteboard and summarise them. Sample questions for reflective discussion are, e.g.:
 - *How to inform research participants about open sharing of data and obtain informed consent?*
 - *What makes health and genomic data special? What scientists should take into account before sharing health and genomic data?*
 - *How to ensure the privacy of research participants? Is it possible to anonymize health and genetic data?*

PLANNING

Resources and equipment:

- Handout "HL_U2A2 Handout"
- Paper for taking notes during small group discussions
- Whiteboard for discussion notes
- Make space for the trainees to work in small groups

FURTHER READINGS

1. The Embassy of Good Science: "[Privacy in research](#)"
2. O'Keefe, C. M., & Connolly, C. J. (2010). Privacy and the use of health data for research. *Medical Journal of Australia*, 193(9), 537-541. <https://doi.org/10.5694/j.1326-5377.2010.tb04041.x>

Activity 2.1. Protection of animals, plants, and ecosystems in OS

DESCRIPTION

This activity is built around case discussion. Trainees are asked to discuss in small groups a case on ethical issues in sharing data related to protection of animals, plants and ecosystems in open access. Afterwards, small groups report to the whole group and continue with a reflective discussion involving the whole group.

Type of activity:

case discussion

Time: 90 min.

Target group: students, early career researchers, senior researchers **Learning outcomes:**

	Learning outcomes <i>It is expected that trainees will:</i>	Indicators for their achievement <i>Trainees who have fully met the learning outcome are able to:</i>
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> recognize and analyse the risks to environment, plants, animals, and ecosystems in the context of OS 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> discuss how to minimize risks to environment, plants, animals, and ecosystems when practicing OS
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> apply critical thinking skills - questioning, comparing, summarizing, drawing conclusions and defending - to case studies and integrity in OS 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> develop reflective questions to define ethical problems in the case study discuss cases with colleagues justify a personal position on the case

PROCEDURE

1. Introduce the activity, its aim and, briefly, the procedure.
2. Ask trainees to split in small groups (4-5 trainees in a group) and to choose a rapporteur - a group member who will report results of the small group discussion to the whole group. Provide each group with a paper for taking notes.
3. Print out the case description and questions for discussion for each trainee (file "HL_U2A2.1 Handout").
4. **Step 1:** small group discussions – **30 minutes**. Trainees read the case description and discuss the questions in small groups. Each group takes notes. Rapporteurs prepare to present the results to the whole group.
5. **Step 2:** reports from small group discussions – **40 minutes**. Depending on the number of the small groups, allocate a time slot for each group presentation (e.g., if there are 4 small groups, each group has 10 minutes for a presentation). Rapporteurs present the results of their group discussions.

6. **Step 3:** group discussion – **20 minutes**. The trainer moderates a reflective group discussion. The trainer writes the ideas suggested during the discussion on the whiteboard and summarise them. Sample questions for reflective discussion are, e.g.:

- *What makes data on animal and plant species and ecosystems special?*
- *What scientists should take into account before sharing data on animal and plant species and ecosystems?*
- *Who is responsible for protection of animals, plants and ecosystems in the context of OS?*

PLANNING

Resources and equipment:

- Handout “HL_U2A2.1 Handout”
- Paper for taking notes during small group discussions
- Whiteboard for discussion notes
- Make space for the trainees to work in small groups

FURTHER READINGS

1. Soroye, P., Edwards, B. P., Buxton, R. T., Ethier, J. P., Frempong-Manso, A., Keefe, H. E., ... & Bennett, J. R. (2022). The risks and rewards of community science for threatened species monitoring. *Conservation Science and Practice*, 4(9), e12788.
<https://doi.org/10.1111/csp2.12788>
2. <https://www.inaturalist.org/pages/about>
3. <https://ebird.org/about>

Unit 3. Ethical aspects of citizen science in the context of OS

Activity 3. Development of an ethically sound citizen science project

DESCRIPTION

This activity involves home reading before the classroom activity, to introduce the concept of citizen science in the context of health and life sciences. It is followed by group projects onsite where trainees are asked to develop idea for their own citizen science projects in health or life sciences and analyse ethical aspects of these projects.

Type of activity: home reading and group project

Time: 90 minutes

Target group: students, early career researchers, senior researchers **Learning outcomes:**

	Learning outcomes <i>It is expected that trainees will:</i>	Indicators for their achievement <i>Trainees who have fully met the learning outcome are able to:</i>
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - understand the significance of citizen science for identifying and solving scientific problems and societal challenges 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - provide examples for role of citizen science in identifying and solving scientific problems and societal challenges

PROCEDURE

1. At least one week before the workshop, send trainees the required readings (file “HL_U3A3_1_The Rise of Citizen Science in Health and Biomedical Research” and/or “HL_U3A3_2_Meeting the needs of underserved populations”²). You can use both or one of the readings depending on circumstances and your preferences.
2. During the workshop, introduce the group activity, its aim and briefly, the procedure.

² Wiggins, A., Wilbanks, J. (2019). The rise of citizen science in health and biomedical research. *The American Journal of Bioethics*, 19(8), 3-14. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15265161.2019.1619859> Fiske, A., Prainsack, B., & Buyx, A. (2019). Meeting the needs of underserved populations: Setting the agenda for more inclusive citizen science of medicine. *Journal of Medical Ethics*, 45(9), 617– 622. <https://doi.org/10.1136/medethics-2018-105253>

3. Ask trainees to split into three groups. The group task is to develop an idea for a citizen science project in health or life sciences, based on definitions and examples provided in the required readings. For taking notes print one copy of “HL_U3A3 Handout” for each group.
4. **Step 1** development of the project idea – **30 minutes**. Each group should discuss and fill in table 1 in the “HL_U3A3 Handout”.
5. **Step 2** reflection on ethical aspects of the project – **30 minutes**. Each group should discuss and fill in table 2 in the “HL_U3A3 Handout”.
6. **Step 3** presentation of group projects and general discussion – **30 minutes**.
 Sample questions for reflective discussion are, e.g.:
 - *What does citizen life science can add to the field of health and life sciences?*
 - *What are the main ethical challenges and their solutions in citizen science projects in health and life sciences?*

PLANNING

Resources and equipment:

- Readings “HL_U3A3_1_The Rise of Citizen Science in Health and Biomedical Research” and/or “HL_U3A3_2_Meeting the needs of underserved populations” and Handout “HL_U3A3 Handout”
- Make space for the trainees to work in small groups

FURTHER READINGS

1. Balázs, B., Mooney, P., Nováková, E., Bastin, L., Jokar Arsanjani, J. (2021). Data Quality in Citizen Science. In: *The Science of Citizen Science*. Springer https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-58278-4_8
2. Palmer, R.B., Brocklehurst, M., Tyson E., Bowser, A., Pauwels, E., Bartumeus, F., (2018). Global mosquito alert. Chapter 11 In: Hecker, S., Haklay, M., Bowser, A., Makuch, Z., Vogel, J. & Bonn, A. (Eds.) *Citizen Science: Innovation in Open Science, Society and Policy*. UCL Press, London, pp. 210-215. <https://doi.org/10.14324/111.9781787352339>

Unit 4. Protection of intellectual property in the context of OS

Activity 4. Authorship and contributorship in citizen science

DESCRIPTION

This activity is built around case discussion and involves evaluating pro and contra arguments for different types of acknowledging citizen scientist contributions to research. Trainees are asked to discuss the case in small groups, develop and discuss their arguments. Afterwards, small groups report to the whole group and continue with a reflective discussion involving the whole group.

Type of activity: case discussion

Time: 90 min.

Target group: students, early career researchers, senior researchers **Learning outcomes:**

	Learning outcomes <i>It is expected that trainees will:</i>	Indicators for their achievement <i>Trainees who have fully met the learning outcome are able to:</i>
	- b: aware of protection of intellectual property in OS	- acknowledge authors and contributors of open data sets and other research outputs
	- b: aware of citizen scientists’ rights to be recognised and acknowledged by academic scientists and society	- discuss and assert their right to be recognized and acknowledged by academic scientists and society

		et /	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – apply critical thinking skills - questioning, comparing, summarizing, drawing conclusions and defending - to case studies and integrity in OS 	o is s i i	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – develop reflective questions to define ethical problems in the case study – discuss cases with colleagues – justify a personal position on the case

PROCEDURE

1. Introduce the activity, its aim and, briefly, the procedure.
2. Ask trainees to split in small groups (3-4 trainees in a group) and to choose a rapporteur - a group member who will report results of the small group discussion to the whole group.
3. Print out the case description and questions for discussion for each trainee (file “HL_U4A4 Handout”. You can also choose to watch the case in the classroom - **animation of this case is available on the [ROSIE webpage](#).**
4. **Step 1:** small group discussions – **30 minutes**. Trainees read or watch the case and discuss the questions in small groups. Each group fills in the table included in the handout with pro and contra arguments. Rapporteurs prepare to present the results to the whole group.
5. **Step 2:** short reports from small group discussions – **20 minutes**. Rapporteurs present the results of their group discussions - pro and contra arguments for each type of acknowledging the contribution of citizen scientists in this case.
6. **Step 3:** group discussion – **40 minutes**. The trainer moderates a reflective group discussion. Sample questions for reflective discussion are, e.g.:
 - *Based on the pro and contra arguments developed during the group work, what is the best solution for this case?*
 - *Do you have other suggestions for recognizing the contribution of citizen scientists in scientific publications*

PLANNING

Resources and equipment:

- Handout “HL_U4A4 Handout” and/or video of case animation
- Make space for the trainees to work in small groups

FURTHER READINGS

1. COPE Council (2003). How to Handle Authorship Disputes: A Guide for New Researchers. <https://doi.org/10.24318/cope.2018.1.1>
2. ICMJE. Defining the role of authors and contributors. <https://bit.ly/N7uoq3>

3. Smith, E., Bélisle-Pipon, J. C., & Resnik, D. (2019). Patients as research partners; how to value their perceptions, contribution and labor? *Citizen science: theory and practice*, 4(1). <https://doi.org/10.5334/cstp.184>
4. The Embassy of Good Science: "[Authorship criteria](#)"
5. Vasilevsky, N. A. et al. (2021). Is authorship sufficient for today's collaborative research? A call for contributor roles. *Accountability in Research*, 28(1), 23-43. <https://doi.org/10.1080/08989621.2020.1779591>

Activity 4.1. Inequities and potential of exploitation in OS

DESCRIPTION

This activity is built around case discussion. Trainees are asked to discuss in small groups a case on ethical issues on protection of intellectual property in OS in life sciences and medicine, especially in the context of low- and middle- income countries. Afterwards, small groups report to the whole group and continue with a reflective discussion involving the whole group.

Type of activity: case discussion

Time: 90 min.

Target group: students, early career researchers, senior researchers **Learning outcomes:**

	Learning outcomes <i>It is expected that trainees will:</i>	Indicators for their achievement <i>Trainees who have fully met the learning outcome are able to:</i>
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - aware of protection of intellectual property in OS 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - acknowledge authors and contributors of open data sets and other research outputs
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - apply critical thinking skills - questioning, comparing, summarizing, drawing conclusions, and defending - to case studies on ethics and integrity in OS 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - develop reflective questions to define ethical problems in the case study - discuss cases with colleagues - justify a personal position on the case

PROCEDURE

1. Introduce the activity, its aim and, briefly, the procedure.

2. Ask trainees to split in small groups (3-4 trainees in a group) and to choose a rapporteur - a group member who will report results of the small group discussion to the whole group.
3. Print out the case description and questions for discussion for each trainee (file "HL_U4A4.1 Handout").
4. **Step 1:** small group discussions – **30 minutes**. Trainees read the case description and discuss the questions in small groups. Rapporteurs prepare to present the results to the whole group.
5. **Step 2:** short reports from small group discussions – **30 minutes**. Rapporteurs present the results of their group discussions.
6. **Step 3:** group discussion – **30 minutes**. The trainer moderates a reflective group discussion. Sample questions for reflective discussion are, e.g.:
 - *Based on the arguments developed during the group work, what are the best approaches for protection of intellectual property in the context of open sharing of data and other research outputs?*
 - *Do you have other suggestions for recognizing the contribution of authors of open datasets, methods etc.?*

PLANNING

Resources and equipment:

- Handout "HL_U4A4.1 Handout"
- Make space for the trainees to work in small groups

FURTHER READINGS

1. Bull, S., & Bhagwandin, N. (2020). The ethics of data sharing and biobanking in health research. *Wellcome Open Research*, 5. <https://doi.org/10.12688/wellcomeopenres.16351.1>
2. Ross-Hellauer, T., Reichmann, S., Cole, N. L., Fessl, A., Klebel, T., & Pontika, N. (2022). Dynamics of cumulative advantage and threats to equity in open science: a scoping review. *Royal Society Open Science*, 9(1), 211032. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rsos.211032>
3. Vasilevsky, N. A. et al. (2021). Is authorship sufficient for today's collaborative research? A call for contributor roles. *Accountability in Research*, 28(1), 23-43. <https://doi.org/10.1080/08989621.2020.1779591>
4. Zeitlyn, D. (2003). Gift economies in the development of open source software: anthropological reflections. *Research Policy*, 32(7), 1287-1291. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0048-7333\(03\)00053-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0048-7333(03)00053-2)

Unit 5. The quality of the research outputs and data sets

Activity 5. Responsibility for the quality of research data

DESCRIPTION

This activity starts with homework where trainees are asked to read a paper on data quality in citizen science and create a mind map. The purpose of the mind map is to build a background knowledge for case discussion. It is followed by case discussion and development of guidelines for ensuring quality of citizen sciences data in health and life sciences.

Type of activity: home reading and case discussion **Time:** 90 min.

Target group: students, early career researchers **Learning outcomes:**

	Learning outcomes <i>It is expected that trainees will:</i>	Indicators for their achievement <i>Trainees who have fully met the learning outcome are able to:</i>
	be aware of importance of the quality of data sets and research outputs in OS and their responsible use	– explain how to responsibly and critically assess and use open data and research outputs
	apply critical thinking skills - questioning, comparing, summarizing, drawing conclusions, and defending - to case studies on ethics and integrity in OS	– develop reflective questions to define ethical problems in the case study – discuss cases with colleagues – justify a personal position on the case

PROCEDURE

1. At least a week before the workshop, send trainees the required readings (file “HL_U5A5_Data Quality in Citizen Science”) and the handout for creating a mind map (file “HL_U5A5_1 Handout”).
Before the workshop trainees are required to read the required readings “HL_U5A5_Data Quality in Citizen Science”³.

³ Balázs, B., Mooney, P., Nováková, E., Bastin, L., Jokar Arsanjani, J. (2021). Data Quality in Citizen Science. In: The Science of Citizen Science. Springer https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-582784_8.

2. Before the workshop trainees should create a mind map on the quality of data in citizen science, based on the required readings. Instructions for creating a mind map are included in the handout “HL_U5A5_1 Handout”.
3. In the classroom, introduce the activity, its aim and, briefly, the procedure.
4. Ask trainees to split in small groups (4-6 trainees in a group) and to choose a rapporteur - a group member who will report results of the small group discussion to the whole group.
5. Print out the case description (file “HL_U5A5_2 Handout”) for each trainee.
6. **Step 1:** small group discussions – **40 minutes**. Trainees read or watch the case, discuss the challenges, use the ideas from required readings and develop recommendations. Each group

fills in a table with challenges and recommendations. The table is included in the “HL_U5A5_2 Handout”. Rapporteurs prepare to present the results to the whole group.

7. **Step 2:** reports from small group discussions – **30 minutes**. Depending on the number of the small groups, allocate a time slot for each group presentation (e.g., if there are 3 small groups, each group have 10 minutes for a presentation).
Rapporteurs present the results of their group discussions.
8. **Step 3:** group discussion – **20 minutes**. The trainer moderates a reflective group discussion. Sample questions for reflective discussion are, e.g.:
 - *Which ideas from the required readings helped you to develop recommendations? How?*
 - *Which of the recommendations developed during the groupwork are the most useful? Why?*
 - *In your view, what are other considerable ethical challenges for scientists collaborating with citizen scientists? How to address these challenges?*

PLANNING

Resources and equipment:

- Required readings “HL_U5A5_Data Quality in Citizen Science”
- Handout “HL_U5A5_1 Handout” for home reading and creating a mind map
- Handout “HL_U5A5_2 Handout” for case discussion
- Make space for the trainees to work in small groups

FURTHER READINGS

1. Haklay, M. (2021). Why is it so difficult to integrate citizen science into practice? *Citizen Science and Public Policy Making*, 108. <https://discovery.ucl.ac.uk/id/eprint/10130136>.
2. Jollymore, A., Haines, M.J., Satterfield, T., Johnson, M.S. (2017). Citizen science for water quality monitoring: Data implications of citizen perspectives. *Journal of Environmental Management*, 200, pp. 456-467. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2017.05.083>.

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Activity 5.1. Conflicts of interest

DESCRIPTION

This activity is built around case discussion. Trainees are asked to discuss in small groups a case on risk conflicts of interest in citizen science. Afterwards, small groups report to the whole group and continue with a reflective discussion involving the whole group.

Type of activity: case discussion

Time: 90 min.

Target group: students, early career researchers, senior researchers **Learning outcomes:**

	Learning outcomes <i>It is expected that trainees will:</i>	Indicators for their achievement <i>Trainees who have fully met the learning outcome are able to:</i>
	understand the concept of conflict of interest and how to deal with it	– recognize and disclose conflicts of interest in cases when citizen scientists have personal or political interests at stake
	apply critical thinking skills - questioning, comparing, summarizing, drawing conclusions, and defending - to case studies on ethics and integrity in OS	– develop reflective questions to define ethical problems in the case study – discuss cases with colleagues – justify a personal position on the case

PROCEDURE

1. Print out the case description and questions for discussion for each trainee (file “HL_U5A5.1 Handout”). You can also choose to watch the case in the classroom - **animation of this case is available on the [ROSIE webpage](#).**
2. Introduce the activity, its aim and, briefly, the procedure.
3. Ask trainees to split in small groups (4-5 trainees in a group) and to choose a rapporteur - a group member who will report results of the small group discussion to the whole group. Provide each group with a paper for taking notes.
4. **Step 1:** small group discussions – **30 minutes**. Trainees read the case description and discuss the questions in small groups. Each group takes notes. Rapporteurs prepare to present the results to the whole group.

5. **Step 2:** reports from small group discussions – **30 minutes**. Depending on the number of the small groups, allocate a time slot for each group presentation (e.g., if there are 4 small groups, each group have 10 minutes for a presentation). Rapporteurs present the results of their group discussions.
6. **Step 3:** group discussion – **30 minutes**. The trainer moderates a reflective group discussion. The trainer writes the ideas suggested during the discussion on the whiteboard and summarises them. Sample questions for reflective discussion are, e.g.:
 - *What is your personal experience with conflicts of interest in research?*
 - *What types of conflicts of interests should be disclosed? Is there a consensus on that in your field of science?*
 - *Do potential conflicts of interest in citizen science differ from potential conflicts of interest in science in general? If yes, what is the difference?*
 - *How to deal with conflicts of interest in cases where they are discovered after the publication of a research study?*

PLANNING

Resources and equipment:

- Handout “HL_U5A5.1 Handout” and/or video of case animation
- Paper for taking notes during small group discussions
- Whiteboard for discussion notes
- Make space for the trainees to work in small groups

FURTHER READINGS

1. COPE Council (2021). COPE Flowcharts and infographics: Undisclosed conflict of interest in a published article. <https://doi.org/10.24318/cope.2019.2.7>
2. Macey, G. P., Breech, R., Chernaik, M., Cox, C., Larson, D., Thomas, D., & Carpenter, D. O. (2014). Air concentrations of volatile compounds near oil and gas production: a community-based exploratory study. *Environmental Health*, 13(1), 1-18. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1476-069X-13-82>
3. Resnik, D. B., Konecny, B., & Kissling, G. E. (2017). Conflict of interest and funding disclosure policies of environmental, occupational, and public health journals. *Journal of occupational and environmental medicine*, 59(1), 28. <https://doi.org/10.1097/JOM.0000000000000910>
4. The Embassy of Good Science: [“Conflict of interests”](#), [“Intellectual conflicts of interest”](#)

Unit 6. Responsible sharing and reuse of open data

Activity 6. Concerns to share and reuse data

DESCRIPTION

This activity starts with brainstorming where trainees are asked to share their views on sharing and reusing research data. It is followed by group discussion on concerns to share and reuse data, as well as possible solutions. **Type of activity:** brainstorming and group discussion

Time: 90 min.

Target group: early career researchers, senior researchers **Learning outcomes:**

	Learning outcomes <i>It is expected that trainees will:</i>	Indicators for their achievement <i>Trainees who have fully met the learning outcome</i>
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> be aware about factors influencing willingness to share and use of research data 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> discuss how to increase willingness

PROCEDURE

- Step 1: brainstorming – 15 minutes.** The trainer starts brainstorming by posing two questions: (1) “Are you ready to share your research data in an open data repository? Why yes or no?” and (2) “Are you ready to use open access data in your research? Why yes or no?” and invite trainees to take a minute’s silence to think about it. Once the minute is up, invite everyone to share their views. Have a single person (trainer or one of trainees) who takes notes on a whiteboard. The main aim of brainstorming is just to listen to different views without criticism.
- Ask trainees to split into small groups (4-6 trainees in a group) and to choose a rapporteur - a group member who will report results of the small group discussion to the whole group.
- Distribute the handout (file “HL_U6A6_1 Handout”) to each group. Half of the groups receive Task 1 from the handout (“Sharing your own research data”), other groups get Task 2 from the handout (“Using open data created by other researchers”).
- Step 2: small group discussions – 30 minutes.** Trainees discuss and fill in a table with concerns and possible solutions. Rapporteurs prepare to present the results to the whole group.
- Step 3: reports from small group discussions – 30 minutes.** Depending on the number of the small groups, allocate a time slot for each group presentation (e.g., if there are 3 small groups, each group have 10 minutes for a presentation). Rapporteurs present the results of their group discussions.
- Step 3: group discussion – 15 minutes.** The trainer moderates a reflective group discussion. Sample questions for reflective discussion are, e.g.:
 - What are the most important concerns discouraging researchers to share their data for reuse and to use open data created by other researchers? What are possible solutions?
 - How to responsibly share and reuse data in health and life sciences?

PLANNING

Resources and equipment:

- Whiteboard for discussion notes
- Make space for the trainees to work in small groups

FURTHER READINGS

1. Data sharing and the future of science. *Nature Communications* 9, 2817 (2018). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-018-05227-z>
2. Gewin, V. (2016). Data sharing: An open mind on open data. *Nature*, 529(7584), 117-119. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nj7584-117a>
3. Staunton, C., Barragán, C. A., Canali, S., Ho, C., Leonelli, S., Mayernik, M., ... & Wonkham, A. (2021). Open science, data sharing and solidarity: who benefits? *History and Philosophy of the Life Sciences*, 43(4), 115. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40656-021-00468-6>
4. Zuiderwijk, A., Shinde, R., & Jeng, W. (2020). What drives and inhibits researchers to share and use open research data? A systematic literature review to analyze factors influencing open research data adoption. *PloS one*, 15(9), e0239283. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0239283>

Activity 6.1. Case discussion on concerns about sharing the data

DESCRIPTION

This activity is built around case discussion. Trainees are asked to discuss in small groups cases on scientists’ concerns to share the data. Afterwards, small groups report to the whole group and continue with a reflective discussion involving the whole group.

Type of activity: case discussion

Time: 90 minutes

Target group: students, early career researchers, senior researchers **Learning outcomes:**

Learning outcomes <i>It is expected that trainees will:</i>	Indicators for their achievement <i>Trainees who have fully met the learning outcome are able to:</i>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - aware about factors influencing to share and use open research data 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - discuss how to increase willingness to share and use open research data

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - apply critical thinking skills - questioning, comparing, summarizing, drawing conclusions and defending - to case studies and integrity in OS 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - develop reflective questions to define ethical problems in the case study - discuss cases with colleagues - justify a personal position on the case
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PROCEDURE

1. Depending on the size of the group and background of the trainees choose how many cases to discuss during the workshop. There are four cases included in the file "HL_U6A6.1 Handout". You can also choose to watch two of the cases in the classroom - **animations of cases are available on the [ROSIE webpage](#).**
2. Introduce the activity, its aim and, briefly, the procedure.
3. Ask trainees to split in small groups (4-5 trainees in a group) and to choose a rapporteur - a group member who will report results of the small group discussion to the whole group. Provide each group with a paper for taking notes.
4. Print out case description(s) and questions for discussion for each trainee (file "HL_U6A6.1 Handout").
5. **Step 1:** small group discussions – **30 minutes**. Trainees read the case description and discuss the questions in small groups. Each group takes notes. Rapporteurs prepare to present the results to the whole group.
6. **Step 2:** reports from small group discussions – **40 minutes**. Depending on the number of the small groups, allocate a time slot for each group presentation (e.g., if there are 4 small groups, each group have 10 minutes for a presentation). Rapporteurs present the results of their group discussions.
7. **Step 3:** group discussion – **20 minutes**. The trainer moderates a reflective group discussion. The trainer writes the ideas suggested during the discussion on the whiteboard and summarises them. Sample questions for reflective discussion are, e.g.:
 - *What are the most important concerns discouraging researchers to share their data for reuse and to use open data created by other researchers? What are possible solutions?*
 - *What could be done to encourage scientists to share research data?*
 - *Are there any legitimate reasons not to share research data?*
 - *How to responsibly share and reuse data in health and life sciences?*

PLANNING

Resources and equipment:

- Handout "HL_U6A6.1 Handout" and/or animations of cases available on ROSIE webpage

– Paper for taking notes during small group discussions

- Whiteboard for discussion notes
- Make space for the trainees to work in small groups

FURTHER READINGS

1. Availability of Data. Nature portfolio. <https://www.nature.com/natureportfolio/editorial-policies/reporting-standards#availability-of-data>
2. Data sharing and the future of science. *Nat Commun* 9, 2817 (2018). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-018-05227-z>
3. Gewin, V. (2016.) Data sharing: An open mind on open data. *Nature* 529. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nj7584-117a>
4. Laine, H. (2017). Afraid of scooping: Case study on researcher strategies against fear of scooping in the context of open science. *Data Science Journal*. <https://doi.org/10.5334/dsj-2017-029>
5. Staunton, C., Barragán, C. A., Canali, S., Ho, C., Leonelli, S., Mayernik, M., ... & Wonkham, A. (2021). Open science, data sharing and solidarity: who benefits? *History and Philosophy of the Life Sciences*, 43(4), 115. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40656-021-00468-6>
6. Zuiderwijk, A., Shinde, R., & Jeng, W. (2020). What drives and inhibits researchers to share and use open research data? A systematic literature review to analyze factors influencing open research data adoption. *PloS one*, 15(9), e0239283. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0239283>

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Activity 6.2. Case discussion on reanalysis of data in medicine

DESCRIPTION

This activity is built around case discussion. Trainees are asked to discuss in small groups a case on reanalysis of data in medicine. Afterwards, small groups report to the whole group and continue with a reflective discussion involving the whole group.

Type of activity: case discussion

Time: 90 min.

Target group: students, early career researchers, senior researchers **Learning outcomes:**

	Learning outcomes <i>It is expected that trainees will:</i>	Indicators for their achievement <i>Trainees who have fully met the learning outcome are able to:</i>
	be aware of importance of reanalysis of data sets and research outputs in OS	– explain how to responsibly and critically assess and use open data and research outputs
	apply critical thinking skills - questioning, comparing, summarizing, drawing conclusions, and defending - to case studies on ethics and integrity in OS	– develop reflective questions to define ethical problems in the case study – discuss cases with colleagues – justify a personal position on the case

PROCEDURE

1. Introduce the activity, its aim and, briefly, the procedure.
2. Ask trainees to split in small groups (4-5 trainees in a group) and to choose a rapporteur - a group member who will report results of the small group discussion to the whole group. Provide each group with a paper for taking notes.
3. Print out case description and questions for discussion for each trainee (file "HL_U6A6.2 Handout").
4. **Step 1:** small group discussions – **30 minutes**. Trainees read the case description and discuss the questions in small groups. Each group takes notes. Rapporteurs prepare to present the results to the whole group.
5. **Step 2:** reports from small group discussions – **40 minutes**. Depending on the number of the small groups, allocate a time slot for each group presentation (e.g., if there are 4 small groups, each group has 10 minutes for a presentation).
Rapporteurs present the results of their group discussions.
6. **Step 3:** group discussion – **20 minutes**. The trainer moderates a reflective group discussion. The trainer writes the ideas suggested during the discussion on the whiteboard and summarise them. Sample questions for reflective discussion are, e.g.:
 - *What is the role of data reanalysis in health and life sciences?*

- What ethical issues are important in the process of reanalysis of open data sets?
- What are the benefits and risks of reanalysis of open data sets?

PLANNING

Resources and equipment:

- Handout “HL_U6A6.2 Handout”
- Paper for taking notes during small group discussions
- Whiteboard for discussion notes
- Make space for the trainees to work in small groups

FURTHER READINGS

1. The original study:

Keller, M. B., Ryan, N. D., Strober, M., Klein, R. G., Kutcher, S. P., Birmaher, B., ... & McCafferty, J. P. (2001). Efficacy of paroxetine in the treatment of adolescent major depression: a randomized, controlled trial. *Journal of the American Academy of Child & Adolescent Psychiatry*, 40(7), 762-772. <https://doi.org/10.1097/00004583-200107000-00010>

2. Bauchner, H., Golub, R. M., & Fontanarosa, P. B. (2016). Data sharing: an ethical and scientific imperative. *Jama*, 315(12), 1238-1240.

<https://doi.org/10.1001/jama.2016.2420>

3. Faria, M., Spoljaric, S., & Caruso, F. (2022). Reanalysis: the forgotten sibling of reproducibility and replicability. *Nature Reviews Methods Primers*, 2(1), 1-2. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s43586-022-00103-z>

4. Neutra, R. R., Cohen, A., Fletcher, T., Michaels, D., Richter, E. D., & Soskolne, C. L. (2006). Toward guidelines for the ethical reanalysis and reinterpretation of another's research. *Epidemiology*, 17(3), 335-338.

<https://doi.org/10.1097/01.ede.0000209464.97895.bf>

Unit 7. Prevention of research malpractice in the context of OS

Activity 7. Violations of research integrity in OS and their prevention

The activity aims to discuss different types of violations of research integrity in OS and their prevention. The trainees are split into five groups and their task is to reflect on potential violations and preventive measures in each particular type of Open Science activity. Each group shares the results of their discussions, and group work is followed by a plenary activity where all trainees have an opportunity to supplement the results of group work.

Type of activity: group work and plenary activity

Target group: students, early career researchers, senior researchers **Learning outcomes:**

	Learning outcomes <i>It is expected that trainees will:</i>	Indicators for their achievement <i>Trainees who have fully met the learning outcome are able to:</i>
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – know potential types of research practice in OS 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – discuss causes of violations of research integrity in OS and ways of its prevention

PROCEDURE

- Before the exercise, print out the pages with different types of Open Science activities (file “HL_U7A7 Printout”) and mark sections of a wall with the titles:
 - *Open access publishing*
 - *Sharing and using open data*
 - *Open reproducible research, e.g., open lab notes, reproducing of research studies*
 - *Open science evaluation, e.g., open metrics and impact, open peer review – Citizen science*
- Ask participants to split into five groups. Assign one of the types of Open Science activities listed above to each group.
- Step 1:** group discussion – **25 minutes**. Each group discusses the following questions in the context of the particular type of Open Science activities:
 - *What potential violations of research integrity and ethics may arise in the context of this type of open science activities?*
 - *How to prevent these potential violations?*
 The results of the discussion should be written on paper cards/sticky notes – one potential type of violation and preventive measure on each card/sticky note and hanged on the wall under the respective type of Open Science activities.
- Step 2:** group work presentations and general discussion – **65 minutes**. Each group presents their results in 5 minutes. After each presentation there is a general discussion where every trainee has an opportunity to suggest additional challenges and preventive measures. These additional challenges and preventive measures are written on paper cards/sticky notes and added to the respective type of Open Science activities.

PLANNING

Resources and equipment:

- Printout “HL_U7A7 Printout”
- Large wall or multiple pinboards to hang on printouts and results of discussions

- Empty cards & tape/sticky notes, pens/markers
- Make space for the trainees to work in small groups and to move around

FURTHER READINGS

1. Düwell, M. (2019). Open science and ethics. *Ethical Theory and Moral Practice*, 22, 1051-1053. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10677-019-10053-3>

Activity 7.1. Should scientists use access to pirated papers?

DESCRIPTION

This activity is built around case discussion. Trainees are asked to discuss in small groups a case on violations of intellectual property rights by providing access to pirated scientific publications. Afterwards, small groups report to the whole group and continue with a reflective discussion involving the whole group.

Type of activity: case discussion

Time: 90 minutes

Target group: students, early career researchers, senior researchers **Learning outcomes:**

	Learning outcomes <i>It is expected that trainees will:</i>	Indicators for their achievement <i>Trainees who have fully met the learning outcome are able to:</i>
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - know potential types of research practices in OS 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - discuss causes of violations of research integrity in OS and ways of its prevention - recognise limits of OS for protection of data and intellectual property rights

PROCEDURE

1. Print out the case description and questions for discussion for each trainee (file "HL_U7A7.1 Handout". You can also choose to watch the case in the classroom - **animation of this case is available on the ROSIE webpage.**
2. Introduce the activity, its aim and, briefly, the procedure.
3. Ask trainees to split in small groups (4-5 trainees in a group) and to choose a rapporteur - a group member who will report results of the small group discussion to the whole group. Provide each group with a paper for taking notes.
4. **Step 1:** small group discussions – **30 minutes.** Trainees read the case description and discuss the questions in small groups. Each group takes notes. Rapporteurs prepare to present the results to the whole group.

5. **Step 2:** reports from small group discussions – **30 minutes**. Depending on the number of the small groups, allocate a time slot for each group presentation (e.g., if there are 4 small groups, each group have 10 minutes for a presentation). Rapporteurs present the results of their group discussions.
6. **Step 3:** group discussion – **30 minutes**. The trainer moderates a reflective group discussion. The trainer writes the ideas suggested during the discussion on the whiteboard and summarises them. Sample questions for reflective discussion are, e.g.:
 - *How important are intellectual property rights for scientific research and achievements?*
 - *Does the case address a relevant issue for you and researchers you are working together?*
 - *What are potential solutions at the policy level to the problem described in the case?*

PLANNING

Resources and equipment:

- Handout “HL_U7A7.1 Handout” and/or video of case animation
- Paper for taking notes during small group discussions
- Whiteboard for discussion notes
- Make space for the trainees to work in small groups

FURTHER READINGS

1. Monbiot, G. Scientific publishing is a rip-off. We fund the research - it should be free. *The Guardian*. 13.09. 2018. <https://www.theguardian.com/commentisfree/2018/sep/13/scientific-publishingrip-off-taxpayers-fund-research>
2. Van Noorden, R. (2016). Alexandra Elbakyan: Paper pirate. *Nature*, 540, 512. <https://www.nature.com/articles/540507a>
3. Vogel, G., & Kupferschmidt, K. (2017). A bold open-access push in Germany could change the future of academic publishing. *Science*, 23. <https://www.science.org/content/article/bold-open-access-push-germany-couldchange-future-academic-publishing>

Unit 8. Responsible dissemination and publication practices

Activity 8. Open access publishing and predatory practices

DESCRIPTION

This activity applies the Four Quadrant Method for case analysis on predatory practices.

Trainees are asked to discuss a case in small groups and fill in the four quadrant template. Afterwards, small groups report to the whole group and continue with a casuistic reasoning and justification discussion involving the whole group.

Type of activity: case discussion (Four Quadrant Method)

Time: 90 min.

Target group: students, early career researchers **Learning outcomes:**

	Learning outcomes <i>It is expected that trainees will:</i>	Indicators for their achievement <i>Trainees who have fully met the learning outcome are able to:</i>
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> know criteria for good practice standards in open access publishing 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> critically assess scientific results published in open access and identify predatory publishing practices
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> apply critical thinking skills - questioning, comparing, summarizing, drawing conclusions and defending - to case studies and integrity in OS 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> develop reflective questions to define ethical problems in the case study discuss cases with colleagues justify a personal position on the case

PROCEDURE

1. Introduce the activity, its aim and, briefly, the procedure of the Four Quadrant Method⁴.
2. Print out the case description (file “HL_U8A8 Handout”) for each trainee.

⁴ Detailed description of the modified Four Quadrant Method for case analysis is provided by the EnTIRE project: Armond A.C. et al. (2019). [D.5.3 Delivery of the entire set of case deliberation methods and case analyses as input for the platform](#), pp: 98-102.

3. Ask trainees to split in small groups (3-4 trainees in a group) and to choose a rapporteur - a group member who will report results of the small group discussion to the whole group.
4. **Step 1.** Initial perception – **20 minutes**. Trainees read the case and in small groups discuss some general questions to identify relevant aspects of the case:
 - *What are the ethical issues at stake in this case?*
 - *Who are the stakeholders?*
 - *How should stakeholders react to this case?*
 - *What should/can stakeholders do to prevent such cases?*

5. **Step 2.** The Four Quadrant Analysis – **20 minutes.** Each group fills in the four quadrant table included in the file

“HL_U8A8 Handout”.

<p>I. Relevant Facts: What are the most relevant facts concerning the situation?</p>	<p>II. Uncertainties: Which features of the situation are uncertain, lacking in clarity, or controversial?</p>
<p>III. Courses of Action: What are the practically available options for providing a solution to the case (how to react to the case and how to prevent such cases in the future)?</p>	<p>IV. Contextual Features: What legal, financial and institutional policies and regulations apply to the case?</p>

1. **Step 3.** Reports from small groups – **20 minutes.** The small groups report the results of the Four Quadrant Analysis to the whole group.
2. **Step 4.** Casuistic reasoning and justification – **30 minutes.** The trainer moderates the whole group discussion on the following questions:
 - *What is at issue? What is the major ethical issue at the case?*
 - *Do you know other cases like this one?*
 - *Why do academics publish their research in a predatory journal or books published by predatory publishers? What are the main factors that motivate such a practice? What are negative consequences of such a practice? What policies might minimise predatory publishing practices?*
 - *How should stakeholders react to cases like this?*

PLANNING

Resources and equipment:

- Handout “HL_U8A8 Handout”
- Make space for the trainees to work in small groups

FURTHER READINGS

1. Bartholomew, R. E. (2014). Science for sale: The rise of predatory journals. *Journal of the Royal Society of Medicine*, 107(10), 384–385. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0141076814548526>
2. Beall, J. (2015). Criteria for determining predatory open access publishers. <https://beallist.net/wp-content/uploads/2019/12/criteria-2015.pdf>
3. Kurt, S. (2018). Why do authors publish in predatory journals? *Learned Publishing*, 31(2), 141-147. <https://doi.org/10.1002/leap.1150>
4. The Embassy of Good Science: “[Predatory publishing](#)”

Activity 8.1. Open peer review

DESCRIPTION

This activity is built around case discussion. Trainees are asked to discuss in small groups a case on open peer review. Afterwards, small groups report to the whole group and continue with a reflective discussion involving the whole group.

Type of activity: case discussion

Time: 90 min.

Target group: early career researchers, senior researchers **Learning outcomes:**

	Learning outcomes <i>It is expected that trainees will:</i>	Indicators for their achievement <i>Trainees who have fully met the learning outcome are able to:</i>
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – aware of importance of open peer review practices 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – explain how to responsibly and critically perform open peer review
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – apply critical thinking skills - questioning, comparing, summarizing, drawing conclusions, and defending - to case studies on hiccups and integrity in OS 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – develop reflective questions to define ethical problems in the case study – discuss cases with colleagues – justify a personal position on the case

PROCEDURE

1. Introduce the activity, its aim and, briefly, the procedure.
2. Ask trainees to split in small groups (4-5 trainees in a group) and to choose a rapporteur - a group member who will report results of the small group discussion to the whole group. Provide each group with a paper for taking notes.
3. Print out case description and questions for discussion for each trainee (file "HL_U8A8.1 Handout").
4. **Step 1:** small group discussions – **30 minutes**. Trainees read the case description and discuss the questions in small groups. Each group takes notes. Rapporteurs prepare to present the results to the whole group.
5. **Step 2:** reports from small group discussions – **40 minutes**. Depending on the number of the small groups, allocate a time slot for each group presentation (e.g., if there are 4 small groups,

each group has 10 minutes for a presentation). Rapporteurs present the results of their group discussions.

6. **Step 3: group discussion – 20 minutes.** The trainer moderates a reflective group discussion. The trainer writes the ideas suggested during the discussion on the whiteboard and summarise them. Sample questions for reflective discussion are, e.g.:
 - *What is the role of open peer review in the scientific publishing process?*
 - *What are the benefits and risks of open peer review?*

PLANNING

Resources and equipment:

- Handout “HL_U8A8.1 Handout”
- Paper for taking notes during small group discussions
- Whiteboard for discussion notes
- Make space for the trainees to work in small groups

FURTHER READINGS

1. Harms, P. D., & Credé, M. (2020). Bringing the review process into the 21st century: Post-publication peer review. *Industrial and Organizational Psychology*, 13(1), 51-53. <https://doi.org/10.1017/iop.2020.13>
2. Ross-Hellauer, T., Deppe, A., & Schmidt, B. (2017). Survey on open peer review: Attitudes and experience amongst editors, authors and reviewers. *PloS One*, 12(12), e0189311. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0189311>
3. Tenorio-Fornés, Á., Tirador, E. P., Sánchez-Ruiz, A. A., & Hassan, S. (2021). Decentralizing science: Towards an interoperable open peer review ecosystem using blockchain. *Information Processing & Management*, 58(6), 102724. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ipm.2021.102724>
4. The Embassy of Good Science: “[Post-publication peer review](#)”
5. The Embassy of Good Science: “[Open peer review - transparent way of gatekeeping science](#)”

Activity 8.2. Publishing of preprints

DESCRIPTION

This activity is built around case discussion. Trainees are asked to discuss in small groups a case on publishing preprints. Afterwards, small groups report to the whole group and continue with a reflective discussion involving the whole group.

Type of activity: case discussion

Time: 90 min.

Target group: early career researchers, senior researchers
Learning outcomes:

	Learning outcomes <i>It is expected that trainees will:</i>	Indicators for their achievement <i>Trainees who have fully met the learning outcome are able to:</i>
	- be aware of importance of preprints in open publication process	- explain how to responsibly and critically publish and use preprints
	- apply critical thinking skills - questioning, comparing, summarizing, drawing conclusions, and defending - to case studies on hiccups and integrity in OS	- develop reflective questions to define ethical problems in the case study - discuss cases with colleagues - justify a personal position on the case

PROCEDURE

1. Introduce the activity, its aim and, briefly, the procedure.
2. Ask trainees to split in small groups (4-5 trainees in a group) and to choose a rapporteur - a group member who will report results of the small group discussion to the whole group. Provide each group with a paper for taking notes.
3. Print out case description and questions for discussion for each trainee (file "HL_U8A8.2 Handout").
4. **Step 1:** small group discussions – **30 minutes**. Trainees read the case description and discuss the questions in small groups. Each group takes notes. Rapporteurs prepare to present the results to the whole group.
5. **Step 2:** reports from small group discussions – **40 minutes**. Depending on the number of the small groups, allocate a time slot for each group presentation (e.g., if there are 4 small groups, each group has 10 minutes for a presentation). Rapporteurs present the results of their group discussions.
6. **Step 3:** group discussion – **20 minutes**. The trainer moderates a reflective group discussion. The trainer writes the ideas suggested during the discussion on the whiteboard and summarise them. Sample questions for reflective discussion are, e.g.:
 - *What is the role of open peer review in the scientific publishing process?*
 - *What are the benefits and risks of open peer review?*

PLANNING

Resources and equipment:

- Handout "HL_U8A8.2 Handout"
- Paper for taking notes during small group discussions

- Make space for the trainees to work in small groups

FURTHER READINGS

1. COPE Council (2018). COPE Discussion Document: Preprints. <https://doi.org/10.24318/R4WByao2>
2. Elmore, S. A. (2018). Preprints: what role do these have in communicating scientific results? *Toxicologic pathology*, 46(4), 364-365. <https://doi.org/10.1177%2F0192623318767322>
3. Ravinetto, R. et al. (2021). Preprints in times of COVID19: the time is ripe for agreeing on terminology and good practices. *BMC Medical Ethics*, 22(1), 1-5. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12910-021-00667-7>
4. Sheldon, T. (2018). Preprints could promote confusion and distortion. *Nature*, 559(7715), 445–445. <https://doi.org/10.1038/d41586-018-05789-4>

UNDER REVIEW BY THE EUROPEAN COMMISSION

ROSIE

TRAINING MATERIALS for Responsible Open Science Part V: Citizen Scientists

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UNDER REVIEW BY THE EUROPEAN COMMISSION

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Introduction

The aim of the ROSIE Training Materials for Responsible Open Science is to learn how to practice Open Science (OS) responsibly and how to prevent research misconduct in the context of OS by providing necessary knowledge and developing specific skills and attitudes.

In the ROSIE Didactic Framework we have identified the following skills and attitudes necessary for responsible practising of OS in four domains: (i) local and global citizenship, (ii) personal and social responsibility, (iii) epistemic skills, and (iv) collaborative problem-solving.

Local and global citizenship

- awareness of the importance and social benefits of OS and citizen science in local and global contexts
- participation in ethics and integrity self-regulation of OS and citizen science community

Personal and social responsibility

- personal and professional responsibility for implementation of OS and production of results
- openness to share own research data, results, tools and publications and appreciation of efforts of others

Epistemic skills

- ability to organize, present and use open data and knowledge with integrity
- ability to critically assess data, knowledge and scientific results produced by others
- ability to identify ethical and integrity issues in OS

Collaborative problem-solving

- ability to apply critical thinking skills in collaborative analysis of ethical and integrity problems in OS
- discussing, finding solutions and making decisions to handle ethics and integrity issues within OS community

To achieve optimal results, the ROSiE training materials rely on several learning and teaching strategies: (i) collaborative problem solving; (ii) case-based activities; (iii) dialogical activities; (iv) transformative learning. More information about these teaching strategies you can find in the ROSiE Didactic Framework.

The training material consists of a trainers' file including 6 units and respective activities, as well as a separate folder including materials for trainees – required readings, handouts and printouts. The activities can be implemented separately (e.g., for organising a single workshop to discuss cases) or for organising a complete two-days training course. The suggested schedule for the training course is as follows:

Time	DAY 1	Type of activity
90 min.	Unit 1. Ethical and societal foundations of citizen science, its purpose	Socratic seminar

15 min.	Break	
90 min.	Unit 2. Protection of research participants	Case discussion
15 min.	Break	
90 min.	Unit 3. Rights of citizen scientists	Case discussion (Pro and Contra)
Time	DAY 2	Type of activity
90 min.	Unit 4. The quality of the research outputs and data sets	Case discussion
15 min.	Break	
90 min.	Unit 5. Conflicts of interest in citizen science	Case discussion (Four Quadrant method)
15 min.	Break	
90min.	Unit 6. Risks to environment, animals, plants, and ecosystems	Case discussion

Unit 1. Ethical and societal foundations of citizen science, its purpose

Activity 1. Responsible citizen science

DESCRIPTION

This activity based on home readings a classroom discussion in a form of Socratic seminar on principles and values of citizen science. The discussion is based on European Citizen Science Association (ECSA) 10 principles of citizen science. The main purpose of the activity is to address the issues of nature and ethical foundations of citizen science. **Type of activity:** Socratic seminar **Time:** 90 min.

Target group: citizen scientists **Learning outcomes:**

<p>Learning outcomes <i>It is expected that trainees will:</i></p>	<p>Indicators for their achievement <i>Trainees who have fully met the learning outcome are able to:</i></p>
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	-demonstrate knowledge of nat and ethical foundations of OS and citizen science	ure nd	- explain and discuss principles and values
	-understand the significance of and citizen science for identifying and solving scientific problems societal challenges	OS rg and	- provide examples for role of OS and citizen science challenges

PROCEDURE

1. Before the workshop print out the required readings (European Citizen Science Association 10 Principles of Citizen Science, file “CS_U1A1 Reading_ECSA_Ten_Principles_of_CS”) and the handout (file “HL_U1A1 Handout”) for each trainee.
2. **Step 1 – 20 minutes.** At the beginning of the workshop trainees should read the required readings and fill in the double-entry reading journal table in the handout. The left side should contain quotations from the European Citizen Science Association 10 Principles of Citizen Science. The right side should contain trainee’s response to each quotation (a question, commentary, analysis). When filling in the table, trainees may use the following prompts, included in the handout:
 - I agree/disagree with..., because...
 - It is not clear for me...
 - I see the following challenges...
 - I have a question regarding...
3. **Step 2 – 60 minutes.** The classroom discussion is organized as a Socratic seminar. The aim of the Socratic seminar is to achieve “a deeper understanding about the ideas and values in a particular text”⁶. The trainer is facilitator of the discussion, the discussion is led by using open-ended, high-level questions. Trainees are sitting in a circle.
4. The Socratic Seminar starts with introduction of the rules:
 - Only those trainees who have read the text and filled in the double-entry reading journal are allowed to participate;
 - It is important to focus on the text and to refer to evidence from the text;
 - Trainees are encouraged to talk to each other, not just to the trainer and to listen and respond to others’ arguments.

⁶ Castellanos-Reyes, D. (2020). Socratic Seminar. In R. Kimmons & S. Caskurlu (Eds.), *The Students' Guide to Learning Design and Research*. EdTech Books.

https://edtechbooks.org/studentguide/socratic_seminar

5. Common questions used during a Socratic Seminar activity both by trainer and trainees include:
 - *What does this concept/idea/phrase etc. mean?*
 - *What do you think the authors are trying to say?*
 - *Is this what you mean to say...? –*
What is the origin of this?
 - *What are the implications this?*
 - *What else could that mean? –*
What would happen if....?
6. This [overview of Socratic seminar](#) provides a list of suitable questions and more information about how to prepare for a discussion.
7. **Step 2 – 10 minutes.** At the end of Socratic seminar the trainer leads a reflection on the main ideas discussed.

PLANNING

Resources and equipment:

- Handout “CS_U1A1 Handout”
- Required readings “CS_U1A1 Reading_ECSA_Ten_Principles_of_CS ”
- Make space for the trainees to sit in a circle

FURTHER READINGS

1. Haklay, M. (Muki), Dörler, D., Heigl, F., Manzoni, M., Hecker, S., & Vohland, K. (2021). What Is Citizen Science? The Challenges of Definition. In: K. Vohland, A. Land-Zandstra, L. Ceccaroni, R. Lemmens, J. Perelló, M. Ponti, R. Samson, & K. Wagenknecht (Eds.), *The Science of Citizen Science* (pp. 13–33). Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-58278-4_2
2. Haklay, M., Fraisl, D., Greshake Tzovaras, B., Hecker, S., Gold, M., Hager, G., ... & Vohland, K. (2021). Contours of citizen science: a vignette study. *Royal Society open science*, 8(8), 202108. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rsos.202108>
3. Vohland, K., Land-Zandstra, A., Ceccaroni, L., Lemmens, R., Perelló, J., Ponti, M., Samson, R., & Wagenknecht, K. (2021). Editorial: The Science of Citizen Science Evolves. In: K. Vohland, A. Land-Zandstra, L. Ceccaroni, R. Lemmens, J. Perelló, M. Ponti, R. Samson, & K. Wagenknecht (Eds.), *The Science of Citizen Science* (pp. 1–12). Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-58278-4_1

UNDER REVIEW BY THE EUROPEAN COMMISSION

Unit

2. Protection of research participants

Activity 2. Collecting personal data in citizen science

DESCRIPTION

This activity is built around case discussion. Trainees are asked to discuss in small groups cases on ethical issues in gathering and open sharing of personal data in citizen science by using examples from social sciences and natural sciences. Afterwards, small groups report to the whole group and continue with a reflective discussion involving the whole group.

Type of activity: case discussion **Time:** 90

min.

Target group: citizen scientists **Learning outcomes:**

	Learning outcomes <i>It is expected that trainees will:</i>	Indicators for their achievement <i>Trainees who have fully met the learning outcome are able to:</i>
	recognize and analyse the risk to research participants in the context of citizen science	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - discuss how to minimize risks to research participants when practicing citizen science
	apply critical thinking skills - questioning, comparing, summarizing, drawing conclusions and defending - to case studies ethics and integrity in OS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - develop reflective questions to define ethical problems in the case study - discuss cases with colleagues - justify a personal position on the case

PROCEDURE

1. The activity includes a case discussion. Two case descriptions are included in the file "SC_U2A2 Handout". You can also choose to watch one of the cases in the classroom - **animation of this case is available on the [ROSIE webpage](#).**
2. Print out the case description and questions for discussion for each trainee (file "SC_U2A2 Handout").
3. Introduce the activity, its aim and, briefly, the procedure.
4. Ask trainees to split in small groups (4-5 trainees in a group) and to choose a rapporteur - a group member who will report results of the small group discussion to the whole group. Provide each group with a paper for taking notes.

5. **Step 1:** small group discussions – **30 minutes**. Trainees read the case description and discuss the questions in small groups. Each group takes notes. Rapporteurs prepare to present the results to the whole group.
6. **Step 2:** reports from small group discussions – **40 minutes**. Depending on the number of the small groups, allocate a time slot for each group presentation (e.g., if there are 4 small groups, each group have 10 minutes for a presentation).
Rapporteurs present the results of their group discussions.
7. **Step 3:** group discussion – **20 minutes**. The trainer moderates a reflective group discussion. The trainer writes the solutions suggested during the discussion on the whiteboard and summarises them. Sample questions for reflective discussion are, e.g.:
 - *What citizen scientists can do to protect privacy of research participants and/or persons affected by the research?*

PLANNING

Resources and equipment:

- Handout “CS_U2A2 Handout” and/or video of case animation
- Paper for taking notes during small group discussions
- Whiteboard for discussion notes
- Make space for the trainees to work in small groups

FURTHER READINGS

1. Campbell, R., Goodman-Williams, R., & Javorka, M. (2019). A trauma-informed approach to sexual violence research ethics and open science. *Journal of interpersonal violence*, 34(23-24), 4765-4793. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0886260519871530>
2. DuBois, J. M., Strait, M., & Walsh, H. (2018). Is it time to share qualitative research data? *Qualitative Psychology*, 5(3), 380–393. <https://doi.org/10.1037/qup0000076>
3. Fox, J., Pearce, K. E., Massanari, A. L., Riles, J. M., Szulc, Ł., Ranjit, Y. S., ... & L. Gonzales, A. (2021). Open science, closed doors? Countering marginalization through an agenda for ethical, inclusive research in communication. *Journal of Communication*, 71(5), 764-784. <https://doi.org/10.1093/joc/jgab029>
4. Scheibner, J., Jobin, A., & Vayena, E. (2021). Ethical issues with using Internet of Things devices in citizen science research: a scoping review. *Frontiers in Environmental Science*, 9, 629649. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fenvs.2021.629649>
5. The Embassy of Good Science: “[Privacy in research](#)”

3. Rights of citizen scientists

Unit

Activity 3. Authorship, contributorship and group coauthorship in citizen science

DESCRIPTION

This activity is built around case discussion and involves evaluating pro and contra arguments for different types of acknowledging citizen scientist contributions to research. Trainees are asked to discuss two cases in small groups, develop and discuss their arguments. Afterwards, small groups report to the whole group and continue with a reflective discussion involving the whole group.

Type of activity: case discussion

Time: 90 min.

Learning outcomes:

	Learning outcomes <i>It is expected that trainees will:</i>	Indicators for their achievement <i>Trainees who have fully met the learning outcome are</i>
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> be aware of citizen scientists' right to be recognised and acknowledged by academic scientists and society 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> discuss and assert their right to be recognised and acknowledged by academic scientists and society
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> apply critical thinking skills - questioning, comparing, summarizing, drawing conclusions, defending - to case studies and integrity in OS 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> develop reflective questions to discuss cases with colleagues justify a personal position on the cases

PROCEDURE

1. Introduce the activity, its aim and, briefly, the procedure.
2. Ask trainees to split in small groups (3-4 trainees in a group) and to choose a rapporteur - a group member who will report results of the small group discussion to the whole group.
1. Print out case descriptions and the table to fill in pro and counter arguments (file "CS_U3A3 Handout"). You can also choose to watch one of the cases in the classroom - **animation of this case is available on the [ROSIE webpage](#).**
3. **Step 1:** small group discussions – **30 minutes**. Trainees read the case description and discuss the task in small groups. Each group fills in the table included in the handout with pro and contra arguments. Rapporteurs prepare to present the results to the whole group.
4. **Step 2:** short reports from small group discussions – **20 minutes**. Rapporteurs present the results of their group discussions - pro and contra arguments for each type of acknowledging the contribution of citizen scientists in this case.

5. **Step 3:** group discussion – **40 minutes**. The trainer moderates a reflective group discussion. Sample questions for reflective discussion are, e.g.:
 - *Based on the pro and contra arguments developed during the group work, what is the best solution for this case?*
 - *Do you have other suggestions for recognizing the contribution of citizen scientists in scientific publications*

PLANNING

Resources and equipment:

- Handout “CS_U3A3 Handout” and/or video of case animation
- Make space for the trainees to work in small groups

FURTHER READINGS

1. COPE Council (2003). How to Handle Authorship Disputes: A Guide for New Researchers. <https://doi.org/10.24318/cope.2018.1.1>
2. ICMJE. Defining the role of authors and contributors. <https://bit.ly/N7uoq3>
3. Smith, E., Bélisle-Pipon, J. C., & Resnik, D. (2019). Patients as research partners; how to value their perceptions, contribution and labor? *Citizen science: theory and practice*, 4(1). <https://doi.org/10.5334/cstp.184>
4. The Embassy of Good Science: “[Authorship criteria](#)”
5. Vasilevsky, N. A. et al. (2021). Is authorship sufficient for today’s collaborative research? A call for contributor roles. *Accountability in Research*, 28(1), 23-43. <https://doi.org/10.1080/08989621.2020.1779591>
6. Ward-Fear, G., Pauly, G. B., Vendetti, J. E., & Shine, R. (2020). Authorship Protocols Must Change to Credit Citizen Scientists. *Trends in Ecology & Evolution*, 35(3), 187–190. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tree.2019.10.007>

4. The quality of the research outputs and data sets

Activity 4. Responsibility of citizen scientists for quality of data

DESCRIPTION

This activity is built around case discussion. Trainees are asked to discuss in small groups a case on data quality in citizen science. Afterwards, small groups report to the whole group and continue with a reflective discussion involving the whole group.

Unit

Type of activity: case discussion **Time:** 90

min.

Target group: citizen scientists **Learning outcomes:**

	Learning outcomes <i>It is expected that trainees</i>	Indicators for their achievement <i>will: Trainees who have fully met the learning outcome are</i>
	- be aware of responsibilities of citizen scientists for data quality and integrity	- explain how biased, fabricated, falsified data can be identified
	- demonstrate knowledge of the importance of open data and how to ensure its quality	- collect data responsibly and keep it open

PROCEDURE

1. Print out the case description and questions for discussion for each trainee (file "CS_U4A4 Handout").
2. Introduce the activity, its aim and, briefly, the procedure.
3. Ask trainees to split in small groups (4-5 trainees in a group) and to choose a rapporteur - a group member who will report results of the small group discussion to the whole group. Provide each group with a paper for taking notes.
4. **Step 1:** small group discussions – 30 minutes. Trainees read the case description and discuss the questions in small groups. Each group takes notes. Rapporteurs prepare to present the results to the whole group.
5. **Step 2:** reports from small group discussions – 30 minutes. Depending on the number of the small groups, allocate a time slot for each group presentation (e.g., if there are 4 small groups, each group have 10 minutes for a presentation). Rapporteurs present the results of their group discussions.
1. **Step 3:** group discussion – 30 minutes. The trainer moderates a reflective group discussion. The trainer writes the solutions suggested during the discussion on the whiteboard and summarises them. Sample questions for reflective discussion are, e.g.:
 - Which ideas proposed during the discussion so far seem to you the best? Why?
 - How the case reflects the problems faced in citizen science practice?

PLANNING

Resources and equipment:

- Handout “CS_U4A4 Handout”
- Paper for taking notes during small group discussions
- Whiteboard for discussion notes
- Make space for the trainees to work in small groups

FURTHER READINGS

1. Balázs, B., Mooney, P., Nováková, E., Bastin, L., Jokar Arsanjani, J. (2021). Data Quality in Citizen Science. In: *The Science of Citizen Science*. Springer
https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-58278-4_8
2. Herodotou, C., Scanlon, E., & Sharples, M. (2021). Methods of promoting learning and data quality in citizen and Community Science. *Frontiers in Climate*, 53.
<https://doi.org/10.3389/fclim.2021.614567>
3. Haklay, M. (2021). Why is it so difficult to integrate citizen science into practice? *Citizen Science and Public Policy Making*, 108.
<https://discovery.ucl.ac.uk/id/eprint/10130136>.

5. Conflicts of interest in citizen science

Activity 5. How to recognize conflicts of interest in citizen science?

DESCRIPTION

This activity applies the Four Quadrant Method for case analysis on conflict of interests in citizen science. Trainees are asked to discuss a case in small groups and fill in the four quadrant template. Afterwards, small groups report to the whole group and continue with a casuistic reasoning and justification discussion involving the whole group.

Type of activity: case discussion (Four Quadrant method)

Time: 90 min.

Unit

Target group: citizen scientists **Learning**

outcomes:

	Learning outcomes <i>It is expected that trainees</i>	<i>will:</i>	Indicators for their achievement <i>Trainees who have fully met the learning outcome are</i>
	– understand the concept of interest and how to deal with it	– recognize and disclose conflicts of interest	– recognize and disclose conflicts of interest
	– apply critical thinking skills questioning, comparing, summarizing, drawing conclusions and defending integrity in OS	– discuss cases with colleagues and justify a personal position	– develop a personal position

PROCEDURE

1. At least one week before the class send the trainees the link to the reading material on Conflict of Interests from The Embassy of Good Science (<https://embassy.science/wiki/Theme:6d71bd59-c3bc-4cd5-9c9f-1ab4e53fc320>).
2. Print out the case description for each trainee (file “CS_U5A5 Handout”. You can also choose to watch the case in the classroom - **animation of this case is available on the ROSIE webpage**.
3. Introduce the activity, its aim and, briefly, the procedure of the Four Quadrant Method⁷.
4. Ask trainees to split in small groups (3-4 trainees in a group) and to choose a rapporteur - a group member who will report results of the small group discussion to the whole group.
5. **Step 1. Initial perception – 20 minutes.** Trainees read the case and in small groups discuss some general questions to identify relevant aspects of the case:
 - What are the ethical issues at stake in this case?
 - Who are the stakeholders?
 - How should stakeholders react to this case?

⁷ Detailed description of the modified Four Quadrant Method for case analysis is provided by the EnTIRE project: Armond A.C. et al. (2019). [D.5.3 Delivery of the entire set of case deliberation methods and case analyses as input for the platform](https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/documents/downloadPublic?documentIds=080166e5c3a7e938&appId=PPGMS), pp. 98-102. <https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/documents/downloadPublic?documentIds=080166e5c3a7e938&appId=PPGMS>

6. **Step 2.** The Four Quadrant Analysis – **20 minutes**. Each group fills in the four quadrant table included in the file “CS_U5A5 Handout”.

<p>I. Relevant Facts: What are the most relevant facts concerning the situation?</p>	<p>II. Uncertainties: Which features of the situation are uncertain, lacking in clarity, or controversial?</p>
<p>III. Courses of Action: What are the practically available options for providing a solution to the case (how to react to the case and how to prevent such cases in the future)?</p>	<p>IV. Contextual Features: What legal, financial and institutional policies and regulations apply to the case?</p>

7. **Step 3.** Reports from small groups – **20 minutes**. The small groups report the results of the Four Quadrant Analysis to the whole group.
8. **Step 4.** Casuistic Reasoning and Justification – **30 minutes**. The trainer moderates the whole group discussion on the following questions:
- *What is at issue? What is the major ethical issue at the case?*
 - *Do you know other cases like this one?*
 - *How to recognize a conflict of interests? What types of conflicts of interests should be disclosed in citizen science?*
 - *What should stakeholders do to prevent conflicts of interests?*

PLANNING

Resources and equipment:

- Handout “SC_U5A5 Handout” and/or video of case animation
- Paper for taking notes during small group discussions
- Whiteboard for discussion notes
- Make space for the trainees to work in small groups

FURTHER READINGS

1. Macey, G. P., Breech, R., Chernaik, M., Cox, C., Larson, D., Thomas, D., & Carpenter, D. O. (2014). Air concentrations of volatile compounds near oil and gas production: a community-based exploratory study. *Environmental Health*, 13(1), 1-18.
<https://doi.org/10.1186/1476-069X-13-82>
2. Resnik, D. B., Konecny, B., & Kissling, G. E. (2017). Conflict of interest and funding disclosure policies of environmental, occupational, and public health journals. *Journal of occupational and environmental medicine*, 59(1), 28.
<https://doi.org/10.1097/JOM.0000000000000910>
3. Resnik, D. B., Elliott, K. C., & Miller, A. K. (2015). A framework for addressing ethical issues in citizen science. *Environmental Science & Policy*, 54, 475-481.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsci.2015.05.008>

Unit 6. Risks to environment, animals, plants, and ecosystems

Activity 6 Protection of animals, plants and ecosystems in citizen science

DESCRIPTION

This activity is based on a case discussion. Trainees are asked to discuss in small groups a case on risks for ecosystems created by conducting citizen science activities. Afterwards, small groups report to the whole group and continue with a reflective discussion involving the whole group.

Type of activity: case discussion **Time:** 90

min.

Target group: citizen scientists **Learning outcomes:**

	Learning outcomes <i>It is expected that trainees will:</i>	Indicators for their achievement <i>Trainees who have fully met the learning outcome are able to</i>
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> understand the risks to environment, plants, animals, and ecosystems in the context of citizen science 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> minimize risks to environment, plants and animals

PROCEDURE

1. Introduce the activity, its aim and, briefly, the procedure.
2. Ask trainees to split in small groups (4-5 trainees in a group) and to choose a rapporteur - a group member who will report results of the small group discussion to the whole group. Provide each group with a paper for taking notes.
3. Print out case description and questions for discussion for each trainee (file "CS_U6A6 Handout").
4. **Step 1:** small group discussions – **30 minutes**. Trainees read the case description and discuss the questions in small groups. Each group takes notes. Rapporteurs prepare to present the results to the whole group.
5. **Step 2:** reports from small group discussions – **30 minutes**. Depending on the number of the small groups, allocate a time slot for each group presentation (e.g., if there are 4 small groups, each group have 10 minutes for a presentation). Rapporteurs present the results of their group discussions.
6. **Step 3:** group discussion – **30 minutes**. The trainer moderates a reflective group discussion. The trainer writes the solutions suggested during the discussion on the whiteboard and summarise them. Sample questions for reflective discussion are, e.g.:
 - *How to make citizen scientists aware about possible risks to ecosystems, animals and plants?*
 - *What steps can be taken to minimize the risks?*
 - *What is your personal experience of participation in research that has a potential to cause harm to ecosystems, animals or plants?*

PLANNING

Resources and equipment:

- Handout "CS_U6A6 Handout"
- Paper for taking notes during small group discussions
- Whiteboard for discussion notes
- Make space for the trainees to work in small groups

FURTHER READINGS

1. Soroye, P., Edwards, B. P., Buxton, R. T., Ethier, J. P., Frempong-Manso, A., Keefe, H. E., ... & Bennett, J. R. (2022). The risks and rewards of community science for threatened species monitoring. *Conservation Science and Practice*, 4(9), e12788.
<https://doi.org/10.1111/csp2.12788>
2. <https://www.inaturalist.org/pages/about>
3. <https://ebird.org/about>

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